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AN ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF DOMESTIC FOOD PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined economic determinants of domestic food production in Nigeria. It used of secondary data which were drawn from various sources including Food and Agriculture Statistical Facts, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, World Hunger Index. The data spanned between 1981 and 2021. Descriptive and econometric (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) methods were employed for data analysis. Findings showed that in Nigeria, arable land, exchange rate, and food imports significantly affected domestic food production. It is, therefore, recommended that the vast uncultivated arable land be cultivated for more domestic food production to match the food need of the increasing population and to reduce food imports. Also, production of domestic agricultural inputs should be encouraged through the development of appropriate technology. This will bring about increase in domestic agricultural inputs, and consequent decrease in importation of agricultural inputs, thus reducing the influence of exchange rate on agricultural production.

KEYWORDS: Domestic Food Production, Food Import, Economic Determinants, and Undernourishment

INTRODUCTION

Food is the most essential and basic need of all humans. Provision of adequate quantity and quality of food, therefore, is one goal every country seeks to achieve and to sustain. This is one reason every country pursues veritable agricultural programmes to achieve

adequate food production. In Nigeria, from early 1970s to the present, various food production programmes have been adopted by successive governments to boost food production so as to balance food demand with food supply. Such programmes included Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) adopted in 1972, with the aim of increasing agricultural productivity, increasing incomes of farmers and raising the standard of living of the people, especially rural dwellers (Ojo, 1991). In 1974, the government established the National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFFP) which aimed at accelerating the rate of food production and reducing food imports. National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFFP) was in operation for only two years, and within this short period, it could not achieve its broad objectives. In 1976, NAFFP was replaced with Operations Feed the Nation (OFN), which aimed at producing enough food to feed the nation. In the same year, 1976, River Basin Development Authority (RBDA) was established with the aim to “regenerate rural agriculture, provide modern farm settlements with basic amenities such as electricity and water supply, create congenial environment in rural areas to discourage farm labour from migrating to urban centres” (Ekong, 1997). River Basin Development Authority (RBDA), which is still in operation, is yet to optimally deliver on its lofty objectives.

In 1980, the Green Revolution was adopted with the aim of revolutionizing agriculture in Nigeria. After six years, Directorate for Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) was established in 1986 to increase food production and reduce rural poverty. In 1990s, National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA) and National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) were adopted. The National Fadama Development Project was initiated to address some of the factors that militated against full realization of the benefits of agricultural production activities in some areas. Some of these factors were poor development of rural infrastructure, low investment in irrigation technology, poor organization of Fadama farmers, and limited access to foreign exchange for importation of irrigation equipment (CBN, 2010: 145). In 1998, National Special Programme on Food security (NSPFS) was adopted. This programme was jointly sponsored by the Federal Government and Food and Agricultural Organization, and was designed to be executed over a five-year period at the cost of US\$ 45.2million. The broad objective of NSPFS was to attain food security for the country. The National Special Programme on Food security (NSPFS) was supported by Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP) which was launched in 2003 to tackle the inadequate food situation in the country. Between 2011 and 2022, the government adopted various food production programmes such as National Food Security Programme (NFSP) and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), with a view to radically change Nigeria's agriculture, and rejuvenate the sector for improved food production.

However, global report of assessment of food situations in countries in the last decade placed Nigeria among food-insufficient countries in the world. As reported by IFPRI (2016) and FAO (2017) between 2014 and 2016, the number of people undernourished in Nigeria increased to an estimated 14.3 million, up from 10.2 million between 2010 and 2012. The number of people undernourished increased to 23.9 million between 2017 and 2019, while the number of severely food insecure people between 2014 and 2016 was estimated at 44.6 million, the highest in West Africa. The situation of food inadequacy in Nigeria placed the country in 90th position, with a score of 32% in a pool of 133 countries in global food security ranking by FAO in 2016 (FAO, 2017). In 2022, in Global Food Security assessment/ranking,

12.7% of population in Nigeria was undernourished, with 35.3% children stunted (IFPRI, 2022). This assessment placed Nigeria in 107th position, with a score of 42.0%, in a poll of 133 countries. This indicates that food supply in Nigeria is insufficient and inadequate. Food supply in any country comes from two main sources – local food production and food imports. From the literature, both domestic food production and food imports are determined by some factors. The objective of this study is to analyze economic determinants of domestic food production in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Theoretical Literature

Malthusian Theory of Population and Food Supply

Thomas Robert Malthus (1766 – 1834) was the first to address food scarcity as an issue in relation to growth in human population in relatively recent time. He developed his views on population in relation to food supply to contradict his father's perfectionist opinion that the human race was always improving (Samuelson and Nordhaus, 2010). In his work, “An Essay on the Principle of Production, as it affects the future improvement of society”, (Malthus, 1798) pointed that the growth of population is ultimately limited by the food supply. In other words, he postulated that population, when allowed to increase without limit, increases in a geometrical ratio while the food supply can, at least, increase in an arithmetical ratio, thus, making it impossible for agricultural production to sustain growing population indefinitely. Malthus (1798), therefore, hypothesized that “The power of population is indefinitely greater than the power in the earth to produce subsistence for man (Samuelson and Nordhaus, *ibid*). That is, growing global population will eventually eclipse the earth's capacity to feed it. The Malthusian theory of population growth in relation to food supply was based on the law of diminishing returns which explains that output from farm land would decrease as more and more of the poorer lands were brought into cultivation (even repeatedly) as a result of population pressure.

Malthus, in Blaug (1986), maintained that “Whatever the plausible rate of increase of the food requirements, an unchecked multiplication of human beings would quickly lead to standing room only”. It seemed obvious to him that something had to keep the population in check to prevent wholesome starvation. He said that there were two general kinds of checks that limit population growth - preventative checks and positive checks. Preventative checks reduce the birth rate while positive checks increase the death rate. In other words, he labelled preventive checks as “manifestations of vice”, which could be achieved through abortion and infanticide, which hold down the birth rate, while the positive checks he labelled as “manifestations of misery”, and can be achieved through war, famine, pestilence, etc., which increase death rate. He further asserted that population could be checked by “moral restraint”, meaning postponement of the age of marriage accompanied by strict-sexual abstinence before marriage and sexual restraint by married couples (Blaug, *Ibid*).

Malthusian Population Theory over the years has instigated intense arguments; while some scholars, demographers and development analysts are in support of the theory, some are in disagreement and of differing views.

Qays's Theory of Food Supply

Qays's theory of food supply is also known as theory of agricultural intensification. It was developed by Ester Boserup in 1965. Qays's theory is about the relationship between human population growth and food production. Boserup (1965), in her work "The conditions of agricultural growth: The Economics of agrarian change under population pressure" challenged Malthus' conclusion that the size of the human population is limited by the amount of food it can produce. Qays's theory in contrast states that "food production can and will increase to match the needs of the population". For instance, where population grows rapidly, the theory argues that the threat of starvation and the challenge of feeding more mouths will motivate people to improve their farming methods and invent new technologies in order to produce more food. Boserup (1965) described this as "agricultural intensification. According to Qays's theory, a farmer who has four fields to cultivate and produce food for his family might cultivate three of the fields, and leave the fourth field empty probably due to the ground being very dry, and would not support his crops. However, if the farmer has two more children, the pressure to produce more food might drive him to build irrigation canal to bring water to the fourth field or to buy a different type of seed that will grow in drier ground. He certainly would change the way he farms so as to make sure that he has enough food to support a large family (Boserup, 1965).

Boserup's theory seems to provide a model for continuous population growth. Boserup (1965) failed to consider that growth in human population is continuous, while agricultural land is static. The theory ignored the aspect of population density, increased urbanization and erosion which reduce the size of crop land yearly. According to Pimentel, Huang, Cordova and Pimentel (1997), about 33 per cent or 1.5 billion hectares of world crop land has been abandoned due to erosion. They attributed global food shortage to lower land productivity, which is as a result of continuous environmental degradation.

Empirical Literature

Credible evidences that point to the growing imbalance between demand for food and supply of food, especially in less-developed countries abound. Babatunde and Ajayi (2010) sought to investigate the relationship between population growth and production of selected food crops (maize, rice, beans, plantain, yam, cassava and groundnut) in rural areas in Western Nigeria. They adopted ordinary least square estimation. Results revealed an inverse relationship between population growth and growth of each of the food crops. That is, as population in rural areas increase, production of the food crops considered rather decreased. They attributed this to relegation of agriculture by many rural youths who migrate to urban areas in search of white-collar jobs. They recommended rapid government intervention in rural development and rural agriculture, as rural areas are the prime food producers in Nigeria.

Maisonet-Guzman (2011) observed that area of land dedicated to agriculture plays a central role in determining a countries agricultural production. However, some countries, especially in Africa, with vast areas of land dedicated to agriculture still experience low agricultural production due to poor and low level of modern technology. Recommendation, therefore, was that such countries should invest more in modern agricultural technology to increase agricultural production. Ojo and Adebayo (2012) assessed the state of food sufficiency in Nigeria by reviewing Nigeria's agricultural policies and programmes between 2000 and 2012. They observed that some agricultural policies and programmes adopted in

Nigeria though ideally sound were haphazardly implemented. They argued that there is a wide gap between agricultural policies and agricultural practices in Nigeria. Thus, they attributed the food scarcity in Nigeria largely to poor implementation of agricultural policies. They recommended agricultural policies that match agricultural practices in Nigeria.

Abdulrahman (2013) investigated the relationship between population growth and food security using agricultural production as a proxy for food security. He used Ordinary Least Square (OLS) in model estimation and data analysis. Findings revealed that food insecurity in Nigeria is largely due to rapid population growth which outmatches food production, as such, established family planning measures should be adopted to check the rapid population growth. Di-Marcantonio, *et al.*, (2014) carried out a study to investigate the determinants of food production in sub-Saharan Africa. They adopted a macro approach, with country level data for 41 sub-Saharan countries obtained from Food and Agriculture Organization Statics (FAOSTAT) and individual country data set. Their independent variables included agricultural land, irrigation, agriculture labour, inflation, conflicts, and number of tractors, food aid agricultural research, and governance. They used panel data regression technique with fixed and random effects for model estimation and analysis. Findings from their study showed, among others, that food production is usually and substantially low in landlocked countries and countries with prolonged conflicts. They also found out that food aid related negatively but significantly with local food production, while agricultural research related positively and significantly with local food production. They strongly recommended congenial macroeconomic environment and good governance with minimal conflict. For landlocked countries, with very low agricultural production, they recommended adequate technology transfer from the industrialized countries.

Anigbogu, *et al.*, (2015) sought to investigate the reasons the growth in food production and population growth are out of balance. Specifically, they sought to examine the socio-economic factors responsible for food production among cooperative farmers in Anambra state of Nigeria. They selected their sample and gathered their data by survey. Precisely, they adopted multi-stage sampling techniques to determine the sample size of their study from the three senatorial districts of the state. Two local governments were randomly selected from each senatorial district. Two towns were then selected from each local government; and from each town, two farmers cooperatives were randomly selected. The twenty-four farmers cooperatives selected comprised of 171 farmers to whom 171 copies of the questionnaire were administered out of which, 142 copies were completed and returned. The ordinary least square technique was what they used for model estimation and data analysis. The variables they considered included outputs of farmers, sizes of households, credit obtained by farmers, quantities of fertilizers, incomes of farmers, type of technology, soil fertility, sex, age, and educational qualification of farmers. All the variables, from the findings, related positively with farmers' output except sex and age, which related negatively. They recommended, among others, improvements in the provision of credits to cooperative farmers, by the government and financial institutions, to aid in the expansion of their farm activities. Also, to address the problem of shortage in agricultural labour, young graduates should be encouraged and incentivized to involve in agricultural activities

Matemilola and Elegbede (2017) investigated the challenges of food production in Nigeria using a descriptive approach. They assessed Nigeria's food production status prior to and after the discovery of oil up to 2016. In the findings, they observed that prior to the

discovery of oil in Nigeria in commercial quantity; Nigeria was food secure as the agricultural sector was given considerable regard and adequate attention, which enabled the sector to produce enough food to feed its population. However, since the discovery of oil, the agricultural sector has been relegated and, consequently its productivity has been decreasing. Also, they argued from the findings that of about 75 percent of Nigeria's land suitable agriculture, only 40 percent is actually cultivated. They identified the causes (challenges) of food security in Nigeria to include increasing population, decreasing per capita arable land, inadequate supply and deplorable state of infrastructure, inefficient agricultural policies, conflicts and civil insecurity, oil spillage, low level of technology in processing and storage of agricultural products. To bring Nigeria out of its food insecurity situation, they recommended adequate provision of basic infrastructure in rural communities, access roads, electricity, proper control of oil spillage, which negatively affects some farmlands and aquatic lives, improvement and adoption of congruent science and technology in processing and storage of agricultural produce.

Similarly, in 2018, Khan, *et al.*, sought to examine the key socio-economic determinants of food security in Jhang, one of the largest districts in Punjab, Pakistan. They adopted survey method and applied proportionate random sampling technique to select 200 households from whom data were drawn through questionnaire administration. In their study, per capita calorie intake was a proxy for food security, while independent variables of interest included age, sex, and education status of household heads, family size, and tenancy status, total earning hands, number of domestic animals, floods, and drought. Logit regression technique was used for data analysis. Findings showed that total earning hands, sex and education status of household, tenancy status determined the odds of being food secure, while total number of animals, floods, family size, draught and age of household head determined the odds of being food insecure. They recommended, among others, family planning though awareness campaigns use of modern technology in weather forecast to give timely information to farmer about some adverse, natural occurrences.

Similarly, Mota, *et al.*, (2019) assessed the determinants of food insecurity in rural households in Damot Gale Woreda, Wolaita zone of Southern Ethiopia. They used survey approach in which 155 households were randomly selected. They used logit regression technique for data analysis. The findings based on the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAC), revealed that about 71.6 percent of rural households in Damot Gale Woreda were food insecure. Large family size, low income, and fragmented farm lands were among the major determinants of food insecurity in the study area. They recommended family planning and income-generating activities to help rural households to be food secure.

Nigeria's Domestic Food Production: Agricultural Sector Performance

We will assess the performance of Nigeria's agricultural sector using share of agricultural output to gross domestic product, annual growth rate of agricultural production and growth in major crop production. Table 3.1 mirrors total real GDP, agriculture's contributions and the growth rates of the contributions.

Table 1: Contribution of Agriculture to GDP at 2010 Constant Basic Prices, GDP, (N Billion), 1990 – 2021 Year

Year (1)	Total GDP (2)	Share of Agriculture in Total GDP (3)	Share of Agriculture as % GDP (4)	Growth rate of Agricultural GDP (5)
1990	19,705.63	3,463.72	17.58	4.14
1991	19,19438	3,590.84	18.71	3.67
1992	19620-29	3,674.79	18.73	2.34
1993	19,927.39	3,748.47	18.81	2.01
1994	19,979.12	3,839.46	19.22	2.43
1995	20,353.28	3977.48	19.54	3.59
1996	21,177.32	4,131.55	19.51	3.87
1997	21,782.10	4,305.68	19.77	4.21
1998	22,332.87	4,475.24	20.04	3.94
1999	22,449.42	4,705.64	20.96	5.15
2000	22,688.23	4,840.87	21.34	2.87
2001	25,267.54	5,024.54	19.89	3.79
2002	28,967.71	7,817.38	26.99	55.58
2003	31,709.46	8,364.83	26.38	7.00
2004	35,020.55	8,388.57	23.95	0.28
2005	37,474.95	9,516.99	25.40	13.45
2006	39,995.50	10,222.47	25.56	7.41
2007	42,922.41	10,695.47	24.92	4.63
2008	46,012.52	11,645.,37	25.31	8.88
2009	49,856.10	12,330.33	24.73	5.88
2010	54,612.26	13,068.89	23.93	5.99
2011	57,511.04	13,439.38	23.37	2.83
2012	59,929.89	14,329.71	23.91	6.62
2013	63,218.72	14,750.52	23.33	2.94
2014	67,152.70	15,380.29	22.90	4.27
2015	69,022.03	15,052.22	21.81	- 2.13
2016	67531.36	16,407.34	24.30	9.00
2017	68,499.90	17,179.80	25.08	4.71
2018	69,815.02	17,544.15	25.13	2.12
2019	71,387.83	17,958.58	25.16	2.36
2020	70,014.37	18,348.18	26.21	2.17
2021	72,393.67	18,738.41	23.88	2.13

Sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Statistical Bulletin*, 2018: 111 – 112; 2022

Note: Columns 4 and 5 calculated by the authors from columns 2 and 3.

From Table 1, in 1990, real GDP was N19, 705.63 billion with agriculture's share of N3, 463.72 billion (17.58 %). Real GDP rose to N20, 353.28 billion with N3, 977.48 billion (19.54 %) as value added from agriculture. In 2002, real GDP reached N28, 907.71 billion to which agriculture contributed N7, 817.38 billion (26.99 %). In 2004, real GDP was N35, 020.55 billion, and agriculture contributed N8, 388.57 (23.95 %), 3.04 % less its contribution in 2002. In 2015, real GDP was N69, 022.03 billion, with N15, 052.22 billion (21.81 %) from agriculture. In 2018, real GDP was N69, 815.02 billion; agriculture contributed N17, 544.15 billion (25.13 %). In 2021, GDP was N72,393.67 billion, with N18,738.41 (23.88%) from agriculture.

Between 1998 and 2001, growth rates of GDP of agriculture were positive. In 2002, it increased by 55.58 %. Thereafter, it grew by 0.28 in 2005. Between 2009 and 2014, growth rates of GDP of agriculture were all positive but less 7 %. In 2015, it grew by – 2.13 %. In 2016, agriculture GDP grew by 9.00 %, and in 2017, it grew by 4.17 %. In 2018, share of agriculture to GDP grew by 2.12 %. In 2021, share of agriculture in GDP grew by 2.13%. Between 1990 and 2021, the period under review, growth rates of agriculture GDP fluctuated. The swings in growth rates of agriculture GDP indicate the undeveloped state of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, and that the sector is not self-sufficient in food production.

A consideration of growth in major crop production also portrays the performance agricultural sector in Nigeria. Growths in major crop production in recent past have not been impressive. Table 2 presents growth in major crop production in Nigeria between 2010 and 2018.

Table 2: Growth in major crop production

Crops	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Beans	6.1	6.5	4.2	3.2	1.7	4.3	2.2	1.1	2.2
Cassava	6.9	6.0	2.2	3.8	4.4	3.9	3.7	2.0	1.9
Cocoa	6.6	8.3	3.4	4.7	3.4	3.3	3.2	3.3	3.5
Maize	5.9	6.5	2.8	3.7	1.2	1.4	4.4	0.7	0.4
Millet	4.9	5.2	1.2	2.6	1.1	0.7	0.6	0.4	1.9
Palm oil	8.3	9.7	3.3	2.2	4.1	4.0	3.8	3.6	2.2
Plantain	5.5	6.5	2.7	2.1	2.6	4.4	2.5	2.0	3.5
Potatoes	5.8	6.8	4.1	4.0	3.1	4.5	3.2	1.3	2.0
Rice	4.0	5.0	2.4	4.0	4.1	4.0	3.7	2.6	5.4
Sorghum	4.0	5.4	3.1	3.3	1.3	4.1	5.5	1.8	2.0
Soya-beans	8.4	8.6	3.8	4.5	3.3	3.2	3.2	3.6	7.9
Wheat	5.5	6.3	2.6	2.3	2.6	2.4	5.5	2.2	3.3
Yam	4.8	5.4	1.4	3.4	0.1	3.8	1.6	0.3	2.9

Sources: Compiled from:

1. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2011, p.129
2. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2014, p.141
3. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2016, p.193
4. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) *Annual Report*, 2019, p.183

From Table 2, growth in beans production was 6.1 % in 2010 and 6.5 % in 2011. In 2016, beans production grew by 1.1 %, and in 2017 it grew by 1.1 %. It grew by 2.2 % in 2018. Cassava production grew by 6.9 % and 6.0 % in 2010 and 2011, respectively. In 2017 growth in cassava production was 2.0 % and 1.9 % in 2018. In the same vein, cocoa production which grew by 6.6 % and 8.3 %, in 2010 and 2011, respectively, reduced to 3.3 % in 2017, and rose marginally to 3.5 % in 2018. In 2010 and 2011, maize production in Nigeria grew by 5.9 % and 6.5 %, respectively. In 2017, growth in maize production reduced to 0.7 %. It further reduced to 0.4 % in 2018. Growth in production of potatoes was 5.8 % in 2010, and rose to 6.8 % in 2011. In 2017 it reduced to 1.3 %, and grew marginally to 2.0 % in 2018. Wheat production grew by 5.5 % in 2010. It increased to 6.3 % in 2011. It reduced to 2.2 % in 2017, then rose slightly to 3.3 % in 2018. In the same direction of wheat production, palm oil production grew by 8.3 % in 2010 and increased to 9.7 % in 2011. It reduced to 3.6 % in 2017 and further to 2.2 % in 2018. Production of yam has also reduced. In 2010, yam production grew by 4.8 %, and increased to 6.3 % in 2011. It reduced to 1.6 % in 2016 and further to 0.3 % in 2017. It marginally grew by 2.9 % in 2018. Rice production increased by 4.0 % in 2010, in 2011 it grew by 5.0 %. In 2012 and 2017, growth in rice production in Nigeria reduced to 2.4 % and 2.6%, respectively. However, it rose by 5.4 % in 2018. Soya-beans production in 2010 increased by 8.4 % in 2010 and increased to 8.6 % in 2011. Thereafter, it reduced to 3.8 % in 2012 and further to 3.2 % in 2015 and maintained same in 2016. It grew sluggishly by 3.6 %. In 2018 Soya-beans production increased by 7.9 %. From the above analysis, there has been a general decrease in the growth of domestic production of major crops in Nigeria for some years now.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to examine the determinants domestic food production in Nigeria. Based on this objective, the functional relationship is specified as in Equation 1

$$\text{Equation 1: } AGDP = f(AL, EXR, GEA, POP, IR, CPI)$$

where: AL is arable land, GEA is government expenditure on agriculture, POP is population, IR is interest rate, EXR is exchange rate, and CPI is consumer price index.

For econometric analysis, equation 1 is stated in a linear form as in Equation 2.

$$\text{Equation 2: } AGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 AL + \alpha_2 EXR + \alpha_3 GEA + \alpha_4 POP + \alpha_5 IR + \alpha_6 CPI + U$$

Where α_0 is the intercept of the model, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5$ and α_6 are slope coefficients (that is, partial elasticities of agricultural output to percentage of arable land (AL), exchange rate (EXR), government expenditure on agriculture (GEA), population (POP), interest rate (IR) and consumer price index (CPI), respectively. A priori, in equation (3.4), the independent variables were expected to assume either positive or negative values depending on their relationship with the dependent variable. Thus, $\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_4 > 0$; $\alpha_2, \alpha_5, \alpha_6 < 0$, and U is the error term, which captures other variables which may affect agricultural output in Nigeria but not taken into account explicitly in the model.

The study used time series data from secondary sources - the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin (various issues), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Statistical Facts, Food Security Indicators, National Population Commission Official Gazette (1991 and 2006), World Development Indicators (WDI) (various issues), World Development

Reports (WDR) (various issues), Global hunger index, State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World, World Food Programme.

The study adopted the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method for model estimation and analysis, since the data for the study were stationary at both 1(0) and 1(1), from the stationarity test. Moreover, the ARDL has its inbuilt error correction mechanism. It permits variables to have different optimal lags, and allows for simultaneous estimation of the long-run and short-run coefficients of the model as the error correction term is taken care of by the lagged period. With appropriate number of lags, ARDL addresses the problem of auto correlation and endogeneity (Parasan, *et al.*, 2001).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unit Root Test

The Kwiatkowski – Phillips – Schmidt - Shin and Ng – Perron tests for unit root were adopted. The results are reported in the table below

Table 3: Unit root test results

Kwiatkowski – Phillips – Schmidt – Shin Test				Ng – Perron tests		
Variab les	Level	CV 1 %	Order of Integration	Level	CV 5%	Order of Integration
AGDP	0.6707***	0.7390	1(0)	-6.4193***	-2.5800	1(0)
AL	0.5879***	0.7390	1(0)	-2.9694***	-2.5800	1(1)
CPI	0.6845***	0.7390	1(0)	-10.4688***	-2.5800	1(1)
EXR	0.4157***	0.7390	1(1)	-2.8509***	-2.5800	1(1)
GEA	0.7185***	0.7390	1(0)	-3.9474***	-2.5800	1(1)
IR	0.1793***	0.7390	1(1)	-3.0095***	-2.5800	1(1)
POP	0.4631***	0.7390	1(1)	-6.6298***	-2.5800	1(0)

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0

*** indicates stationarity at 1 percent level of significance

** indicates stationarity at 5 percent level of significance

The unit root test results in Table 3 show that our variables are stationary at level, 1(0) and first difference 1(1) at 1 % and 5 % levels of significance. The mixed order of integration necessitated the use of ARDL approach for estimation.

ARDL Bound Test Result

The result of the bound test is reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Bound Test Results

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	15.60085	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.

As Table 4 shows, our calculated F-statistic of 15.6 is greater than the lower and upper bounds values of 2.27 and 3.28 respectively at 5% percent level of significance. This implies that there is a long run cointegrating relationship among the variables in the model.

Model Selection Criteria

Next, we subjected our model to lag length selection. This ensures that information about the relationship is not lost to inappropriate lag specification. Relying on Akaike information criteria for lag selection the lag specification of: ARDL (2, 3, 3, 0, 3, 2, 2) was Selected for the analysis and reported on Figure 1

Figure 1: Model Selection

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0

Short run relationship between AGDP and its determinants

Table 5: Short Run Result
Dependent Variable: (AGDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
(AGDP(-1))	0.228863	0.084822	2.698159	0.0183
(AL)	-1.675785	0.302119	-5.546765	0.0001
(AL(-1))	1.486956	0.304576	4.882048	0.0003
(AL(-2))	0.489935	0.209848	2.334712	0.0362
(EXR)	-0.033803	0.033027	-1.023514	0.3247
(EXR(-1))	-0.495315	0.043119	-11.48707	0.0000
(EXR(-2),	-0.476556	0.039951	-11.92861	0.0000
(GEA)	0.044411	0.026930	1.694104	0.1231
(POP)	1.497416	3.568021	0.419677	0.6816
(POP(-1))	-4.676368	5.081512	-0.920271	0.3742
(POP(-2))	22.32625	3.557148	6.276445	0.0000
(IR)	-0.064459	0.082239	-0.783798	0.4472
(IR(-1))	0.268259	0.084396	3.178570	0.0073
(CPI)	1.166324	0.109884	10.61416	0.0000
(CPI(-1))	-0.695918	0.109864	-6.334385	0.0000
ECM (-1)	-1.323213	0.095492	-13.85678	0.0000
R-squared	0.951872	Mean dependent var		-0.002585
Adjusted R-squared	0.918182	S.D. dependent var		0.181090
S.E. of regression	0.051799	Akaike info criterion		-2.785378
Sum squared resid	0.053662	Schwarz criterion		-2.118801
Log likelihood	63.74412	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.555276
Durbin-Watson stat	1.948391			

Source: Authors' computation from E views 10.0

The agricultural production model shows economic factors that affect agricultural production in Nigeria within the period under review. The significant value of ECM - 1.32 shows the speed of adjustment of agricultural production (AGDP) to its past and present values, and past levels of AL, EXR, GEA, POP, IR AND CPI.

From Table 5, the coefficient of arable land is – 1.6757, which indicates that there is a negative relationship between arable land and AGDP in Nigeria. However, one-year lag of arable land (AL) showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP with a coefficient of 1.4869 which implies that a hectare increase in arable land would increase AGDP by N1.49 billion. Also, two-year lag of arable land (AL) showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP with a coefficient of 0.4899 which implies that a hectare increase in arable land would increase AGDP by N49 billion.

The coefficient of exchange rate is – 0.0338, which implies a negative relationship in the short run between exchange rate and AGDP. However, the relationship is insignificant. Nevertheless, past relationship between exchange rate and AGDP also shows negative but significant relationship at 5 % level of significance with coefficient of - 0.4953. This implies that a 1% decrease in the value of the naira relative to the dollar (US \$) would cause AGDP to decrease by about N49.5 billion. Government expenditure on agriculture (GEA) related

positively with agricultural GDP; however, the relationship was not significant at 5 % level of significance.

The coefficient of population is 1.4974. This indicates a positive relationship between population and agricultural output in Nigeria, that is, increase in population would lead to increase in agricultural output. However, the relationship was not significant. Nevertheless, two-year lag in population showed positive and significant relationship with agricultural output at 5 % with a coefficient of 22.3262. This implies that 1 % increase in population would increase AGDP by N22.33 billion. Interest rate with coefficient of – 0.0645 related negatively with agricultural output. This implies that a percentage increase in interest rate would reduce AGDP by N6.5 billion. However, the relationship was not significant.

The relationship between Consumer price index (CPI) and agricultural GDP is positive and significant at 5 % level of significance with a coefficient of 1.1663. This implies that a 1 % increase in CPI would increase agricultural GDP lead to N1.17 billion.

The Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.95 shows that there is no serial correlation in the model. The adjusted R² of 0.9181 shows that about 92 % variation in the dependent variable (AGDP) is explained by the independent variables.

Long run Analysis between AGDP and its determinants

Table 6: Long Run Estimates

Dependent variable: AGDP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
(AL)	-2.561288	0.684093	-3.744062	0.0025
(EXR)	0.397301	0.119248	3.331721	0.0054
(GEA)	0.033563	0.020852	1.609559	0.1315
(POP)	0.284403	2.600768	0.109353	0.9146
(IR)	-0.204423	0.247440	-0.826154	0.4236
(CPI)	0.821790	0.146949	5.592331	0.0001
C	0.018059	0.022790	0.792410	0.4423

Source: Authors' computation from E views 10.0

In the long run, from Table 6, the coefficient of arable land is – 2.5613. This implies that arable land has negative relationship with agricultural output, and the relationship is significant at 5 % level of significance.

In the long run, it is observed that exchange rate, that is, the rate at which the naira is exchanged for dollar, plays a positive and significant role in agricultural production in Nigeria with a coefficient of 0.3973. This implies that a percentage increase in exchange rate would increase AGDP by N39.7 billion

Government expenditure on agriculture (GEA) in the long run has a coefficient of 0.0336, which implies positive relationship with agricultural output; however, the relationship is not significant at 5 % level of significance. Population with a coefficient of 0.2844 also plays a positive role in agricultural production in Nigeria; however, the relationship is not significant at 5 % level of significance.

Interest rate in the long run has a coefficient of -0.2044 , which implies negative relationship with agricultural output. That is, a 1 % increase in interest rate would cause agricultural GDP to decrease by N20 billion. However, the relationship is insignificant. Consumer Price Index in the long run relates with agricultural GDP positively. Consumer Price Index, as we know is the measure of how the cost of purchasing a given basket of consumer good changes over time; so, as CPI increases, agricultural GDP also increases.

Stability results

The stability result of our model is reported in Figure 4.2. The cumulative sum of squares graph shows the parameter estimates fall within an acceptable confidence interval at 5 % level of significance. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from the results are reliable.

Figure 2: Stability results

Source: Authors' computation from E-views 10.0s

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The short run result exhibited negative and significant relationship between arable land and domestic food production in Nigeria which does not agree with a priori expectation. This may be attributed to increasing insecurity (herdsmen attacks on farmers) in many parts of the country. The attacks have, in recent times, caused some rural farmers to abandon their farmlands with consequent decrease in domestic food production. The one – year lag of exchange rate showed negative and significant relationship with domestic food production. This is because some agricultural inputs are imported and valued in dollar; and the value of the naira has been decreasing consistently relative to dollar. So, with the decreased value of the naira, less agricultural inputs would be imported, given the existing level of technology in agriculture in Nigeria, agricultural output will decrease. The two-year lag in population which showed positive and significant relationship with AGDP implies that, as population grows, demand for food would increase, and this would induce agricultural intensification with resultant growth in agricultural production nay food production. This agrees with Qays's theory of agricultural intensification by Busarup (1965) which argued that as population

increases, food production, through agricultural intensification, can and will increase to match the food needs of the people.

The long run negative and significant relationship between arable land and agricultural output was not in agreement with theoretical a priori expectation. Some probable factors might have caused the negative relationship given the Nigerian economy. Due to increased urbanization, there is a deterioration in the quality of marginal lands which leads to low productivity. In Nigeria, rural – urban migration is increasing, due to the quest for white-collar jobs, among other factors. Many people pursue formal education in order to secure formal employment either with the government or with the private sector. As we know arable land abound in the rural areas, so as rural-urban migration increases, agricultural labour in rural areas will decrease with consequent decrease in food production. In addition, our cultural perception of involvement in agriculture is discouraging as it is associated with third class (poor) citizens. This perception could make some rural youths who do not migrate to urban areas to dissociate themselves from agricultural activities. This again will reduce agricultural labour with consequent decrease in domestic food production. This, therefore, suggests that some part of arable land in the rural areas will be uncultivated, and this will lead to low agricultural production.

The long run positive and significant relationship between exchange rate and AGDP suggests that, given the long-time of consistent decrease in the value of the naira, that is, persistent increase in exchange rate and persistent rise in prices of food items, the prices at which agricultural products are sold in Nigeria support importation of agricultural inputs for more agricultural activities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The determinants of domestic food production as specified in our Model were examined and the results showed that the key determinants of domestic food production in the short run were arable land (AL) and consumer price index (CPI). However, a one-period and a two-period lag in exchange rate showed negative but significant relationship with domestic food production. Also, a two-period lag in population showed positive and significant relationship with domestic food production. In the long run, the results showed that the key determinants of domestic food production were arable land (AL), exchange rate (EXR) and consumer price index (CPI). The Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.95 showed that there was no serial correlation in the model. The adjusted R^2 of 0.918 showed that about 92 % of variation in the dependent variable (AGDP) is explained by the independent variables. In Nigeria, arable land, exchange rate and consumer price index significantly affect domestic food production. Generally, in Nigeria, domestic food production has been decreasing while food import has been increasing making the country to be food import dependent and one that cannot feed itself.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study the following recommendations are made.

- i. Vast uncultivated land in the rural areas should be cultivated. This can be done through special incentives (free agricultural grants, modern agricultural equipment, processing and storage facilities) to the youths who involve in agriculture in the rural areas. This will encourage optimal cultivation of vast uncultivated arable land

and discourage rural-urban migration.

- ii. Exchange rate has been identified as a significant determinant of domestic food production, as many agricultural inputs have been imported. Production of domestic agricultural inputs should, therefore, be encouraged through domestic industries. This, in turn, will bring about decrease in importation of agricultural inputs, thus reducing the influence of exchange rate on agricultural production.

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DIVINATION AND MENTAL HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR OF THE IBIBIO PEOPLE OF SOUTHERN NIGERIA: A QUALITATIVE EXPLORATION

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined divination and mental health seeking behaviour of Ibibio People in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researcher made use of Mental Health Seeking Behaviour Model (MHSBM). Ibibio-speaking local government areas were purposively selected, and clustered into the 3 existing senatorial districts. Study participants were randomly selected from 16 Ibibio clans from randomly selected Ibibio-speaking local government areas. Study participants were engaged in interviews and their socio-demographic data collected were also presented with respective narratives. The findings of the study were analyzed qualitatively in thematic analysis with excerpts from the study participants. The findings of the study revealed that Ibibio people have a great belief that mental illness is spiritually influenced and priority is given to treatment with spiritual powers which diviners are usually patronized in terms of mental health services. It was concluded that divination become the preferred option for knowing the cause of the mental illness and for the control of the spirit in order to subject the patient to effective treatment; and most of the Ibibio people chose not to go to psychiatric hospitals for treatments to avoid the cultural implication of stigmatization which also contributes to the high dependency on divination and other forms of treatments. The researchers among others recommended that the Ibibio people should be educated on the causes of mental health and illnesses in order to reduce the stigmatization among the people and encourage patronage of psychiatric hospitals throughout Akwa Ibom State.

KEYWORDS: Mental illness, divination, Ibibio people, and health-seeking behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Positive mental health is linked to a range of development outcomes and is fundamental to coping with adversity, while poor mental health impedes an individual's capacity to realize their potential, work productively, and contribute to their community (World Health Organization 2012, cited in Azeem 2014). Every human being is a constitution of both mental and physical states and the health and wellbeing of any individual is ultimately dependent on the inter-relationship that exist between the physical and mental health (Kolappa *et al*, 2013). The disharmony between the mental and physical states results in a condition called mental illness, and mental illness, also called mental disorder or psychiatric illness is a disorder characterized by psychological symptoms, abnormal behaviours, impaired functioning or any combination of these (American Psychological Association APA, 2005).

Mental illness is said to refer to a wide range of mental health disorders that affect the mood, thinking, behaviour and one's ability to function in social, work or family activities (APA, 2018 cited in Esen and Peters, 2023^a). Mental health disorders according to Jack-Ide, Uys and Middleton (2013) constitute the major causes of disabilities worldwide, accounting for 37% of all healthy life years lost through disease. It is also universal, affecting people of all countries and societies, regardless of age, gender and income (Esen and Peters, 2023^a). The prevalence of mental illness in the adult population at any given time is about 10% and similarly, around 20% of all patients seen by primary health care providers have one or more mental health disorders (Cuijpers and Stam 2003). Mental health according to Stein (2013) cited in Esen and Peters (2023^b) could be seen as the successful performance of mental functions resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships, and the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. The reverse is mental illness.

Mental illness is considered to be a clinical significant behavioural or psychological syndrome experienced by a person and marked by distress, disability or the risk of suffering disability or loss of freedom (Mohr, 2003). Mental health could be characterised by alterations in reasoning, emotional mood or behaviour that is capable of causing distress, impaired ability to function or both (Esen and Peters 2023^b). Stein *et al*, (2010) defined mental illness as a psychological syndrome or pattern which is associated with distress (e.g. via a painful symptom), disability (impairment in one or more important areas of functioning), increased risk of death, or causes a significant loss of autonomy; however it excludes normal responses such as grief from loss of a loved one, and also excludes deviant behaviour for political, religious, or societal reasons not arising from a dysfunction in the individual. Mental illness as defined by Mental Health Association in Forsyth County (2009) is a disease of the brain that causes mild to severe disturbances in thought processes and/or behaviour, resulting in an inability to cope with life's ordinary demands and routines. Mental Health Association (2009) posit that there are more than 200 classified forms of mental illness. Some of the more common disorders are: clinical depression, bipolar disorder, dementia, schizophrenia and anxiety disorders (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). Mental illness according to Mental Health Association (2009) therefore involves expression of distress, an inability to be independent as well as alteration of mood, behaviour or thought due to a malfunctioning of a certain human organ responsible for these or any of these.

Regarding the nature, causes, and treatments of mental health issues, various societies throughout the world have different explanations (Ahmed *et al.*, 2015). These viewpoints are the outcome of specific societal cultural practices that are deeply ingrained in people's reasoning, behaviour, and speech (Esen and Peters, 2023^c). As the most suitable foundation for the creation of mental health programs, the community's role in the prevention and care of the mentally handicapped is now widely acknowledged (Kabir *et al.*, 2004). Numerous studies have demonstrated that understanding how the general public views mental illness and its treatment is a crucial first step toward the implementation of effective community-based programmes (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). The understanding, treatment, and management of mental health disorders are greatly influenced by the norms, beliefs, and practices of the person's cultural surroundings (Kabir *et al.*, 2004).

According to Shaikh and Hatcher (2005), a community's health-seeking behaviour influences how health services are used, which in turn affects population health outcomes. According to Subhudi (2015), up to 70% to 80% of mentally ill people live in rural areas, visit places of worship first, and seek treatment from indigenous practitioners. Factors influencing health-seeking behaviour can be political, cultural, socioeconomic, or physical. Indeed, cultural norms, economic conditions, and educational attainment can all have an impact on how a person uses the healthcare system (Esen and Peters, 2023^c). Additional variables include the surrounding environment, socio-demographic characteristics, and one's understanding of the healthcare system, gender issues, political climate, and facilities (Ogunlesi and Olanrewaju, 2010). There has been little research conducted in the South Southern region of Nigeria, but research on health seeking behaviour during mental illness has been conducted in several other parts of the world. There is ample evidence of how those who are mentally ill and their loved ones tackle mental illness in an attempt to find relief or a cure. It is commonly known, according to Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) that sub-Saharan Africa lacks access to timely and efficient professional mental health services, which are necessary to prevent chronic illness and the development of irreversible sequelae.

Similarly, Burns and Tomita (2015) noted that a lack of appropriate infrastructure, human resources, and treatment options contributes to a significant treatment gap for mental health in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health data reveals widespread, systematic, and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low-income and middle-income countries; nowhere is this more evident than on the African continent (Burns and Tomita, 2015). Similarly, Burns and Tomita (2015) noted that a lack of appropriate infrastructure, human resources, and treatment options contributes to a significant treatment gap for mental health in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health data reveals widespread, systematic, and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low-income and middle-income countries; nowhere is this more evident than on the African continent (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Researchers have found relative levels of efficacy on the perceived efficacy of traditional and alternative mental health care, which may have maintained their belief and patronage in low-income countries. According to Abbo (2011), who examined the results and profiles of traditional healing practices for severe mental illnesses in two districts of Eastern Uganda, there was a general trend in the symptom scales of a cohort of patients with severe

mental illness who saw traditional healers to show a reduction at the three- and six-month follow-ups. In contrast, patients with mania had the biggest overall improvement at three months (54.0%), followed by those with psychotic depression (42.0%) and schizophrenia (14.8%), in terms of patients' cutoff points for diagnosis. Six months later, the proportion of patients who showed an improvement was as follows: mania (58.3%), psychotic depression (46.4%), and schizophrenia (30.7%) (Esen and Peters, 2023).

Nonetheless, Burns and Tomita (2015) observed that in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), a significant percentage of people seeking treatment for mental disorders consult traditional and religious healers in their pathway to mental health care. This is in their study *Traditional and religious healers in the pathway to care for people with mental disorders in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. The care pathway may be delayed as a result of healers' early involvement, which could be a barrier to early detection and intervention. However, this suggests that traditional and religious healers are unable to effectively treat mental illness, which may lead to patients and their loved ones looking for alternative—typically orthodox—forms of treatment (Burns and Tomita, 2015). Burns and Tomita further argued that since herbalists, diviners, and faith healers have all been identified as traditional and religious healers in this study, an understanding of the patronage of these healers in Nigeria and other African nations will help to clarify the patterns of health-seeking behavior among the mentally ill in these regions, which serves as the foundation for this study.

Sorsdahl *et al.* (2009) found that of the participants who sought treatment (regardless of whether they met lifetime DSM-IV criteria for a disorder or not), 21% were treated by Western practitioners, 13% by alternative practitioners, and 7% by a combination of both Western and alternative practitioners. The study examined the role of traditional healers in the treatment of common mental disorders in South Africa. Six percent of the participants who sought treatment from alternative medicine did so from a traditional healer, seven percent from a spiritual or religious advisor, and two percent from a different kind of healer. But only 2% of research participants exclusively sought treatment from a traditional healer, compared to 14% who sought treatment from a Western practitioner (Sorsdahl *et al.*, 2009).

In a study conducted in 2009 by Adewuya and Makanjuola titled *Preferred Treatment for Mental Illness Among Southwestern Nigerians*, the results revealed that 844 (41%) study participants chose spiritual healers as their preferred treatment option, compared to 634 (30%) who chose traditional healers and 600 (29%) who chose Western medicine. Additionally, they discovered that endorsement of supernatural causal beliefs, being a woman, having a lower level of education, and never having provided care for a person with mental illness were the factors that were independently associated with preference for spiritual or traditional healers. Subsequent examination of the data by Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) revealed that there was no gender difference in the options available to traditional healers, with the majority of the gender difference being in the spiritual healers' category.

The majority of participants (76.8%) in Effiong and Albert's (2016) study, *Pathways to Psychiatric Care among Patients with Schizophrenia in Nigeria*, chose non-orthodox treatment facilities as their first choice for mental health assistance. According to the study, this

group includes (11.1%) of participants who saw traditional healers for the first time and (65.7%) of those who sought treatment from religious healers as their first point of contact. Prior to receiving care in a tertiary psychiatric facility, 41.7 percent of participants visited a second religious treatment center, and 36.8 percent visited a third, according to the study.

With 3.1 million members, or roughly 60% of the state's total population, the Ibibio tribe is the largest in Akwa Ibom State (Esen and Peters 2023^a). This is indicated by the fact that the tribe comprises about 16 of the state's 36 Local Government Areas (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). With their unique customs, culture, ethics, and more, the Ibibio are among the oldest ethnic groups in Nigeria, with a unique cultural heritage that spread across the Ibibio Local Government Area (Paul and Peters, 2023). The Ibibio people are renowned for their unique cultural belief in spirit beings and ancestors who live in the afterlife exactly as they did in this life, determine these. The belief also suggests that the spirit being has the ability to affect human affairs, such as health, the economy, and favour (Esen and Peters, 2023^b). Health issues are typically believed to be associated with offences against the deities, gods, and/or ancestors. In the cultural practice of health management in Ibibio land, the appeasement of the gods or deities is a necessity.

The symptoms one assumes or hears about are indicative of the nature of the illness. Youths have always characterised the largest population and are the driving force of our society (Peters, *et al*, 2022; Peters *et al*, 2023). Noticeable among the Ibibio people has been the fact that youths form the age cohort which is mostly affected by mental illness. This can be traced to the fact that youths are mostly involve in abusive consumption of psychoactive substances. According to Peters and Bassey (2020), youths in Akwa Ibom State especially in the riverine areas depend on one form or drug or the other for their daily activities like boat peddling, dragging of fishing nets and cutting of timbers.

Most often, divinity is invoked to aid in the diagnosis process. All of these are reliant on the Ibibio people's cultural heritage. Religion is a central theme in almost everything in Ibibio. It is believed that spiritual forces control everything from conception to childbirth, fertility, health, fortune, and even social influence (Oreva 2018). The Ibibio adage "*Obut isi mummo Idat ase omum eyeneka Idat*" (the shame of madness does not bother the mad person but his or her family members) indicates that mental illness is not foreign to Ibibio culture. The Ibibio people have made efforts to demystify the issue so that a permanent solution can be given to this illness, which is assumed to affect family members more than the mentally ill.

The lack of access to orthodox mental healthcare in Nigeria causes those who are mentally ill to look for other ways to get well. Gureje and Lasebikan (2006) noted that traditional, spiritual, faith-healing, and complementary medicine fill the service gap left by orthodox mental health practice in Nigeria. These practices are widely used in most communities because the general public's perception of mental disorders is still rooted in superstitious belief systems, particularly among the Ibibio people, and is therefore seen as incurable with western medicine. The present study aimed to bridge the existing gap in understanding the extent and rationale behind the Ibibio people's recourse to diviners as a mental health care alternative.

Source: Esen and Peters (2023^b)

The major components of MHSBM include;

Family of the patients: The family of the mentally ill person is the one who bear the burden of seeking treatment and healing for the said patient (their son/daughter).

Collective Perceived Threat: This refers to the consequences and cost (shame, disgrace, losses through violent behaviour of the patients, etc.), that the family stands to suffer if the said patient (their son/daughter) is not treated and restored to normal health or healed on time.

Collective Belief: This refers to the agreement of the family on a given choice of treatment based on the likely perceived benefits of the choice. This is also based on the level of availability of resources that the family will depend upon throughout the process of treating the said patient (their son/daughter).

Collective Behaviour: This refers to the response of the family toward the treatment/healing of the said patient (their son/daughter). This is based on the likely benefits that the family perceives in available treatment options, which is also based on the availability of resources that will enhance patronage of such available treatment options by the family.

Cue to Action: This refers to a readiness to take action toward the treatment of the said patient (their son/daughter).

METHODOLOGY

An ethnographic research design was adopted with a multi-stage type of data collection approach. The study area was Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of over five million people (NPC, 2006). The study was conducted among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. The Ibibio people are a coastal people in southern Nigeria (Cole and Derk, 2012). They are mostly found in Akwa Ibom State. They are related to the Anaang, Efik and Oron people. The Annang, Efik, and Oron share personal names, culture, and traditions with the Ibibio, and speak closely related varieties of Ibibio-Efik which are more or less mutually intelligible (Esen and Peters, 2023). The one local government area was selected from the three senatorial districts in Akwa Ibom State. Onna,

Etinan, and Ini Local Government Areas were selected for the study.

The researchers adopted a big-net approach (Fatterman, 2010) to gather information from the study participants. Participant observation, in-depth interview (II), key informant interview (KII), and focus group discussions (FGDs) were used by the researchers to obtain primary data. Secondary data were collected through published materials and internet sources.

RESULT

Divination Practice and knowing the cause of mental illness

Divination is the practice of consulting the spirit world in order to know the cause or causes of events or happenings within the traditional society. Diviners' consultation has been part of the cultural practices of the Ibibio people and has influenced their ways of life over generations. According to gathered information from discussions and interviews, the relevance of diviners is reducing across Ibibio land, and their functions have been taken over by the new dimension of the Christian movement especially the prayer house movement of Christianity. The majority of the study respondents agreed in their responses to the fact that divination is no longer relevant in the treatment of illness since people are more interested in solutions than getting to know the source of their illnesses or who is behind their problems.

A study participant aged 48 years in his response to an interview said;

We are no longer interested in who is responsible for our problems or sickness because we have heard enough from all these prophets and prophetesses neither are we interested in knowing the source of any problem or sickness. All we are now looking for are solutions to our diverse problems and healing to our sicknesses (Male, 48 years, interviewed on 22/8/2019).

Mental illness is a health condition that forces everyone around the patient to focus on a solution instead of concentrating on the source of the illness. Gathered information revealed that it is only on rare occasions that people care to know who is responsible for or the source of the mental condition of their relatives. One of the key informants from Ikot Okpudo in Nsit Ubium Local Government Area, in his responses, said;

People are not really interested in knowing who is responsible for their problems, what they are really after is solutions, if they can get the solution, they easily forget about how it happened, what they have passed through while trying to get to the solution, talk more of source or who is responsible. Their joy especially in the case of madness is always so much that they will not want to know any other thing. It has been only on very rare occasion right from the days of my father till today that someone will want to know who is responsible for the mental health condition of their relative (Male, 38 years, interview conducted on 24/8/2019).

Though interest in divination is fading away among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State due to the influence of Christianity, study participants revealed that very few persons on

special demands do request divination services in knowing what and who is/are responsible for the problem. A key informant from Nkwot Etok in Ini Local Government Area said;

Well, I have been in this practice for many years, people have brought their patients to me from far and near, I have treated them, and they do recover but only on special requests have I seen a few persons ask to know in form of consulting the office of the diviner priest, and I collect from them what I have to collect and consult for them. I told them who was responsible and why those who plotted the evil against me wanted to get out of their brothers' madness (Male, 50 years, interview conducted on 26/8/2019).

Divination has not been a treatment method for mental illness among the Ibibio, but a way to discover or inquire about the source or who is responsible for a particular mental illness. Information gathered from the participants revealed that divination practice is in most cases combined by traditional herbalists. The office of divination is always consulted for inquiry of the ancestors of gods. Christianity has greatly reduced the influence of divination and the relevance of diviners.

Divination Practice and Seeking control of the spirit of madness

Seeking to know which spirit is responsible for the mental illness among the people is one of the reasons Ibibio people consult diviners as gathered by the data through interviews. Narratives revealed that behind seeking to know what spirit is responsible is the aim of seeking control of such spirit. Study participants agreed through interviews and discussion that many people especially relatives of mentally ill persons do seek to control the spirits that are responsible for the mental illness in order to see how to rescue their victims from the forces of such spirits. One of the study participants in her narratives reported that;

We believe that madness or mental sickness is controlled by the spirit. In fact, whenever anybody has a mental problem these evil spirits will come into such a person and overtake the person. You can remember in the Bible that the mad man that Jesus healed by casting out legions was a lesson to us that spirits are responsible for madness and Jesus was able to control these spirits. So most of our people....ah, ah, ah, including me, oh, we believe that spirits are responsible for madness and to cure madness you have to control the spirits. That is why our people patronize these diviners for help (Female, 46 years, trader, interviewed on 17/9/2023).

Observations from fieldwork show that most of the mentally ill persons are forced under control in order to subject them to treatments. Diviners are specialist in controlling the mentally ill person and subject such to treatment. One of the key informant who is a specialist as a diviner in treating mental illness in his narratives said that;

I have been in this business since I was a young boy with my late father who was in-charge before he handed over to me just before his death. I was taught that the only way you can treat a violent mad man or what you call mental sick person is to control him or her,

else you cannot treat the person. This is because the person will not collect such thing as medicine from you. Sometimes the spirit will not allow the person to collect anything that can give the person relieve from the power of madness. So, my father taught me how to use this grass called “*Mkpa tatad*“ which is has a tiny rod and I will tie them with the robe from the grass and they will be calm and the spirit will be controlled and the person will be subjected to treatment. There was a time they brought a young man with chains to me and when they pulled him out of the car and he saw me, he started screaming and tore the chains into pieces and wanted to run away, but because I always have *mkpa tatad* with me, I quickly rush and flog him with the grass and he began to beg and be calm. Else, he would have ran away and the family will not see him again. But, thank God, today he is normal because he was healed and returned home to his family (Male, 58 years, interview conducted on 26/8/2019)

Divination has been a cultural practice in African Traditional Medicine (ATR) where its major practice is for the control and consultation of the spirits. In the case of mental illness, divination has played great role by diviners who through this mean have claimed to have treated many mentally ill person who were free from the illness. Among the Ibibio people, divination is one of the major means of seeking treatment and other solutions to man's problems.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

On general knowledge about mental illness, findings show that Ibibio people consider mental illness to be caused by spiritual forces which create the basis for high level of diviners' consultation. There is a high level of belief that some spiritual forces are responsible for mental illness. This situation and belief system greatly affects the mental health seeking behaviour of the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State. On choice of treatment for mental illness, finding's show that since Ibibio people believe that mental illness is spiritually controlled, the first and best choice of treatment as revealed through discussions and interviews is faith healing or traditional herbalist which are normal practiced in combination with divination and the services are always provided by diviners or people with the gift of divination, who will be able to deal with the spirits in order to deliver the mentally ill persons. Credence to this finding is gotten from Kabir *et al* (2004) who posit that community attitude and beliefs, play a role in determining help-seeking behaviour and successful treatment of the mentally ill.

Findings on consultation of diviners for mental illness among Ibibio people revealed that though diviners' consultation has been a long-standing cultural practice of the Ibibio people, the majority of the people do not patronize diviners for mental health care or cure. The reasons for poor patronage of diviners for mental illness according to the findings include; a lack of interest in knowing the source of the mental problem or who is responsible since solution is paramount, and the services of diviners have been taken over by the prophets and prophetesses of some of the churches and prayer houses found within Ibibio land. Ahmed *et al* (2015) confirmed this finding by stating that certain aspects of the cultural practices of the

society, which are entrenched in the way people think, reason, act, and speak influence their reason for health-seeking behaviour. Further findings showed that most of the traditional herbalists combine herbs and roots with divination. On very rare occasions very few persons have consulted the office of the diviners for anything in relation to the mental problems of their relatives. A key reason for poor patronage of orthodox treatments for mental illness is that the majority of people consider mental illness to be a spiritual case rather than physical.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to investigate divination patronage as an alternative mental health seeking behaviour of Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Mental illness to the Ibibio people is spiritually controlled ailment which needs spiritual intervention for the control of the spirit toward successful and effective treatment. The most preferred treatment for mental illness among the Ibibio people is the spiritualist's treatment which is always practiced by diviners though the majority of them engage faith healing practice and traditional herbalist treatments. There is high degree of stigmatization among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State in relation to mental illness. Diviners play key roles in controlling the spirits of madness in order to subject the mentally ill person to treatment. Out of fear of stigmatization, a lot of people have chosen to take their mentally ill patients to diviners especially those who combine divination with faith healing, and herbal treatment. This practice has positioned a lot of Ibibio people in diviners' patronage and poor patronage of psychiatric hospital.

RECOMMENDATION

Base on the findings of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations;

1. More psychiatric hospitals should be built across the Ibibio speaking local government areas to match the rising number of mentally ill persons.
2. Government and non-government organizations should embark on proper education of the people on the causes of mental illness in order to replace or reduce the degree of belief that mental illness is a spiritual problem.
3. The people should be enlightened on the likely actions to be taken immediately if there is observation of signs of mental illness among the people.
4. Faith healers and traditional herbalists should be supported and formally registered for proper monitoring and control by the government in order to reposition them for better service delivery, and efficient contribution in tackling the menace of mental illness in society.

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THE EFFECT OF CATHARSIS IN EXPRESSIVE WRITING AS A STRESS INTERVENTION AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Individuals who are stressed and accompanied by anxiety will become impatient, complain, and think negatively about things around them. Some symptoms of stress are anxiety, restlessness, decreased self-esteem, feeling unable to meet academic demands, irritability, mood swings, frequent panic, and acting without thinking. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. This type of research is a quasi-experimental research, which is a type of research where the implementation does not use random assignment but uses existing groups. The design of this research is one group pre-test-post-test design. This one group pre-test-post-test design consists of one group that has been determined. The research population in the study was 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Programme at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University as many as 27 students. Data collection techniques in this study by giving pre-test and post-test using an instrument given through Google Form After participating in expressive writing activities, the subject experienced a decrease in the mean score of perceived stress, namely for the pretest of 31.26 and the posttest score of 27.13. Based on the results of hypothesis testing conducted, a significance value of $p=0.026$ ($p<0.05$) was obtained, indicating that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. The results of hypothesis testing show that there is an effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention on college students.

KEYWORDS: Catharsis, stress, students, and expressive writing

INTRODUCTION

The experience of studying at university can be both exciting and nerve-wracking.

University learning requires students to adapt quickly and think independently. They must have consistent motivation to learn and take the initiative to complete the many coursework assignments. If they are not enthusiastic in doing the tasks from lectures, the specified learning outcome targets will not be met. Some students who are unable to keep up with the demands of learning are forced to repeat certain courses because they do not pass the course standards, or even some of them are forced to *drop out of lectures* because they are unable to complete lecture assignments (Mayangsari, 2013).

The opportunity to become a student is a chance for someone to develop their potential while building a career network that can later become a way of life. It is also the momentum of a bridge to future success. However, being a student is not always sweet either, there are tough times to go through. For example, college assignments that come at the same time or the challenge of managing time between doing college assignments or self-development activities outside of college. These complications can be draining, stressful and very challenging (Doygun and Gulec, 2012). Students become vulnerable to psychological disorders, Musabiq and Karimah (2018) found that students often experience fatigue and feel weak due to stress caused by intrapersonal stressors. The experience of the COVID-19 pandemic is a clear example of the number of students experiencing stress, changes in the dynamic learning process were found to make students experience severe stress (referring to the DASS-42 test results) with a high frequency (Sitorus *et al.*, 2023). In addition to intrapersonal factors, Dewi (2016) also found that high stress in students is caused by academic task demands, social environmental pressures and interpersonal pressures. High academic responsibilities, a large task load, social demands, financial problems, and drastic changes in environmental conditions can trigger increased stress in students (Muslim, 2020).

Mills *et al.* (2014) mentioned that stress can cause damage to physiological functions such as stomach pain, arthritis, asthma and headaches. Individuals who are stressed and accompanied by anxiety will become impatient, complain, and think negatively about the things around them. Some symptoms of stress are anxiety, restlessness, decreased self-esteem, feeling unable to meet academic demands, irritability, mood swings, frequent panic, and acting without thinking (Barseli and Ifdil, 2017). Stress has become a difficult part of life to avoid, high levels of stress can be detrimental to the individuals experiencing it (Lin and Huang, 2014). Considering the difficulties faced by university students, there is a need for stress management strategies and relieving negative emotions. This is because hiding or holding back emotions, thoughts, and behaviours is stressful (Pennebaker 2017).

Researchers distributed DASS-21 as an instrument to determine the stress level of students, the distribution of DASS-21 was carried out on 3 May 2023 through *Google form*. After distributing the DASS-21, 27 non-psychology subjects were obtained. The results found that 6 students experienced very severe stress, 5 students experienced severe stress, 4 students experienced moderate stress, no students experienced mild stress and 12 students were in normal stress conditions.

As a stress management strategy, expressive writing has emerged in recent years as an attractive and effective alternative to reduce stress (Bockarov, 2015). Expressive writing means writing some self-expression on a personal book or other contemporary media in a narrated way (Savera *et al.*, 2022). The things written down are positive and negative experiences that result in learning and better health. According to Mukhlis *et al.*, (2020) in

expressive writing, various topics can be written about, but it is very important to explore feelings from objective experiences that write the deepest emotions. Conversations about mental health are currently prominent in various media with a large focus on what we can do to maintain our mental health as well as our physical health. Mental health doesn't always require major life changes or a lot of money. Something, simple writing can relieve stress, reduce anxiety, and help ease feelings of depression (Mohamed *et al.*, 2023). Expressive writing reduces distracting thoughts and can improve memory performance, which in turn can free up our cognitive resources for other mental activities, including our ability to cope effectively with stress (Klein and Boals, 2001).

Pennebaker (1997) found that expressive writing makes individuals tend to use more causal analysis and express more emotions in writing, so psychologists also speculate that expressive writing helps people to simplify and organise fragmented memories. Expressive writing has been shown to help reduce depressive symptoms, when writing down feelings on paper they are easier to analyse and writing down feelings also helps individuals to understand the train of thought that can lead to a worsening mental state (Koschwanez *et al.*, 2013).

The benefit of expressive writing for stress management is that it reduces emotional tension. When you feel overwhelmed thinking about multiple tasks and problems, it can be difficult to think about them. However, putting them down on paper gives you a place to organise your thoughts, rather than letting them stay in your brain all the time. Often people find it difficult to find the words to explain how they feel, or what they are thinking. However, expressive writing exercises help you find the words that allow you to understand your emotions better (Murray, 2002). Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of expressive writing on stress in university students. The hypothesis of this study is that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as an intervention for stress in university students.

It is hoped that the findings of this study can provide an understanding of the concept of catharsis in expressive writing and can also apply the results of this study in order to bounce back when experiencing stress, so that they can overcome mental health problems experienced independently. In addition, it can be used as a reference by mental health practitioners or educators in the university environment in reducing psychological stress through a simple way in the form of expressive writing.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Stress Theory

Stress theory is a social theory that explains observations about stress, an aspect of social life. Theories use concepts that represent classes of phenomena to explain observations. Stress theory is a relatively new field of theoretical development; it proposed that since the beginning of the human race, people having dealing with stress. Stress theory point to psychological crisis with various forms of humans' emotional problems. According to Boss (2002), Stress theory developed into individual stress theory and family stress theory. Individual stress theory has made valuable contributions to understanding family stress (Boss, 2002). Stress theory here explains the psychological problems facing students in the university as individuals, as they engage in school activities. The study tries to examine the effects of

cathartic in expressive writing as an intervention for stress among university students.

METHODOLOGY

This type of research is *quasi-experimental research*, which is a type of research where the implementation does not use *random assignment* but uses existing groups (White and Sabarwal, 2014). In this study, experimental research methods were used to examine the effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention on students of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University. This research design is a *one group pre-test-post-test design*. This *one group pre-test-post-test* design consists of one group that has been determined. In this design, two tests are carried out, namely before treatment is called a *pre-test* and after treatment is called a *post-test*. the *pre-test* was given to the experimental group (O_1). After the *pre-test*, the researcher gave treatment in the form of expressive writing (X), at the final stage the researcher gave a *post-test* (O_2).

The research population in the study were 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Programme at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University as many as 27 students, while the samples involved were students who had qualifications in accordance with the criteria determined by the researcher, namely: non-psychology students, willing to participate in all stages of the experimental process, and have mild to very severe stress levels. After *screening*, a sample of 15 people with mild-severe stress levels was obtained, while the other 12 people did not meet the criteria to become research subjects because they had normal stress levels.

The data collection technique in this study is by giving a *pre-test and post-test* using an instrument given through *Google Form*, namely by using the DASS-21 to measure stress levels in students. DASS-21 has 3 subscales: depression (7 items), anxiety (7 items), and stress (7 items). The stress subscale was developed based on the five dimensions of stress presented by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995), namely: difficulty to calm down, easily agitated / upset, feeling nervous, impatient, and irritable / overly reactive. DASS-21 (*Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21*) is one of the *self-assessment* instruments by giving a score from 0-3 where: 0: never, 1: sometimes, 2: often or, 3: very often on each item. On the DASS-21 there are 21 items that are asked. The interpretation of stress levels on this instrument is normal, moderate, mild, severe, and very severe.

The procedure in which the researcher adopted was by conducting a screening process using the DASS 21 measuring instrument on 3 May 2023 for 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Program at UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta. After the *screening* process, 15 students passed the research. Before participating in the study, participants were asked for their willingness to participate in the study. The intervention in this study was in the form of expressive writing which was carried out for 5 days on 6 - 11 May 2023. Every day monitoring was carried out by the researcher to ensure that each participant had done expressive writing on that day.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants in this study were 4th semester students of the Shari'ah Economics Study Programme at UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta who had mild to severe stress levels.

Table 1. Stress level categorization

Disruption	Severity				
	Normal	Lightweight	Medium	Weight	Very Heavy
Depression	0-9	10-13	14-20	21-27	28+
Anxiety	0-7	8-9	10-14	15-19	20+
Stress	0-14	15-18	19-25	26-33	34+

Table 2. Pre-test and Post-test Results

I	Initials	Pre-test score	Category	Post-test score	Category	Gain Score
	DF	42	Very Heavy	39	Very Heavy	3
	F	42	Very Heavy	35	Very Heavy	7
	KAA	43	Very Heavy	32	Very Heavy	11
	D	19	Medium	17	Lightweight	2
	I	28	Weight	21	Medium	7
	N	27	Weight	24	Medium	3
	YD	23	Medium	19	Medium	4
	ZR	49	Very Heavy	40	Very Heavy	9
	H	27	Weight	27	Weight	0
	QT	29	Weight	30	Weight	1
	M	28	Weight	24	Medium	4
	A	39	Very Heavy	20	Weight	19
	RIS	19	Medium	25	Medium	6
	APM	20	Medium	26	Weight	6

Based on the Table above, 15 students all participated in the study from beginning to end. The results of the *pre-test* and *post-test* showed that 11 students experienced a decrease, 1 student had a fixed pre-test and post-test score, while 3 students experienced an increase in score after being given the *post-test*.

Table 3. Wilcoxon Test

	Pre-test Post-test
Z	-2.232 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-Tailed)	.026

The results of data analysis show that the Z value is -2.232 and the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) value is 0.026. These results show that $p = 0.026$ ($p < 0.05$), meaning that there is a significant effect of writing catharsis in reducing stress in college students.

This study used a *one-group pretest-posttest* design so that this study only had

one research group. A total of 15 students participated in the study from beginning to end. The results of the *pre-test* and *post-test* showed that 11 students experienced a decrease, 1 student had a fixed *pre-test* and *post-test score*, while 3 students experienced an increase in score after being given the *post-test*. Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) suggest that stress is an individual response to conditions that are considered challenges or threats. Stress arises when individuals experience adjustment or adaptation in any case. When individuals feel pressure in the long term and also the individual's body cannot adapt to it, it will cause stress. Li et al (2016) stress is the condition of the individual when feeling pressure, problems and threats.

Silverman et al (2010) suggest that stress is the body's reaction to changes that require a response, physical adaptation or regulation, psychological, and emotional. Stress can also come from situations, thoughts, conditions or situations that cause frustration, anxiety and nervousness. Hunt and Eisenberg (2010) suggest that the stress experienced by students is related to the problems that have been experienced during lectures. Nur and Mugi (2021) suggest that individuals who have high stress will be dangerous so that it will cause psychological, biological, and social problems.

Participants participated in cathartic writing activities for 5 days. Every day the researcher reminded the subject to write on the expressive sheet that he had for 5 consecutive days and then was given a DASS 21 evaluation *form*. After participating in expressive writing activities, the subject experienced a decrease in the *mean* score of perceived stress, namely for the *pre-test* of 31.26 and the *post-test* score of 27.13. The decrease in the *mean* score is also due to the fact that during expressive writing, the subject is required to be more aware and think positively. Nickerson (2023) suggests that cathartic writing can release negative emotions to relieve intense anxiety, stress, anger, or fear.

In the *pre-test* results, there were 6 students who had very severe stress levels, 5 students had severe stress levels, and 4 students who experienced moderate stress levels. After participating in expressive writing activities for 5 days, there was 1 student who had a mild level and 5 students who had moderate stress. Based on the results of hypothesis testing conducted, a significance value of $p=0.026$ ($p<0.05$) was obtained, which shows that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. Pennebaker (2017) suggested that expressive writing is a personal and emotional writing skill as an alternative strategy to relieve stress.

CONCLUSION

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention for university students. There is a decrease in the *mean* score of stress level from pretest to posttest. Thus, the level of stress experienced by students decreased in the second measurement compared to the first measurement. As a suggestion in future research, it is expected to apply expressive writing activities to be used as a stress coping medium so as not to drag on the stress felt and can rise from adversity.

By applying expressive writing activities, they can live their daily lives with more positive feelings. The shortcomings in the study are that the implementation of cathartic writing is quite short and the collection of cathartic writing is carried out on the last day of the experiment, so the possibility of bias is quite large. In addition, the monitoring of the cathartic

writing process is only through WhatsApp communication, so it cannot be ascertained whether the respondent is doing the writing activity or not.

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AMALGAMATION SOCIOLOGY: THE BANE OF NIGERIA'S POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses Nigeria's development within the context of colonialism. The research is aimed at examining the negative effects of amalgamation policy of 1914 on the economic and political development of Nigeria. The paper argued that Nigeria's economic and political problems can be traced to the negative impact of indirect rule strategy which has accounted for the violent post-colonial politics leading to continued hindrance to the nation democracy and development since independence. The paper therefore concludes that, the injurious effects of amalgamation policy and its implications on ethnic conflicts inequality in revenue-allocation formula, religious division and civil war Vis-à-vis militancy and terrorism notwithstanding are contemporary issues affecting economic and political development in Nigeria till date.

KEYWORDS: Amalgamation, Political Economic Development, Ethnic Conflict, Religious Division and Revenue Allocation

INTRODUCTION

The ascendancy of Nigeria as a nation can be traced to two different periods in history: The influx of colonialism and the amalgamation geography producing two protectorates by British imperialism. The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary defined “amalgamation” as the joining of different constituent parts to form one large organization. Sociologically, it refers to a sociological process by which two different cultures blend together and a new culture originates. In other words, it is a process of bringing together of people from different ethnic, religious and cultural background or nationality into one administrative political authority in order to achieve or promote collective conscience, morality and collective representation as a group. The 1914 amalgamation in Nigeria which produced the northern and southern protectorates which were previously administered as separate through related territories is generally regarded as the birth date of the Nigerian State (Egbosa, 2022). Paradoxically, the amalgamation policy of 1914 by British colonialists was not for the interest and development of Nigeria, rather it helps to galvanize the exploitation of Nigeria's economic resources and also to strengthen a coercive economic administration (Egbulem, 2010) In effect, the 1914 amalgamation in Nigeria destroyed an indigenous political and administrative system that was far from more democratic and accountable and replaced it with a colonial system of government that was wholly undemocratic and lacked any kind of accountability. A corollary of this gave birth to the creation of northern, southern and eastern regions with attendant wide

range devastating consequences that has hindered economic and political development of the nation till date. Consequent upon the foregoing, one major democratic problems of Nigeria during post-colonial to independence period with grave consequence on economic and political development is the uneven approach giving to derivation formula for the sharing of federally collected revenue based on 65% within the three federating regions now states between 1952 to 1954 which was not favourably to eastern region and a host of other problems that will be discussed in the later part of this paper, points to amalgamation drama in Nigeria.

In reference to economic and political development, Annana (2006) did make the point that, economic development suggests qualitative change and the creation of new economic and non-economic structures which increase the quality of life of the citizenry through proper fiscal arrangements between the levels of government in a federation and each of the levels of government will be developed economically and lives of the citizens will be transformed. In real sense, economic development denote a situation where the basic need of individuals of health, education, food, water, sanitation and housing are provided by the state.

On the other hand, political development refers to the development of the institutions, attitudes, and values that form the political power system of a society (Burnell, 2011). As Park observed in 1984 that, the values to be developed are in terms of the capacity of the political system to satisfy the changing needs of members of the society. From the foregoing assertion, it must be deduced that economic and political development are like Siamese twins in the context of development and governance in Nigeria. This is because the both concepts is basically concern with the idea of meeting the needs of members of the society by enhancing the standard of living. However, it is against this background that this research paper seeks to examine the effects of amalgamation on Nigeria's political and economic development. Structurally, the paper is divided into two main parts. Part one places basic concepts in their correct perspectives. Part two situates the effects of amalgamation Policy on economic and political development of Nigeria. This is followed by summary and conclusion.

CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE

Amalgamation: The Nigeria Perspective

The evolution of Nigeria as a nation is a direct result of the 1914 amalgamation policy which British colonialism introduced. During this period the Northern and Southern protectorates was merged to form what is now known as Nigeria. The colonial administration and imperial occupations carved up boundaries that divided territories inhabited by indigenous societies and brought together a diversity of ethnic communities within unitary administrative structures. According to Ebegbulem (2010) in Nigeria, between 1914 to 1915 British colonial administrators created three unequal territories that explain “ethno-genesis” and later “ethno-tension”; thus the North became Hausa/Fulani and the West inhabited by Yoruba while the East occupied by Ibos. In fact within these divisive colonial structure ethnic tensions emerged between these unequally developed groups. Commenting further, Dare in 1986 observed that, the administrative structure that followed the amalgamation policy also introduced a contradictory administrative system through the operation of the so called “Indirect rule” policy which continued to treat the various units as separate entities and allowed each to develop in whatever direction it choses in isolation from the others. Again as I have occasion to point out in the introductory chapter, that economic determinism warranted

the amalgamation of the two protectorates in Nigeria (North and south). It is argued in some quarters that before 1914 the Northern protectorate would not find sufficient funds to maintain its own administrative structure rather the financial position of the southern protectorate was encouraging because of its vast sea ports, as such the economic resources in the southern protectorate were utilized to oil the development of both Northern and southern protectorates through amalgamation. This policy was carried out for selfish interest of the colonial government. Essentially, the amalgamation principle came into the political dictionary of Nigeria through the personal interest or ambition of Lord Lugard. It was argued that the main reasons were to secure firm control over the southern protectorate as he had done in the North and to extend the policies he had introduced in the Northern protectorate to the south. Reacting further, Gana and Egwu (2003) asserts that the 1914 amalgamation principle established a system of indirect rule that was based on a policy of non-centralized administration. Theoretically, indirect rule meant the utilization of existing traditional administrative structures for governing and also allowing each ethnic group to develop along its own lines. What this meant in practice was that; the traditional rulers were located and empowered to govern their respective domains as before. Where no paramount leaders were known to exist in the traditional setup, warrant chiefs were appointed. It was these warrant chiefs that governed in most parts of the East with varying degrees of success.

The upshot of amalgamation were numerous in the Nigerian body politics and contemporary crisis which are the outcome of a number of forces reflective of colonial indirect rule whose interactions have pushed the nation down a particular path and has exacerbated ethnicity, regionalism, religious division, uneven derivation policy and lopsided fiscal federalism implementation thus making it difficult to achieve any meaningful political and economic development in Nigeria after independence.

THE EFFECTS OF AMALGAMATION POLICY ON NIGERIA'S ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT

Inequality in Revenue Allocation Formula

It is clearly evident that one of the problems affecting Nigerian's economic and political development is the direct result of the struggle between the three ethnic regions over the control of the national wealth and power at the centre. This phenomenon has made Nigeria's politics rather volatile. More so, the pressure that was put on the then colonial government by the different regions arising from the unequal contribution of all economic areas to the national wealth led to the evolution of revenue allocation formula in Nigeria. In post-colonial to Independence era, it was argued that between 1954 to 1959, the colonial government establish an autonomous revenue and tax jurisdiction policy to the regional governments based on the principle of derivation in the sharing of federally collected revenue. This formula created a lot of disparities within the three regions in terms of economic development. Consequently at different stages, the revenue allocation formula were adjusted and criteria between and within levels of governments in Nigeria. Nevertheless there appears to be a significant relationship between structural and power relations as regard to the distribution of revenue within the major ethnic groups which were the main contributors to the nation's wealth. Allocation of revenue was based on the average of 65%. One major distinguish

factor of these phases of revenue sharing formula was the much accorded emphasis on the derivation principle.

This revenue sharing formula distorted the economic and political development of Nigeria, because significant development projects were centred on regional level rather than national development. As observed by Egwaikhide and Isumoniah (2001) derivation formula pleased the northern and western regions considering the boom in their export commodities: cotton and groundnut in the North and Cocoa in the West. The Eastern region whose main export crop palm oil was facing difficult times in the global market was unhappy with the derivation policy because it affected the development of the Eastern region in all ramifications as compare to the other two regions (West and North) economically. When revenue allocation was based on derivation principle, the Northern and Western regions had various social and economic facilities including universities, banks, business outfits and chains of Hotel facilities to show for their regions resources while the case was different in the Eastern region. Another important issue worthy of note is the declaration of Chief Awolowo when he expresses the opinion that “in embracing western culture, the Yoruba take the lead and benefited by the regions wealth based on 65% derivation. This policy galvanized them into the great height in Nigeria's political economy. This however, was the genesis of fiscal imbalance and the agitation for equitable revenue sharing formula was given deaf ears because of the contending primordial interest between the northern and western region elites.

In reality, the derivation formula created a lot of inequalities within ethnic lines, and did not go well in Nigeria as a newly developing nation. The derivation policy did not only affect the economic and political development, but it also weakens the legitimacy of the central government in performing its responsibilities to the citizens. As a result, Nigeria's standard of living was undoubtedly affected mostly within the minority ethnic groups. The different phases of revenue allocation commissions in the post-colonial period notably of Phillipson assertion of 1946, Hicks position in 1951, Chicks assertion of 1958, and Barisman position of 1958 emphasized the derivation formula in revenue allocation. Besides these era points to the fact that: the much agitated revenue allocation formula of derivation which also includes resource control thus, its re-emphasises in contemporary times had almost, turned the nation ablaze. Ironically, it has been in practice during post-colonial and independence era without any complains because the North and West were the major beneficiaries of this derivation policy.

The foregoing factors puts the minority ethnic groups in contemporary times particularly the South-South region in a state of dilemma in considering why the North and the power configuration in the West are now rejecting restructuring of the Nigerian federation when resource control has been a common practice in the past. Finally for this section to be noted also is the fact that when Nigeria got her independence, there was a change in emphasis as regard to revenue allocation formula thus subsequent revenue allocation commissions were constituted notably: Aboyade in 1977, Okigbo in 1979 and National Revenue Mobilization Allocation and Fiscal commission in 1989 de-emphasized derivation policy. It was argued that, as a new independent state it was necessary for the federal government to have financial stability that will guarantee development in the regions; as a result the first two post-independence constitutions of 1960 to 1963 provided 50% derivation in respect to all revenues from minerals. Ironically, this was a deliberate attempt by the power configuration in Nigeria

because it was realized that crude oil was discovered in a neglected parts of Eastern region now known as South-South region.

More so, the pre-eminence accorded to crude oil globally cannot be compared to the political economy of agriculture that has sustained the northern and western regions in the past. Crude oil became the major source of Nigeria's economy. In other words, the assertion of Fashina in 1998 lends credence when he opined that the weight accorded to derivation principle appears to have been determined by the interest of the different factions of the ruling class and their political power. From the above assertion, it can be deduced that the discovery of crude oil in the minority region of South-South orchestrated the paradigm shift in revenue formula for sharing of federally, collected revenue to the different federating units to fiscal federalism because of primordial interest of self-acclaimed power blocs representing the north and west. In so far as the problems of Nigeria's economic and political development is seen to be associated with the imbalances created by the introduction of derivation policy which 1914 amalgamation nurtured, although conceived in the womb of colonialism, bedevilled the unity and progress of the nation in general. It is clearly evident that inequality in revenue allocation has in contemporary times created a lot of challenges between federal and state governments in considering which sharing formula is appropriate for the country because of 1914 amalgamation drama.

ETHNIC CONFLICTS

One central reason for the stunted democracy, economic and political development in Nigeria is the issue of ethnicity. The prevalence of ethnic conflicts in the nation is the direct effect of amalgamation policy of 1914, as mentioned before in the introductory chapter, the indiscriminate merger of various ethnic groups under one national umbrella and as it to contradict this effort, through the operation of the so called indirect rule policy which continued to treat the various units as separate entities and allowed each to develop in whatever ways it chose to in isolation to others. Besides since the various ethnic groups that formed what is now known as Nigeria were not consulted before the merger resulted to ethnic differences and conflicts among them at every point in contact.

In contemporary Nigeria society, ethnicity has been widely recognised as a central factor contributing to political problems. Balewa in 1994 aptly observed that probably the most important and sinister factor in Nigeria's political development is ethnicity. For Balewa, this ubiquitous factor intrudes in a great many situations because Nigerian societies are made up of many ethnic groups of various sizes and influence. These imply that groups are distinct from each other on the basis of language, social organization and other cultural characteristics. Adamu (1999) also noted that "No two people can walk together except they agree, and no two people can ever agree except they understand themselves". Thus the absence of consensus within these diverse groups before merging undoubtedly exacerbates conflict with high level of immobilism. The amalgamation policy denied the different ethnic groups in Nigeria the right to basic need of participation, equality and social wellbeing thereby creating ethnic cleavage. The effects of amalgamation were numerous. First, colonialism through indirect rule policy fostered ethnic cleavage between majority and minority groups by creating a largely artificial regions with each region containing a majority group that dominate in it: the Hausa/Fulani in the North, the Yoruba's in the West and Igbos in the East resulting to fermentation of

what Weiner in 1993 called “*the development of a mono-ethnic tendency*”.

Secondly with regional system of government these major ethnic groups became the political elites that were in control of the affairs of the state, as major political parties that emerged to control each regions were political elites from these major ethnic groups. The three major political parties that came up at independence were regional ethnic parties: Northern people congress (NPC) in the North, the National Council of Nigerian Citizen (NCNC) in the East, the Action Group (AG) in the West. In reality the Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba and the Igbos formed the first political parties before independence and the minority ethnic groups were silence in political participation.

Nevertheless these political parties were all intents and purpose, sectional parties political parties which could have acted as agents of national development became champions of interest and particularism of the major ethnic groups. The more these political parties struggle and fight among themselves because of ethnicity, the more it becomes difficult for the federal government to achieve any meaningful economic and political development. The mentality which indirect rule system created encouraged the fractionalization of ethnic groups in Nigeria and these has in turn reinforced ethnic conflicts as these sentiments were often aroused in the competition for power, material resources and privileges. Political participation often degenerates into an unrelenting war to acquire defend or gain access to state power. As Ebegbulem (2010) aptly observed, the politics of ethnic and regional security play a key role in Nigeria's political and economic development as well as its role in Africa. This is because ethnicity is the major source of growing political crisis in Nigeria. Ethnicity undermines the proper selection of responsible national leadership by politicizing ethnicity. In Nigeria, national leaders are recruited on the basis of ethnicity, not experience and vision thus Nigeria's political and economic growth falls below comparison with other countries. The prevalence of ethnicity in political arena has resulted in periodic outbreaks of ethnic violence between different ethnic groups in Nigeria (Ebegbulem, 2010).

The indirect rule system contributed greatly in politicizing ethnicity which is detrimental to national unity and socio economic well-being. It was argued that indirect rule policy was used by colonialists to create inter-ethnic war thereby capitalizing on the isolation of ethnic groups and also to pitch on ethnic groups against each other thus hindering unity among them. Ethnicity was also used by colonialists in the distribution of economic resources to favour a particular ethnic group pushing marginalized groups to use their ethnic front to mobilize for equality; these often result to conflicts. The indirect rule was not the appropriate mechanism for managing tribal animosity in the country, Coleman in 1958 opined that, rather it only reinforced ethnic divisions; it complicated the task of welding diverse elements into a Nigerian nation.

Suffice it to say, the injuries which ethnic conflicts created in Nigeria's political atmosphere contributed greatly to the demise of the first republic and subsequent military regime of General Ironsi in 1966. It was argued by Dare in 1984 that the military regime of Ironsi was short lived because of ethnicity. The Hausa/Fulani ethnic group in the North saw it as a means of dislodging the Northern hegemony from power and the imposition of a southerner particularly Ibo domination over the whole Nigeria. These ethnic sentiments provided an inroad to the May riots and the massacre of Ibos in the North points to incontestable facts into the problems of ethnic conflicts in Nigeria as an impediment to

political and economic development.

RELIGIOUS DIVISION

There is no denying the fact that religion plays a very significant role in the unification of any group in the society and the world in general. It determines the way of life of any group in terms of culture, character and belief system. Religion defines what is perceived as beautiful and ugly, right and wrong, good and bad in the eyes of its followers. Thus religion, culture and ethnicity are inter-woven in any given situation. Edward Tylor's position of 1871 adds credence to this when he asserted culture as the way of life of people which implies that, as a way, people's life is reflected in their beliefs, religion and behaviour involving, language, dressing, dancing, music and food. As I have occasion to point out that apart from culture, religion and ethnicity are like twins, babies although not conceived at the same time but can be used interchangeably to actualize negative and positive purposes in any sociological situations. This is because both religion and ethnicity enforce each other at one point, and are antagonistic in another situation.

As Crawford Young noted in 1979 that religion offers both comprehensive world view and an all-embracing social identity, so does ethnicity or religious beliefs will also mostly hold similar attitudes and opinions and individuals will behave in a similar way toward each other in social relations than others? These imply that, people seem to identify their collective conscience, morality and collective representation through religion. Studies carried out by various scholars spanning the period from the 1950s till date serve to show that severally religion has deleterious effects on politics and general wellbeing of Nigeria. In a developing nation like Nigeria, religion is used as a springboard for ethnic identification. Insofar as politics and governance is concerned, religion plays a key role in political bargaining and the struggle for control of state affairs. The aftermath of 1914 amalgamation policy generated a lot of ethnic tension that has invariably hindered the economic and political development and is still haunting Nigeria in contemporary times.

The most deliberate act was the confinement of two different religious entities together under one national umbrella and political authority. The merging of Christianity and Islamic religion to a distinct geographical setting called Nigeria with their accompanying differences, prejudices and biases resulted to ethno-religious conflicts and to what Huntington in 1968 called *it accident of geography and colonialism*. These imply that Nigeria's state encompassing many religious, ethnic and linguistic groups. Dare in 1986 reported that, the elites who mounted the political ladder at independence in 1960, and whose duty it was to shape and develop the future of their country became undoubtedly tribal-centred, whose politics were conditioned by primordial and religious interest.

In considering religious identity and solidarity ties as instruments of political bargaining, the elite class of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria engage in constant struggle for the control of state power and when they gain political power they use it to perpetuate and ensure the dominance of members of their own ethnic and religious groups in the nation's bureaucratic setting. These create a situation of conflict among religious groups and also the minority groups struggle for recognition in the distribution of national resources. Religious division has really affected the development of the civil service, it undermines the Weberian

precepts of universalistic orientation based on achieved rather than ascribed norms or particularism thus, distorted the effectiveness and efficiency of the public service. The implications of these is that instead of employing people based on proper qualification or experience rather emphasis is placed on religious affiliation as a basis for employment. In the very words of Margaret Peli in 1976 stated that with “Christianity and Islam” taking centre stage as a multi religious country, the influence of religion has been rather pervasive for quite a long time.

The impact of religious division on employment issues

For instance, between 1954 to 1966 in Northern region: religious division prevented the TIVS ethnic groups in particular and other Non-Hausa Fulani minorities in the Northern region from having access or employment into civil service because of their religious differences, culture and political disparity between the ruling party in the North (NPC). In recent times, national politics in Nigeria has been clouded with religious sentiments both in appointment into federal ministries and allocation of resources within the various federating units in the country and these ugly scenarios is not compatible with economic development. The advent of military into the political sphere worsen, the incidence of religious division in Nigeria as one military regime supplanted the other from 1966 to 1999 all from the same ethnic and religious background. The present civilian administration of President Buhari, the incidence of religious division escalated as majority of the federal appointment of ministers in the federal executive council were mostly members from Hausa/Fulani ethnic and religious group. Politicizing religious division is rather devastating on Nigeria's political and economic development.

CIVIL WAR, MILITANCY AND TERRORISM

The ascendancy of amalgamation policy of 1914 resulting to the unification of Northern and Southern protectorates undoubtedly remain one of the most controversial and contentious issues in contemporary Nigerian federation. More than a 100 years after this policy was introduced. The aftermath consequences of this policy euphoria have made political scientists, sociologists, anthropologists and political activists in considering whether the 1914 amalgamation policy by British colonialism was a curse or blessing to Nigeria as a nation. This is because up till now, Nigeria's political elites are still trying to grapple with the appropriate mechanism on how to manage the crisis and mutual paranoia between the north and south that has generated a lot of insecurity and instability that resulted to the demise of the first republic and military coup in 1966 was orchestrated by ethnicity via amalgamation policy.

The first military coup of January 1966 and subsequent counter coup became obvious to all observers in Nigeria that the civilian regime of the first republic and founding fathers had failed in its primary functions of maintaining law and order and national integration that would have promoted economic and political development in the nation. This is because the political elites in the first republic were uncoordinated in the management of ethnic crisis that polarize the country based on north-south dichotomy. The military coup that brought General Ironsi as the head of state became a bad omen to the northern elements; they saw the military coup as being motivated by ethnicity and sectionalism.

As Dare in 1986 aptly noted, the northerners saw the military regime of Ironsi as a way

of dislodging the Hausa/Fulani hegemony from the control of state powers and also as a means of imposing a southerner particularly Ibo ethnic group domination over the whole Nigeria. The Promulgation of unification decree by General Ironsi administration aimed at building national integration deepened inter-ethnic suspicion and these led to the massacre of Ibos both in the military and civilians officers resident in the northern region. Unlike the January coup of 1966 which happened simultaneously in Lagos, Kaduna and Ibadan. The counter coup of July 1966 showed a lack of formal plan but rather the desperation of the northerners in overthrowing the Ibos and southern hegemony from the control of the state. The assassination of General Ironsi and his associates mostly Ibos points to the fact that politics and ethnicity had already infiltrated the military. These twin factors escalated crisis that almost disrupted national integration and security. Although it was argued that, original plan of the Northern coup plotters was to take the North out of the federation.

The history of Nigeria from this point was that of slow and inevitable degeneration towards a thirty month civil war between 1967 to 1970 couple with the annulment of the presidential election of June 12, 1993 and the ensuing political crisis it generated plus the crisis over sharia law in the year 2000 against the spirit of the 1999 constitution. The precursor of militancy in the Niger Delta also heightens ethnic tension. This is because, the Niger Delta region felt marginalized, neglected and their environment despoiled by oil activities with severe ramifications for her economy. Besides being the kitchen of the nation thus lacks modernity which absence exacerbates issues though ossified thus generated violent protests in the region. Again the political rife between contending power forces in the Northern region resulted to the incidence of Boko-Haram terrorism. The violence of Boko Haram has left over 40,000 people dead since 2009 to 2022. The insurgency of Boko Haram in the North East of Nigeria is the biggest and most pressing challenge facing Nigeria at present.

According to Famuyiwa (2014) since 2009 precisely till date, Boko Haram insurgence in the nation resulted to a several cases of bomb blasts and thousands of death and many people injured or maimed for life, properties worth billions of naira destroyed and several thousand people displaced from their abodes. The foregoing factor represents one of the many attempts to repeal the 1914 amalgamation as being a curse than blessing to Nigeria. It should also be noted that conflicts is bound to arise considering the nature and manner in which the three geographical regions now called Nigeria was merged by British imperialism through amalgamation.

CONCLUSION

There is no gainsaying the fact that this research paper have attempted a critical assessment of how the events discussed above have through ethnicity, unequal derivation sharing formula, religious division, civil war, military and terrorism affected the economic and political development of Nigeria. It is also important to note that amalgamation of 1914 which introduced indirect rule affected the establishment of procedures and routinization of mechanism that would have ushered Nigeria into the pedestine of economic and political development. The events mentioned in this paper have directly or indirectly created a sectional, ethnic consciousness mental virus within the political elites of the three major ethnic groups till date. Essentially, no country can achieve any meaningful development in an

environment that is engulfed with crises. Conflict is not compatible with economic and political development. The struggle for power in the first republic which degenerated into armed struggle was both a reflection of the fact that the established channels for competition was wrongly laid by our colonial masters and was not properly understood by the political gladiators and also to prove that the structures which had been hurriedly setup in the twilight sleep of expiring colonialism did not take precedence. The resort to armed confrontation like the military coup and counter coup of 1966 became logical in a game without accepted rules. In such a game, the professional in the management of violence tend to win.

The years since Nigeria's independence to the present democratic dispensation can be viewed against the struggle for power and attempts at building an effective national integration and equitable distribution of national resources among the various ethnic groups within the federation which has always been compounded by crisis mostly within the minority ethnic groups. Suffice it to say that, no nation ever solves all her problems mostly in a multi-ethnic, plural or federal society. The issue of economic and political development are measured on the basis of how many of the vital problems a society is able to contain. In a developing nation particularly Nigeria, the problems of national unity takes precedence over all others. Sadly enough, political elites in Nigeria have resorted in adopting the various factors of ethnicity, sectionalism, religious division mentality in the performance of their duties against their loyalties to the state. Finally, it is asserted here by way of conclusion that, the various factors mentioned in this paper contributed greatly in the under development of Nigeria's political and economic institutions, more so the in glorious years of colonialism and military rule also resulted to growth without development in Nigerian because of amalgamation.

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STIGMATIZATION AND CHALLENGES OF REINTEGRATION OF WOMEN WITH VVF/RVF IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined stigmatization and challenges of reintegration of women with Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) in Akwa Ibom State. The research design adopted for this study was phenomenology. Data were collected from a sample of seventeen women using interview. Data collected for the study were analyzed manually using the inductive approach of analyzing qualitative data. The findings of the study indicated that women living with VVF in Akwa Ibom State are stigmatized. The stigmatization ranges from isolation, abandonment, mockery and insult. The stigmatization makes life difficult for them since most of them lack or receive very little economic support from their mates and families. After successful repair, the Family Life Centre at Mbribit Itam adopted various methods of reintegration of these women. The most common reintegration strategy was learning of skills and counselling. The study also identified family support as one of the available reintegration strategies used by many. It was concluded that women suffering from VVF are stigmatized and that the common reintegration strategies adopted after their repairs were skill training, counselling and family support. It was recommended that reintegration program designers should bear in mind that all girls and women with fistula are not the same, as such, reintegration strategies need to address the different situations in which these women may find themselves.

KEYWORDS: Stigmatization, reintegration, women and vesico-vaginal fistula

INTRODUCTION

Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) is considered as the abnormal connection between the urinary tract and the vagina such that there is an incessant, uncontrollable leakage of urine into the vaginal tract. According to Villey (2016), VVF is an abnormal communication between the urinary bladder and the vagina that results in the continuous involuntary discharge of urine into the vaginal vault; the pathogenesis of VVF is expressed by the contraction of the pelvis, the prolonged and obstructed labour (labour usually becomes obstructed, when the pelvis is too

small for the passage of the baby) resulting in ischemia of tissues between the bladder and vagina (Akpe, 2013). Few weeks later; the woman experiences sloughing of the tissues and fistula occurs, this could lead to diverse complications like vaginal or urinary tract infections, hygiene problems, stool or gas that leaks through the vagina, irritated or inflamed skin around the vagina, an abscess (a swollen clump of infected tissue with pus that could be life-threatening), and also the risk of fistula forming again. The hallmark symptom of VVF is the uncontrolled leakage of urine into the vagina (Akpeji, 2012).

Though vesicovaginal fistula is a global problem, the health problem appears to be particularly common in Africa. Despite international and national efforts toward the prevention and treatment of obstetric fistula (OF) among women, the problem still remains a major concern and a serious challenge in low income countries where access to emergency obstetric care and skilled birth attendant are insufficient (Delamou *et al.*, 2016).

Over the years, studies have been carried out on cases of obstetric fistula based on hospital records in Nigeria. The National Foundation on Vesico-Vaginal Fistulae (2013) noted that the actual incidence of fistula is not easy to calculate. Harrison (2014) suggested that the incidence might be closer to 80 per 100,000. In Nigeria, the number of cases of VVF and the frequency of occurrence is unknown. This is as a result of the absence of large-scale community based studies.

According to the Federal Ministry of Health in Agu (2013), between 500,000 and 1,000,000 women/girls are living with VVF, and an estimate of up to 80,000 new cases annually. The incidence is estimated at two per 1,000 deliveries. These estimates are based on information gathered from victims who attend established medical facilities seeking healthcare. The reality is, however, that most sufferers, due to either distance or cost, never make it to any formal medical establishment for appropriate attention. There are various predisposing factors to VVF, some of which are; marital status, age, level of education among others.

Researchers have identified marital status as a significant predictor of the likelihood of developing obstetric fistula (Andargie and Debu, 2017; Barageine *et al.*, 2014; Otoo-Oyorley *et al.*, 2014). In a recent study to examine factors associated with the prevalence of obstetric fistula in Ethiopia, Andargie and Debu (2017) found that women whose first marriage fell between the ages of 15 and 19 years old were 87.4% less likely to develop obstetric fistula than those whose first marriage was at an age ranging below 15 years of age. In the same study the researchers indicated that women who first married at age ranging between 20 to 24 years old were 81% less likely to experience obstetric fistula than those who were married before the age of 15 when controlling for other variables in the logistic model. Also, in their study aimed at examining the risk factors for obstetric fistula in West Uganda, Barageine *et al.*, (2014) indicated a significant association between being single and developing obstetric fistula compared to being married. In a qualitative study using 20 women who had previously had repair of obstetric fistula in Malawi, Drew *et al.* (2016) found 80% of the study population to be married prior to the development of the fistula.

Similarly, a literature review of both quantitative and qualitative data from relevant obstetrics and gynecology websites and journals to gather evidence on causes and consequences of obstetric fistula in Ethiopia, by Tollosa and Kibret (2013) revealed a statistically significant association between marital status and experience of obstetric fistula

(p -value < 0.001). In another study, Lufumpa *et al.*, (2018) found that cultural practices around marriage played a key role in the perpetuation of obstetric fistulas sub-Saharan Africa. The researchers also found that dowries decreased with age of the bride in some cultures which served as an incentive for parents to give their daughters in marriage at a younger age. Furthermore, Delamou *et al.* (2016) examined the estimated proportions of failure of fistula closure and incontinence among women undergoing obstetric fistula repair in Guinea. The researchers found that majority of the obstetric fistula patients were married ($n = 523, 69.4\%$).

In addition, Basheer and Pumpaibool (2015) revealed age at first marriage as a significant factor in the occurrence of obstetric fistula in Kebbi State, Nigeria. In their study of fistula and socio-demographic characteristics, Basheer and Pumpaibool (2015) found age at first marriage to be a significant factor in the occurrence of vesico vaginal fistula. Almost all of the women with vesico vaginal fistula got married within the age range between 12 and 15 years old in Kebbi state, Nigeria. The importance of child marriage in this case is the fact that a girl is more likely to get pregnant and deliver a baby that she is not physically and psychological prepared for, when that girl is married at a very young age (Pandya and Bhandari, 2015). Even more important, Pandya and Bhandari (2015) found that there is an increased rate of maternal morbidity and mortality in such young mothers.

The psychological consequences of obstetric fistula are substantial, with depression and early death from suicide (FIGO, 2016). Holtz and Ahmed (2017) demonstrate that women suffering the ordeal of fistula are abandoned by their husbands and family, and are shunned from their communities. Fistula is considered a “social calamity” and women with fistula are often ostracized by their husbands, families, and communities. The condition is often considered a sexually transmitted disease and viewed as a punishment from God. Most women with fistulas report disturbed socio-psychosexual lives and are usually deserted by their husbands. Often, until they are cured, married women with obstetric fistula are sent back to their parents' home where they are not allowed to cook food, participate in social events, or to perform religious rituals. Not only that mourning a dead child is almost inevitable for a woman with a fistula from obstructed labour, but she soon finds herself fighting for her own survival, social position, and value in society. Mentally she is tormented and devastated.

Physical/ medical consequences of obstetric fistula include ulceration, infection, foot drop, kidney diseases and dehydration. In almost all cases of obstetric fistula the leaking of urine and the offensive smell makes the women highly stigmatized and ashamed of themselves (Holtz and Ahmed, 2017; Cook *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, eating, sleeping and praying alone (social isolation), abandonment and divorce, loss of self-esteem and economic deprivation occur. Due to misperceptions surrounding the condition, many of the women survivors see themselves as wretched or cursed, isolating them from their communities and preventing them from seeking help and treatment.

According to the needs assessment carried out by MOH and UNFPA (2014) stigma is an elusive concept, but one that is increasingly recognized as a major component in the perception of the ill person. In Mwingi, Kwale and Homa Bay districts the issue of stigma is not so explicit. The general feeling was that their immediate families did not reject women with fistulas. However, the women, out of their own volition segregated themselves from others because of the embarrassment occasioned by the foul smell. However, having a fistula among the Pokot attracts a social stigma from the community in that the women cannot stay

with others or even cook for the family. Worse still is the situation where a husband returns the wife to her father and demands a refund of the bride price especially if the fistula occurs at birth of the first child.

Fistula is invariably devastating to the lives of women who survive and endure it (Cook et al., 2014). Affected women are frequently driven from their marriages, families and communities to a point of becoming socially invisible and forgotten. They experience a foul smell that results from leaking urine and faecal incontinence and are barred from family activities like cooking and at times driven into isolation. Denied family support, the malnutrition and poverty is aggravated and at times when they can, such women have depended on begging, prostitution or stigmatizing employment. Arguably, social stigma contributes further to women's poverty and gender inequalities.

Women living with fistula experience seclusion and stigma owing to the offensive smell and cultural taboos and this may still be a challenge even after corrective surgery. These women may also face problem reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. In many cases the situation is aggravated by the increasing poverty women with fistula face due to their limited income generating resources (WHO, 2019).

Obstetric fistula is an international public health problem with serious psychosocial consequences. It is characterized by significant emotional disturbance due to continuous involuntary leakage of urine and/or faeces and the resultant discrimination as a result of persistent offensive odour. It is prevalent in resources-poor countries of the world of which Nigeria is included. The experience has overturned the life of many women and makes it miserable. Many have lived for many years rejected and abandoned without hope to live a normal life again. Others have contemplated suicide because of their situations, but thanks to the management of the Family Life Centre at Mbribit Itam and other centres in Nigeria that have given hope to these women through successful surgical repair.

Over the years, there has been a great achievement in the physical treatment of many obstetric fistula patients. However, the long term emotional, psychological, social and economic needs of women after surgical repair have received little attention. For instance, Nduka *et al.* (2023) reported that psycho-social support for women living with obstetric fistula in Nigeria is limited. Nduka further reported that women living with obstetric fistula in Nigeria were found to be ostracized, abandoned by families and friends, stigmatized and discriminated against, which led to depression, loneliness, loss of self-esteem, self-worth and identity. These women also face the problem of reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. Degge *et al.* (2019) reported a rehabilitation program for rehabilitation offered to the women who were affected by obstetric fistula, which made them hopeful and resilient. However, there is paucity of research on the reintegration of women suffering from obstetric fistula in Akwa Ibom State. To bridge this gap, the present study examined stigmatization and reintegration challenges of women with obstetric fistula in Akwa Ibom State, with specific focus on availability of re-integration programs and coping strategies.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Vesico-Vaginal Fistula (VVF)

Vesico-vaginal fistula an abnormal opening between the vagina, bladder and/or rectum, often caused by prolonged obstructed labour and is marked by incontinence of urine, faeces or both (El-Azab *et al.*, 2019). It is closely and directly linked to maternal mortality and morbidity. Basically, there are two main types: (a) Vesico-vaginal fistula (VVF) which is a situation in which the abnormal opening is between the bladder and the vagina resulting in continuous leakage of urine and, (b) Recto-vaginal fistula (RVF), which is a situation when the opening is between the rectum and the vagina resulting in leakage of faeces.

The earliest and oldest evidence of obstructed labour was discovered in the remains of Queen Henhenit, who was a wife of King Mentuhotep II of Egypt sometime in 2050 BC. This observation was made when the Queen's mummy, on discovery by Edouard Naville, was sent to the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York in 1907. A thorough observation of the Queen's mummy indicated that the vagina was normal while there was a mass of tissue 10 cm long, possibly intestine sticking out through the anus.

In 1923, the mummy was returned to Cairo for detailed clinical examination by Professor D. E Derry, which showed that there was a tear in the bladder connecting to the vagina. A closer examination also indicated that the pelvic bone was abnormal in shape, approximating that of apes. Considering the width of the pelvis, the examiner believed it was too small or narrow to allow a passage of fetal head, and that the severe pain and damage done to the bladder and vagina could have been responsible for the death of Queen Henhenit (Zacharin in Agu, 2013).

Prior to the above discovery, an Arabo-Persian physician, named Avicenna, who died in 1037 AD, was the first individual to observe that urinary incontinence in women may be as a result of fistula consequent upon obstructed labour (Agu, 2013). While linking difficult labour to fistula, he advised on pregnancy prevention, especially among young girls, he thus said “in cases in which women are married young, and in patients who have weak bladders, the physician should instruct the patient in the ways of prevention of pregnancy. In these patients, bulk of foetus may cause a tear in the bladder which results in incontinence of urine. The condition is incurable and remains so till death.”

The end of 1600 BC however, became a remarkable period because that was when several clearer descriptions of fistula started coming up. In 1597, Felix Platter, Basle gave the following description of fistula: “as a consequence of a first labour, the young country girl had the opening of the bladder rent to such a degree that there was a long gapping furrow in its place, and the open bladder could be seen on account of this injury, there is a constant involuntary discharge of urine, and the surrounding parts become excoriated and inflamed” (Zacharin in Agu, 2013).

At the beginning of 19th century, major progress was made in the repair and treatment of Vesico-vaginal fistula. Notable among the physicians at the time were de Lmballe, Wutser, Simon, Sims, Emmet and Bozeman (Agu, 2013). Between 1845 and 1859, Doctor Marion Sims has become famous for his aggressive discoveries of instruments and materials used in closing enormous fistula. Till date Sim has been praised for recognizing that health problem faced by women required urgent medical and surgical attention (Fasakin, 2007).

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Several studies report gathered from hospitals in Nigeria show that less than one percent of hospital deliveries are complicated by fistula Harrison (2014). Monitoring of 22,774 deliveries in Zaria from 1976 to 1979 found out those 79 women who had developed VVF was as a result of obstructed labour primarily due to cephalopelvic disproportion. Ijaiya et al (2010). In a report titled; Vesico Vaginal Fistula: A Review of Nigerian Experience, revealed that many Nigerian women are living with vesico-vaginal fistula with the annual obstetric fistula incidence estimated at 2.11 per 1000 births with its prevalent more in northern Nigeria than in southern Nigeria. Obstetric fistula accounts for 84.1%– 100% of the vesicovaginal fistula and prolonged obstructed labour is consistently the most common cause (65.9%–96.5%) in all the series.

Other common causes include caesarean section, advanced cervical cancer, uterine rupture, and Gishiricut. The identified predisposing factors were early marriage and pregnancy, which were rampant in northern Nigeria, while unskilled birth attendance and late presentation to the health facilities was common nationwide. Among the significant contributory factors to high rate of unskilled birth attendance were poverty, illiteracy, ignorance, restriction of women's movement, non-permission from husband, and transportation. All but one Nigerian studies revealed that primiparous women were the most vulnerable group. Pregnancy outcome was dismal in most cases related to delivery with still birth rate of 87%– 91.7%. Stigmatization, divorce and social exclusion were common complications. Overall fistula repair success rate was between 75% and 92% in a few centres that offer such services, Ijaiya *et al* (2010).

Lister in Agu (2013) four years study on 320 cases of obstructed labour in the University College Hospital Ibadan (UCH), observed that (6.6%) 21 of the obstructed labour resulted in VVF. Of the 21 cases, 2 healed spontaneously, 10 were repaired, 1 patient died before repair was possible and nine patients remained untraced. In the same study, he observed 17,230 delivery cases, giving an incidence of obstructed labour of 1 in 189 deliveries accounting for (27.2%) 44 of the 162 maternal deaths in the period.

According to Thaddeus and Maine in Odu and Cleland (2013) analyzed the contributory factors to the delayed treatment in the developing countries. Factors were grouped into three broad categories which were termed the three phases of delay; firstly, delay is looked on the part of the pregnant women, her family or both; secondly, delay in getting to a well-established health care facility and lastly, delay in promptly receiving health care once

their destination has been reached. These delays from available literature are due to the means of getting to the exact place where adequate health-care facility can be sought. Most of the VVF patients come from very poor background, and as such cannot readily get money to transport themselves to the city's health centres. It is when the health of a VVF patient is being seriously threatened and affected that the husband or relatives gather their few belongings for sale in order to get transportation fare to and fro a health centre in the city. The last delay is very peculiar to the Nigeria health system. Some of the health personnel are always very careless with the lives of others, and some get discouraged and prefer to stay at home to be attended to by the traditional birth attendants who are always very caring about the lives of others though they may not have the required knowledge education to carry out what is required of them. Apart from the carelessness of the personnel, there are shortages of supplies and equipment and the interminable internal delays involved in making a marginal work. (Wall in Odu and Cleland, 2013).

Challenges of Women Living with VVF

Evidence shows that many women and girls with obstetric fistulas faced many psychological problems such as humiliation (reported by 97.2% of victims); abandonment, stigmatization, and loneliness (reported by 95.8%) (Ezekiel *et al.*, 2021; Oluwasola and Bello, 2020). Similar studies showed that 85% of women experienced separation from their husbands, and 95.4% reported despair (Baba, 2014; Ezekiel *et al.*, 2021). Women with obstetric fistulas are often afraid and uncertain about their future with sexual partners, marriage, sex, pregnancy, childbirth, and reintegration into the neighborhood community (Letchworth *et al.*, 2018; Khisa *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, other evidence in the developing world shows a divorce rate of 36% to 67%, a stillborn rate of 55.6% to 85%, childlessness of 83.3%, frequent maternal loss of self-esteem, depression, and suicidal thoughts. Urinary inconsistency due to obstetric fistula affects patient self-esteem and quality of life. These can lead to secondary morbidity, disability, infertility, and significant costs for women with obstetric fistula (Ruiz and Kaiser, 2017). However, due to more than one factor, women with fistulas nevertheless live in silence with suffering, and repairing their emotional harm has not gotten much emphasis so far (Bakundane, 2016).

Psychological Consequences of VVF

The psychological consequences of obstetric fistula are substantial, with depression and early death from suicide (FIGO, 2016). Holtz and Ahmed (2017) demonstrate that women suffering the ordeal of fistula are abandoned by their husbands and family, and are shunned from their communities. Fistula is considered a “social calamity” and women with fistula are often ostracized by their husbands, families, and communities. The condition is often considered a sexually transmitted disease and viewed as a punishment from God. Most women with fistulas report disturbed socio-psychosexual lives and are usually deserted by their husbands. Often, until they are cured, married women with obstetric fistula are sent back to their parents' home where they are not allowed to cook food, participate in social events, or to perform religious rituals. Not only that mourning a dead child is almost inevitable for a woman with a fistula from obstructed labour, but she soon finds herself fighting for her own survival, social position, and value in society. Mentally she is tormented and devastated.

Physical Consequences of VVF

Physical/ medical consequences of obstetric fistula include ulceration, infection, foot drop, kidney diseases and dehydration. In almost all cases of obstetric fistula the leaking of urine and the offensive smell makes the women highly stigmatized and ashamed of themselves (Holtz and Ahmed, 2017; Cook et al., 2014). Consequently, eating, sleeping and praying alone (social isolation), abandonment and divorce, loss of self-esteem and economic deprivation occur. Due to misperceptions surrounding the condition, many of the women survivors see themselves as wretched or cursed, isolating them from their communities and preventing them from seeking help and treatment.

Stigmatization of Women Living with VVF

According to the needs assessment carried out by MOH and UNFPA (2014) stigma is an elusive concept, but one that is increasingly recognized as a major component in the perception of the ill person. In Mwingi, Kwale and Homa Bay districts the issue of stigma is not so explicit. The general feeling was that their immediate families did not reject women with fistulas. However, the women, out of their own volition segregated themselves from others because of the embarrassment occasioned by the foul smell. However, having a fistula among the Pokot attracts a social stigma from the community in that the women cannot stay with others or even cook for the family. Worse still is the situation where a husband returns the wife to her father and demands a refund of the bride price especially if the fistula occurs at birth of the first child.

Fistula is invariably devastating to the lives of women who survive and endure it (Cook et al., 2014). Affected women are frequently driven from their marriages, families and communities to a point of becoming socially invisible and forgotten. They experience a foul smell that results from leaking urine and faecal incontinence and are barred from family activities like cooking and at times driven into isolation. Denied family support, the malnutrition and poverty is aggravated and at times when they can, such women have depended on begging, prostitution or stigmatizing employment. Arguably, social stigma contributes further to women's poverty and gender inequalities.

Women living with fistula experience seclusion and stigma owing to the offensive smell and cultural taboos and this may still be a challenge even after corrective surgery. These women may also face problem reintegrating into their local communities that may desert them or regard them as unclean or cursed. In many cases the situation is aggravated by the increasing poverty women with fistula face due to their limited income generating resources (WHO, 2019).

Reintegration Strategies of Women Living with VVF

Reintegration refers to the re-acceptance of the obstetric fistula patients back into their social environment following their harrowing experiences of either fecal or urinary incontinence and in some instances, both of which have been associated with loss of self-esteem and dignity. It is therefore aimed at enabling them realize their full potential in life and gain emotional and psychosocial stability through culturally accepted counselling, peer and community support (Khisa, 2010). Rehabilitation on the other hand, refers to any experience that strives to improve the quality of lives of women before or after corrective surgery

(Lombard, 2010). It is sometimes used interchangeably with reintegration, and includes programs aimed to improve overall status of women, through empowerment and enhancement of their socio-economic status such as vocational

Nigeria having 40% of the global burden of obstetric fistula has put in place measures to eradicate obstetric fistula and its sequels (Ojengbede, 2017). The federal ministry of health designed a National Strategic Framework for Elimination of Obstetric Fistula in Nigeria which guides activities conducted at Federal, state, local level, civil society, and those of and by development partners. The country has 12 dedicated centers for obstetric fistula surgery which also take care of reintegration and rehabilitation as important components of holistic care. Each year, the centers repair 2000 to 4000 obstetric fistula patients, however, the backlog is enormous and it requires more than 100 years to deal with it while ignoring new cases who are 20,000 per annum. The Federal Ministry of Health and stakeholders are dedicated to reduce obstetric fistula incidence rate by 50% and increase rehabilitation by the same percentage.

A study done in Nigeria by Capes et al. (2011) on postoperative care pointed out that all fistula centers and some teaching hospitals have rehabilitation centers where patients can be referred to after repair. In addition to government activities, the Foundation for Women's Health Research and Development (FORWARD) and AMREF for Health provide a holistic approach of care through surgery, and supporting women to have positive rehabilitation experiences through skills training, and creating community awareness, health education, offering gifts in form of clothing and soap and home based care (Fistula Foundation, 2018). A study conducted by Ojengbede (2017) stated that 67% of women who have had successful repair need family support as a backup for their effective reintegration while 60% consider work resumption as imperative in making them feel normal and accepted. In Tanzania, same factors were mentioned by 68% of the successfully repaired obstetric fistula patients as imperative in their effective reintegration.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Goffman's Stigma Theory – Goffman (1963)

The study is guided by Erving Goffman's stigma theory (Goffman, 1963). Goffman defines stigma as an 'attribute that is deeply discrediting', reducing the person that possesses a particular quality 'from a whole and usual person to a tainted and discredited one' whereby consequently the person is socially discounted. For Goffman, the stigmatized can be either discreditable or discredited. The former refers to people that possess a stigmatizing characteristic but have not yet been discredited, mainly because this quality has not yet been fully revealed. The latter relates to those who have been socially judged and marginalized by their surrounding social world.

Stigmatization is the result of a socialization process whereby the person with the quality generally holds the same identity beliefs as normal (i.e. persons without a stigmatizing characteristic) and may in fact feel normal when alone. This is then displaced by a sense of deep abnormality in the presence of normal, frequently resulting in feelings of self-hate, self-isolation, depression and/or hostility. Goffman describes the socialization of the personal identity of a stigmatized person as a process of information control. The discreditable person manages information, continually judging whether or not to reveal their stigmatic quality.

When the person is actually discredited, they are faced with managing the tension that will ensue. Passing is a central concept developed by Goffman, which he uses to help describe information control. This refers to when a person with a stigmatic quality manages information so that they can partly or fully 'pass' as a normal. Given the rewards of being normal, the stigmatized will attempt to pass if they can. Passers draw on several information control strategies. These can include the concealment of stigmatic symbols or use of dis-identifiers.

The relationship of the stigmatized with normal highlights their deviation from societal norms. Consequently, the stigmatized manage their social deviance by creating their own social norms that they will measure themselves against, alienating themselves from the community that upholds the stigmatizing norms, or employing a variety of passing techniques to manage information and their status among the stigmatized and normal.

This theory is quite relevant to this study as it explains the effect of stigmatization on individuals. These ones' always live with the tension that comes from stigmatization and can hardly become emotionally stable. Such individuals can find it challenging to succeed economically as many who stigmatized that may not patronize them or discourage others from patronizing them. The theory further indicated that people can cope with stigmatization by managing information about their reason of stigmatization.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive phenomenology. According to Falaye (2018) phenomenological research is to understand the essence of a social phenomenon from the perspective of those who have experience it. This has two implications. One, people experience what is important for them to know and how they interpret what they experienced within their domain. The second implication is methodological. Phenomenological research design was considered appropriate for this study since the researcher was also interested in conducting in-depth interview to find out the challenges of women living with VVF and that of those who have undergone successful repair.

This study was conducted in the Family Life Centre Located in Mbribit Itam, Itu Local Government Area. The Family Life Centre is located at Mbribit Itam in Itu Local Government Area. It is *an efficient reproductive health and family Health counselling centre with highly skilled personnel*. Family Life Centre/ V.V.F Hospital is a Faith Based hospital which was established in the 1980s. The idea of Family Life Centre/V.V.F Hospital was the initiative of an MMM (Medical Missionaries of Mary sister) obstetrician/ gynecologist - Sr. Dr. Ann Ward. In 1960s while working in St. Luke's hospital, Anua, Sr. Dr. Ward was touched by the large number of young women whose lives were damaged by dehumanizing obstetric injuries. She started offering surgeries to these ladies at that time in St. Luke's Hospital, Anua. As the number increased, it became difficult for her to get enough bed space for them and she also realized they needed specialized care both before and after the surgery. It was then she conceived the idea to get a place for these women who would nurture a supportive environment and where she could train staff on the special kind of care these women needed. Hence Family Life Centre/V.V.F Hospital /VVF hospital was given birth to (<https://www.familylifehospital.org/details/Philosophy/1>).

The population of the study was made up of all women suffering from VVF who were receiving treatment at the Family Life Centre/VVF Hospital Mbribit Itam as at January 2022, the centre reported that 145 patients registered for the VVF/RVF operation. (The Guardian, 2022). A sample size of 17 women was selected for the study. The selection was done using convenience sampling technique. According to Fleetwood (2019) convenience sampling is defined as a method adopted by researchers where they collect research data from a conveniently available pool of respondents. The researcher used an instrument entitled “Challenges of VVF Interview Schedule” was used in collecting data for the study. Data collected for the study were analyzed manually using the inductive approach of analyzing qualitative data.

RESULT

Level of Stigmatization Experienced by Women Living with VVF

The women living with VVF are stigmatized and isolated by member of their families and the community. There is little interaction between a victim of VVF and her community. When there is any form of interaction, they are ridiculed and made to feel less of human being. Some of them are isolated to live in a separate house or room with little interaction with other members of the family and the community in general. Only those women who have the means to package themselves without the notice of others are free from ridicule in the community, but cannot escape from that of their immediate family members. Narrating this challenge, one fistula patient expresses her experience thus;

I lived with my brother and my uncle. I used to change cloths frequently and used rags to collect the urine feces that used to come out. I tried to keep myself very clean, but I always smell because of the leaking urine and feces. My uncle's wife used to cause me and I cried all day long. She could not bear me staying with them again, and my uncle had to send me away to stay in a building without good doors and window. Some people thought I was mad. I could not stay where others are. Even my friends would always disperse if I go to where they are gathering. It was one day, as my uncle's wife was causing me that a nurse that brought me here heard her and asked of where I am. She directed her to me and the nurse took me here for treatment. I really thank God that the surgery was successful.

Another survivor describes her experience while living with VVF this way;

Some looked down upon me. They looked down upon me and laughed at me. They said look at her, she is torn. She is torn at the buttocks! That time, I couldn't talk to people, because they would throe bad words at me. I always avoid where people gather and it was very difficult to even attend church because no one will sit close to me. This is because my seat will always be wet before the close of church for the day. It was very disturbing until I was treated. This is me now, I can stay close to people without smelling.

This was corroborated by key informants who reported that women living with VVF face social stigma and isolation. They are alienated from their husbands, their parents, the other family members and the community at large. In some cases, these women are sent to stay outside the compound so as not to bring shame to their families; they eat and live on their own. Secluded, they also face other challenges such as lack of food or even drinking water.

Challenges of Reintegration of VVF Survivors

The challenges women face after a successful VVF surgery was discussed with some of the women. They mention economic challenge and stigmatization as the main challenge they face. Some of the women mention that many people who knew about their situation find it difficult to believe that they are totally free. They further mentioned that many people still relate with them after the surgery the same way they did before the surgery. For instance, many people who knew about their situation before the surgery would change their sitting location if they happened to sit with them. One of the survivor commented;

I still find it difficult to make people believe me that I do not smell like before. I always feel ashamed when people change their seats when I happened to sit with them. Some of my friends do not still allow me to share in preparing food in some occasions. When I attended marriage and ladies were asked to come and share food, many people who knew about my situation refuse to collect food from me. I was very ashamed of myself when I noticed that they collected from others after rejecting mine.

Another respondent also mentioned stigmatization as a challenge to their reintegration after the surgery. She narrated her experience, thus;

I thank God almighty that I had finally have a cure to my illness. To God be the glory. Though I am free from my sickness, my mother in-law is the one that tries to annoy me. My husband do not have any problem with me, and I always thank God for him. My mother in-law is the problem I am having. She has not been eating my food since this sickness started and will be discussing me to others in the community. When I came back from the surgery, I told her that I am now free from the sickness, she has not still believe me. I noticed that she continue throwing my food away anytime I give her food, so I stopped. I still find it difficult to convince my mother in-law that I am free from the sickness.

Aside from stigmatization being a challenge to the reintegration of women who had successful VVF repair, means of survival is also a great challenge to many. Among these are those who do not have parents or were divorce by their husbands. Some of them are attaching themselves to some religious organizations in order to get support from there. Others are totally depending on the family life centre for their survival and help provided by visitors to the family life centre. This makes it difficult for some of them to mix freely with others since they are still having this feeling of being inferior to others. One of the respondents

commented;

Since I don't have what to do, I decided to stay here. At least, I am being provided with food here. If I go now, I will not have means to survive. I know how I suffered before getting to this place. It is only God that touches the heart of some people to give me food. I used to stay for some days without food. It is even better here, I am only praying that God should make a way for me to have what I can use to take care of myself.

Another respondent commented;

Life was hard when I was suffering from this sickness and it is still hard by now. I used to run a restaurant business. When I had this problem, I couldn't do it again. People did not like to come and eat in the place. My husband left me and survived all alone. I had to sell most of my belongings in order to survive. I have nothing left for me except my cloths. How to start the business again is my greatest challenge. I sometimes go to some church and tell people about my situation to see if I can get help. I am not a lazy person, and I don't want to beg. All what I need is the means to start my own business. Since I cannot achieve that, the only option for me is to continue staying here in the family life centre.

In addition to economic challenge, some of them equally reported having challenge with participation in social life. One of the women commented;

Taking part in social life is painful for us as we think of our odour always. For example, going to church, going to a marital ceremony, and coming to the house to stay and chat with neighbours is difficult. The difficulty was socializing as before. I'm still trying to see how I can mix with other people without feeling ashamed of myself.

Reintegrating VVF Survivors

Some of the women who have survived VVF repair mentioned some of the strategies that help or prevented their reintegration after the surgery. Some of these were supported by key informants who also mentioned other strategies that they have observed during their interaction with VVF survivors. These strategies that influence the reintegration of VVF survivors were discussed, followed by highlights findings on proposed avenues for reintegrating VVF survivors. Most of the proposed avenues were reported by both the survivors and key informants.

- ***Skill training***

Some of VVF survivors were trained by the management of the VVF centre at Mbribit Itam on various skills such as tailoring and hair dressing. Those who received these training reported occupying their minds with the training, instead of always thinking of their situation. Others mentioned that the training helped them to start mixing freely with people especially with the different trainers employed to teach them the skills and they also feel a bit free to interact with visitors who come to the facility. One of the survivor commented;

I really appreciate the management of family life centre for giving me the opportunity to learn tailoring after my successful surgery. Initially, I was thinking how people will look at me if I try getting close to them, but through this tailoring business, I am close to others who suffered the same situation as mine, I am equally close to my trainers who did not even suffer what I went through. I even have the opportunity to go out and buy clothing materials for the training and people do not know what I went through because I do not smell like before. I am really happy that many people that I meet out there do not despise me like before. I feel more comfortable interacting with other people gradually. My only fear now is about those that knew about my situation before now, but I believe they will notice that I no longer smell like before.

Also, another survivor who learned hair dressing has this to say;

I really thank God for the opportunity to come here and be healed. My condition was terrible. My mother died and my father married another woman, the woman used to maltreat us and will not give us food, and that was why I had a boyfriend that put me into this trouble and everybody including my boyfriend abandoned me. I used to cry every day. Thank God that I am healed and I also learn this hair dressing that can help me to make my money and survive. This hair dressing business will help me not to go back and depend on my father and my step mother. I don't feel ashamed staying with people again.

Aside from learning skills as a means of rehabilitating these women, there was also provision for counselling. Many of the survivors have taken advantage of the various counselling session to adjust their mind and belief that they are still humans and have self-worth. They believe that then can still be loved by others and can still live a normal life despite what happened to them. These ones still hope that they would marry one day, but that they would do all what it takes to prevent this situation from repeating itself. One of the respondent commented;

First of all, I want to thank God almighty for what he has done in my life in this Family Life Centre. I did not believe I will ever mix with people again. My mother has tried many places, but there was no cure to my situation until we were directed to this place after many years of suffering. Initially, when I have this problem, I really hate men. I did not think I will marry again, but through the counselling that we used to have here, I learned that I can still marry and that it is possible for me to still have children. If a man comes now, I will still get married.

Some of the survivor also mentioned family support as one of the important factors that helped them in the reintegration process. In cases where the family supported the survivors, they settled down better and were able to live normal lives, get children and do business. One survivor who had been received support from her husband commented;

My husband has really tried for me. When I was suffering from the sickness, he did not abandon me. He did all he could to help me in my situation. Even though her relatives advised him to send me away and marry another woman, he refused. He said I did not have this problem in my father's house. Now that I have been successfully repaired, he has not abandoned me. He still provides me with food here and I do visit him from time to time. I only stay here to learn this tailoring. When am done, I will go back to my husband. He is a good man, God will bless him.

Other who have been taken back by their parents and cared for has also reported feeling relieved and being able to associate with people. One of the survivor who reported being abandoned by his father and step mother while she was suffering from the sickness reported that after treatment, her father came to take her home. She was advised not to return home without a skill in order not to be a burden to her parents again. In words, she stated;

Life was not fair to me. When I had this problem, I was abandoned by my stepmother and father. Now that I have been repaired, I was very happy to see my father coming to take me home. Initially, I was thinking where I will go to, and how my parents will look at me. Now he is the one that asked me to come back home, I am very happy about that.

However, not every woman who had undergone repair was able to get back and receive support from families. Some who had been chased away from home are yet to see any of their family members visiting them. They reported experiencing a lot of problems due to little or no family support.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study has revealed that women who are suffering from VVF in Akwa Ibom State are stigmatized. The reason for the findings could be as a result of the offensive odour that comes from them. This can make them appear to be irritating to people. Even their close friends can feel uncomfortable staying close to them. The stigmatization can lead to abandonment of these women to fend for themselves even with their situation. This is in line with Khisa (2010), who stated that married survivors often are abandoned or forced to separate from their husbands. He further stated that in some cases, in-laws support the survivors and are sympathetic to their plight, on the other hand, the majority contribute to their ostracizing and at times advise their relatives to leave the woman with obstetric fistula and marry another wife. Left without any social or material support, the survivors' situation deteriorates as they often lack basic necessities such as food, shelter, water, soap among others. The finding of this study is similar to that of Emma-Echiegu, *et al.*, (2014) who reported that women living with VVF are stigmatized. The researcher further stated that many of them are avoided, made jest of, laughed at, or mocked. Some stated that they can only relate with their relatives, while others do not want to have anything to do with them. They would not even be allowed to share food no

matter how neatly they appear to dress as people will not collect their food they share.

On the rehabilitation of VVF survivors who have undergone successful surgery, the findings of the study indicated that what is commonly done is helping them to learn trade and providing counselling services. The family life Centre at Mbribit Itam makes provision for these women to learn tailoring and hair dressing in their facility. Trainers are employed by the management of the facility to train these women. Many of them have gone far with the training while others are just starting. These ones appear happy, especially now that they are free from the sickness. Interaction with them indicated that before their surgery, they were not happy people because they were sidelined and rejected by many people. However, they now see life differently after the surgery, since they are trying to mix and interact with others in the process of their training. They find it easier to interact with their colleagues who have also been successfully repaired. With time, they extended their interaction and association to others who visit the centre. The finding of the study is similar to that of Khisa (2010) who identified skill training as one of the major rehabilitation strategies adopted to reintegrate women who have successfully undergone VVF repair.

On the effect of counselling service on the rehabilitation of women who have successfully been repaired of VVF, the study indicated that the family life centre provides both group and individual counselling services to these women. Many of them have reported how beneficial the counselling services have been to them in trying to associate with others. The reason for the findings could be that many of these women might still be looking down on themselves and considering that they have very little or low self-worth compared to others. They might also consider all men as being evil, since their husbands or boyfriends were responsible for the pregnancy that led to their situations. Counselling service provided by the centre might have helped these ones to see life differently and forgive those that hurt them while they were suffering from the sickness. The finding of this study is similar to that of Khisa (2010) who also reported counselling as one of the major factors that help in reintegrating women who have successfully completed VVF repair.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that women suffering from VVF are stigmatized and that the common reintegration strategies adopted after their repairs were skill training, counselling and family support.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The government should expand surgical facilities to make it easy for women suffering from VVF to access treatment, since this can ease the reintegration process.
2. Reintegration program designers should bear in mind that all girls and women with fistula are not the same, as such, reintegration strategies need to address the different situations in which these women may find themselves.
3. There should be couple counselling services before and after surgery to help the survivors' husband to cooperate and support the reintegration process.

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IMPACTS OF MODERNIZATION ON TRADITIONAL MARRIAGE CEREMONY OF THE IBIBIO ETHNIC GROUP OF SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative research used ethnographic methodology to investigate impact of modernization on Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony, among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Modernization theory was adopted for a theoretical framework. Fetterman big-net approach was adopted by the researcher for randomly selection of participants from Etinan, Ibesikpo-Asutan, Ikono and Uruan local government areas. Method of data collection include interview, participant observation and key informant interview. Instrument for data collection was interview guide which was used by the researchers. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts from responses of the study participants. Findings of the study through gathered data show that the order of events during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio has changed due to influence of modernization. Changes were observed in traditional attires, order of traditional rites and introduction of strange delicacies. Among others, the researcher recommended that the Ibibio people should endeavour to promote their cultural values in order to preserve the existence of the fourth largest ethnic group in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Traditional marriage, culture, Ibibio and traditional rites

INTRODUCTION

Culture is universal and marriage is a culture trait. Marriage is an important cultural practice that characterizes every cultural group. Every ethnic group across the earth defines its cultural pre-requisites and processes through which marriage contract is performed, marriage is engaged and the processes or conditions through which marriages are disengaged. These

cultural pre-requisites, processes and conditions form the cultural patterns of marriage for a given cultural or ethnic group, and they are culturally defined by the people which make them differ from one cultural group to the other. These cultural definitions of the cultural groups form the traditions for which the people uphold, preserve their marital practices, and transfer same as traditions from one generation to the other. Traditional African Marriage is a complex institution, involving several stages and characterized by the performance of constituted rites (Ndu-Udeji, 2021).

Marriage from the beginning was meant for the procreation and promotion of life (Kyalo, 2022). Marriage and the idea of marriage are universal but with its definition, there is no one generally acceptable definition of marriage due to its cultural contexts (Ogoma, 2014). Marriage is a relationship between one or more men (male or female) and one or more women (female or male) recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another (Haviland, 2000). Marriage is a transaction and resulting contract in which a woman and a man are recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another, and in which the woman involved is eligible to bear children (Haviland 1996).

Marriage is a union between a man and a woman such that the children born to the woman are recognized as legitimate offspring of both partners. According to Edmund Leach cited in Haviland (1996), marriage can, but doesn't always, accomplish the following: establish the legal father of a woman's children and the legal mother of a man, give either or both spouses a monopoly in the sexuality of the other, give either or both spouses rights to the labour of the other, give either or both spouses rights over the other's property, establish a joint fund or property which is a partnership, for the benefit of the children and establish a socially significant relationship of affinity between spouses and their relatives.

Modernization is an encompassing process of massive social changes that, once set in motion, tends to penetrate all domains of life, from economic activities, social life, to political institutions, in a self-reinforcing process (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005). Modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation, linked with the idea that human societies are progressing (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005). Capitalist notions of modernization have consciously or unconsciously adopted the Marxist idea that modernization starts with changes at the socioeconomic basis, from which it moves on to changes in the institutional and cultural superstructure. The term modernization connotes first of all changes in production technology inducing major economic transitions from preindustrial to industrial societies and from industrial to post-industrial societies. The post-industrial societies are characterized by high level of technological innovations which have brought about the ease path of globalization with influence of culture battles which have produce the dynamic nature of culture through culture shift (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005).

Marriage is a complex of social, political, religious, and economic systems in Ibibio which covers diverse aspects of the society as family and community relationships, sex and sexuality, inheritance, and even political power (as rulership particularly in the past resided in specific and designated families both the secular and the religious) (Ubong, 2010). Marriage in Ibibio land is believed to perform many functions which include procreation, regulate sexual behavior, fulfill economic needs of partners, perpetuates kinships group, and provide institution for enculturation or socialization of children. These functions have over the ages

made marriage a valuable institution among the Ibibio people of the Southern Nigeria. Most social relations are constructed on the basis of marriage union (Wilson, 2007).

The technology which drives modernization has brought about the influences of different cultures of the various parts of the world to Africa and with the high level of illiteracy in Africa, the exploit of technology upon culture and cultural values is fast becoming a great challenge to the African traditional values and the resulting societal problems. The advancement in technology and its consequent globalised influence through various forms of information communication technology has brought changes to the world with many African nations pushing for development thereby buying into the technological phase through internet and satellite television, and the use of handheld phones which bring the various cultures of the world into the hand of the majority of Africans like in Nigeria.

The Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria has been part of the Africans who are making influential use of handheld phone and other forms of technology like the internet and satellite television. Ubong (2010) has posited that what has changed significantly in marriage in Ibibio land has to do with performance during traditional marriage ceremonies, ending the function at night, alterations arising from conflict during negotiations on required traditional items on the 'list' to size of bride price. It is observable that technology has enhance diverse forms of influential shifts in the dynamics of the Ibibio culture especially in the area of traditional marriage ceremony. The shift has brought about different forms of conflicts from the immediate family system to the external societal influence. It is clearly witnessed today within the Ibibio society, that traditional forms of Ibibio marriage and its functions are facing challenges due to culture shift forced by the influence of modernization through the high rate of use of technology among the people. This is creating serious socio-cultural issues among families and the society. According to Paul and Peters (2023), most marriages experience economic, emotional and spiritual instability and hardship which are often the characteristics of post-marriage ceremonies, which are as results of recent changes in Ibibio traditional marriage. Some girls are growing older without suitors, some grooms to-be have decided to practice co-habitation instead of going out for full marriage, girls are becoming single parents in their parents houses and young people are reluctant of going out for full traditional marriage, thereby making the Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony a function for some people. Against this backdrop, having identified the gap in influence of modernization on the traditional marriage system among the Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria, this research sought to examine influence of modernization on the traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State in South-South region of Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Marriage

Marriage from history until recent has been a sacred relationship between man and woman. Odejobi (2013) described marriage as a social institution that unites people in a special form of mutual dependence for the purpose of finding and maintaining a family. It is a culturally sanctioned union between two or more people that establish certain rights and obligations between them, their children and their in-laws. Marriage is an important and natural process in human life that has existed in all cultures and periods in different forms. It has attempted to bridge two ideas with different values and ideologies and to construct human relations.

Havillard et al (2011) noted that when viewed within the entire range of the past and present societies, marriage is more or less a durable union sanctioned by society. However, it is necessary that the relationship be formed and conducted in accordance with written customs and taboos as in primitive societies or in accordance with the established laws as in more sophisticated societies. (Encyclopaedia Americana, 1988 cited in Odunayo and Oyewole, (2019).

Marriage according to Haviland (2000) cited in University of Houston (2023), is a relationship between one or more men (male or female) and one or more women (female or male) recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another. Marriage is a transaction and resulting contract in which a woman and a man are recognized by society as having a continuing claim to the right of sexual access to one another, and in which the woman involved is eligible to bear children (Haviland 1996 cited in University of Houston, 2023). Marriage is a union between a man and a woman such that the children born to the woman are recognized as legitimate offspring of both partners (University of Houston, 2023).

According to Ogoma (2014), marriage is an essentially contentious concept. Marriage and the idea of marriage are universal and there is no one generally acceptable definition of marriage, which makes the definition of marriage relative. Ogoma (2014) further gave various definitions of marriage derived from encyclopaedia as a socially or ritually recognized union or legal contract between spouses that establishes rights and obligations between them and their children, and between them and their in-laws. The import of this definition is that where there are no children, there is no marriage. The same authority as reported by Ogoma traces the origin of marriage to the Middle English, marriage which was also a derivative of Old French *marier* which means to marry. *Marier* is also derived from a Latin word *maritare*, meaning, to be provided with a wife or husband. The same authority goes ahead to cite other authorities, among whom are; Edvard Westermarck who defines marriage as: “a more or less durable connection between male and female lasting beyond the mere act of propagation till the birth of the offspring.” Westermarck was to reject the definition years later and gave another more controversial definition of marriage as: “relation of one of one or more men to one or more women that is recognized by custom or law.” Ogoma (2014) also quotes from the anthropological handbook: Notes and Queries, that marriage is: “a union between a man and a woman such that children born from the woman are the recognized legitimate offspring of both partners.” None of these definitions meet our curiosity but they have been cited just to show how controversial the concept can be.

Marriage is an important and natural process in human life that has existed in all cultures and periods in different forms (Zaheri *et al*, 2020). It has attempted to bridge two ideas with different values and ideologies and to construct human relations. In addition, marriage aims to fulfill a variety of basic human needs such as generation survival and upbringing the children, fulfilling the dream of being parents, achieving the highest level of friendship and intimacy, labor division, cooperation, assisting one another in married life, having a safe place for peace and flourishing skills, as well as achieving human perfection and elevation and mental health (Zaheri *et al.*, 2019).

Ayisi (1997) cited in Ogoma (2014) defines marriage as the process whereby a man and a woman come together to form a union for the purpose of procreation. However, marriage can

be seen as an intended temporary or permanent union between a man and a woman that is socially, culturally or legally recognized (Ogoma, 2014). In other words, marriage is not just an agreement between a man and a woman to live together without the knowledge of others of the kind of relationship that exists between them. Marriage is a public matter. Tonizek (2008) identifies three different types of marriage which are; traditional, court and white marriages. White marriage is done in the Churches and Mosques where clergies preside over the affairs. The Court marriage is done under the law of the state. The traditional marriage is the local form of marriage. However, it is common to see some people taking part in all these forms of marriage.

Marriage from the point of institution of art is a drama in which everyone becomes an actor or actress and not just a spectator. Marriage is regarded as a complex of social, political, religious, and economic systems in Ibibio land (Udo, 1983 cited in Ubong, 2010). According to Ubong (2010) marriage covers diverse aspects of the society as family and community relationships, sex and sexuality, inheritance, and even political power (as rulership particularly in the past resided in specific and designated families both the secular and the religious). The family is not just a component of the man, the wife and their children, but the departed souls, relatives and the unborn generations are regarded as members of the family which make marriage not the union, or the joining of a man and a woman for the purpose of becoming husband and wife (Ubong, 2010).

According to Nmah (2012), for marriage to be marriage, there must be a will or two wills meeting together, that is, there is the consent between the man and the woman which is known as the matrimonial mutual will. According to Shorter (2001), marriage takes many cultural forms, but a general definition of marriage can be given. Marriage according to Shorter is an intimate union between a man and a woman, of which mating is an essential and sacred expression, establishing enforceable rights between them, marking a change of status for them and their parents, giving the children of the union a higher status than extramarital ones, generating relationships of consanguinity and affinity, implying that other forms of mating or intimacy are deviant or preparatory to marriage (Igodo, 2020).

African Conception on Marriage and Family

Marriage is as important as life in Africa. Marriage occupies an important position in the affairs of Africans, and without marriage, there is no family, and without a family, one could not bear children (Ogoma, 2014). The connection between marriage and family can hardly be separated among the traditional Africans. According to Ayisi (1997) as cited by Ogoma (2014), the family is then the logical outcome of marriage. A family consists of a man, his wife, and child or children. By this definition, Ogoma (2014) posits that a childless marriage is not a family and an individual belongs to at least one family in his lifetime. Since the family is the basic unit of any political and social organizations, the process of erecting it should and was given serious attention among the traditional African societies. Marriage, for Africans, though it is purposely for procreation, is more than that. Marriage serves other purposes. According to Ogoma (2014), for African peoples, marriage is the focus of existence. It is the point where all the members of a given community meet: the departed, the living and those yet unborn. All the dimensions of time meet here and the whole drama of history is repeated, renewed and revitalized.

African traditional conception of marriage is teleological. It is primarily for procreation. Marriage can be dissolved on the ground of childlessness. The importance attached to children is however without basis. One major reason for that attachment is summed up in what call is 'personal immortality.' To the African people, whenever a man dies, it is imperative for his offspring to bear his name, so that his name and lineage does not die. According to Awolalu and Adelumo (1979) cited by Ogoma (2014), the Yoruba attach importance to child-bearing. Unfruitful marriage is not only a misfortune but also a curse since the couple have not contributed to the community of the family and therefore, of the society.

In an agrarian society, especially in the past, the manliness of a man was measured by his farm produce. The higher the produce, the greater the respect accorded a man. Many hands in the farm led to greater output. Also, leadership roles and chieftaincy titles were reserved for men who had many wives and children under them. The reasoning behind this is that, a man who could control many wives and children, if given leadership roles, would be effective. Africans were not taught how not to die, but they believed that if they have many children, some of them would outlive them even if some of them would die (Ogoma, 2014).

The Concept of Traditional Marriage

Traditional marriage customs place great importance on parental consent and family involvement in the choice of couple's marriage partner (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019). In Africa, traditional marriage plays great role in ascertaining the legality of marriage among the people though the custom is culturally relative. This could have accounted for the relatively fewer divorces in the past because elders could be assumed to see through their noses more clearly than the young people that would have been blindfolded by what they call love (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019). Traditional marriage in African context used to have many rites of passages like the virginity test which was one of the factors that checkmate pre-marital sex and infidelity but today, traditional virginity test which helps to check indecency and pre-marital sexual relationships seem to have been abandoned (Odunayo and Oyewole, 2019).

Traditional Africans in general, and the Yoruba in particular, laid much premium on marriage because they know that if the foundation is weak, the entire building (that is, the society) will be negatively affected. They know that nothing can be built on nothing. They know that individuals make up the family and families make up the community. To build a strong and stable society therefore, the family must be well-founded (Ogoma, 2014).

Anthropologically, traditional marriage is the primary established form of marriage recognized in a given country or religious or social group at a given time: In that culture, traditional marriage requires the families of the future bride and grooms to engage in ritual visits and exchange gifts. Traditional marriage ceremony in many parts of Africa depends on payment of a bride price and in the past, the tradition of bride price was believed to have operated to give formal recognition to marriages and protect wives against abuse, stabilize the partnership and to join the two families together (Paul and Peters, 2023).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Modernization theory

Modernization theory is used to explain the process of modernization within societies. The "classical" theories of modernization of the 1950s and 1960s drew on sociological

analyses of Karl Marx, Emile Durkheim and a partial reading of Max Weber and were strongly influenced by the writings of Harvard sociologist Talcott Parsons. Modernization refers to a model of a progressive transition from a "pre-modern" or "traditional" to a "modern" society. Modernization theory suggests that traditional societies will develop as they adopt more modern practices. Proponents of modernization theory claim that modern states are wealthier and more powerful and that their citizens are freer to enjoy a higher standard of living. The theory looks at the internal factors of a country while assuming that with assistance, "traditional" countries can be brought to development in the same manner more developed countries have been. Modernization theory both attempts to identify the social variables that contribute to social progress and development of societies and seeks to explain the process of social evolution. Authors such as Daniel Lerner explicitly equated modernization with Westernization.

Modernization has greatly influenced the quest for change especially through western education in most of the traditional or rural societies across the world. The desire to be aligned with the developments of the western countries and other parts of the nation, the Ibibio people have chosen to adopt other dressing patterns from other culture to replace the dignified Ibibio traditional wears during traditional marriage ceremonies. In recent times, Ibibio young men are feeling ashamed to tie wrappers and some of them do not know how to tie the wrapper and are so uncomfortable with it. The quest to look-like and behave-like the civilized of the modern culture have made our young ones to push the Ibibio cultural patterns and practice in traditional marriage ceremonies to extinction.

METHODOLOGY

Ethnographic research design was adopted by the researchers for the study. This research design involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques such as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. The study was conducted in four Ibibio local government areas across Akwa Ibom State. Etinan Local Government Area, Ibessikpo-Asutan Local Government Area, Ikono Local Government Area and Uruan Local Government Area were selected for the study. Two villages were randomly selected from each of the four selected local government areas.

The researcher through Fetterman (2010) big-net approach randomly selected participants from one village per local government area. Study participants were randomly selected who co-operated, and were ready to give answers to the questions as were required. Method of data collection include interview, participant observation and key informant interview. Instrument for data collection was interview guide which was used by the researcher and his three research assistants. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts from responses of the study participants.

RESULT

Changes in Traditional Attires during Traditional Marriage Ceremony

Emergence from findings of the study shows that modernization in term of fashion through the many means of internet reach has greatly influence the mode of dressing among the Ibibio people. This influence has brought about a great shift in the dressing of the Ibibio

people who were known among the people of the Niger region of Nigeria to dress with wrappers, shirts or blouses with traditional hats as relatively connected to the ethnic culture of the group within the South-South region. Findings have revealed that, there is a culture shift in the mode of dressing especially during traditional marriage ceremonies of some Ibibio people.

The majority of the study participants agreed through their responses to interviews that there have been situations whereby an Ibibio man or woman will rather prefer another cultural attire to the Ibibio traditional wrapper and shirt or blouse during their traditional marriage ceremony. One of the study participants during interview reported that;

My brother we are seeing different things these days with our children. May be it is because they are fortunate to travel out or may be it is because of the big phones they use today which according to them they can reach anywhere through their phones. They are borrowing so many things into our traditional marriage ceremony which were not part of our traditional marriage ceremony. Like today as I observed along stadium road, I saw a picture of the traditional marriage and I thought it was a Yoruba boy who was coming to marry our daughter because of the Yoruba *apada* that he wore. But when I find out, it was our son in the Yoruba attire. What is wrong with our own wrapper or our cultural wears? Are we now saying that their traditional wears are better than our own? We have to curtail this influence else, we will be strangers in our own land (male, 63 years, Etinan, Retired Civil Servant)

Another participant from Uruan Local Government Area in his responses reported that;

There is a lot of changes in our dressing code during marriage ceremony here in Uruan. Before now, we used to wear what is called *Ayoioyo* which to alot of people, it is believed to be the Efik traditional dress. The *Ayoioyo* is Uruan traditional dress for women especially in traditional occasions or ceremonies like the traditional marriage ceremony. But today there have been several changes in terms of our mode of dressing in Uruan. The young generation are copying everything they see in television and phones and so many of them do not know about their culture which is the more reason why they are wearing everything they see and everything they feel is attractive to them. These changes have to be control. We have to begin to promote our traditional wears especially during occasions like the traditional marriage (Male, 60 years, Uruan, Trader)

Data gathered through interview revealed that there exist shift in culture of the Ibibio people and this is very visible in the dressing patterns of the people during some traditional marriage ceremony across the Ibibio land. The majority of the study participants agreed that most of the Ibibio sons and daughters have decided to showcase traditional attires of other culture instead of promoting their cultural attires. Some factors were found to be responsible for the shift in the traditional dressing during some traditional marriages among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State.

Changes in the Traditional Order of Traditional Marriage Ceremony

Findings through data collection show that there are lots of changes in the traditional marriage ceremony patterns among the Ibibio people in these modern days as compare to what was obtainable in the past. Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people according to data gathered by the researcher had specified patterns which have over the years been shifted as result or impact of modernization. Findings of the study revealed that there are lots of changes in the patterns of Ibibio's traditional marriage ceremony. One of the study participants from Ikono Local Government Area in her responses reported that;

You see today we are all victims of modernity which has brought about changes within the life patterns of the Ibibio people and as a reflection of such, is the changes in the patterns of traditional marriage ceremony. In our own days, traditional marriage use to take place in the late evening through the night. Let say around 6 to 7 pm, the groom family will arrived for *udia ibeye* which was cooked in the evening after the bride's mother might have come back from the market with her siblings and relatives to prepare the meals for the groom's family which the size were manageable as compare today which we call crowd to witness traditional marriage ceremony instead of family members who will take the young girl home and nurture her as their wife. But what we have today is much more cooking and outrageous expenditure because we want crowd to come, in fact today people feel more satisfy based on the large crowd that turn up in their traditional marriage ceremony. This is a change that has happen among us the Ibibio people (Female, 61 years, Ikono, Trader)

Another study participant from Uruan Local Government Area in his responses reported that;

Traditional marriage ceremony used to be between the two families and strangers we were not concern with strangers as we are today. Family members especially the elderly used to go and get their daughter in-law for their son. Mind you, the groom's father was not part of the ceremony. All that the groom's father does was to send item to the proposed daughter in-law's family. The groom's father used to send an elder of the major family (Ekpuk) to represent him. The elder will go with some other elders and selected elderly women who are members of the groom's family for the ceremony which was mostly indoor activity. On return, the bride's family will send cook food and raw food items like yam, fish or goat for the groom's father and other members of the groom's member who were not part of the ceremony.

He further narrated that:

The elder who represented the groom's father in the company of the other elders and women will take the new bride the groom's father with the groom and handed over the couple to the groom's father as a sign of successful mission delivery. On the reception of the bride, the groom's father will call his wife who is the groom's mother if alive; call his other

daughter in-laws if any and call other wives of his brothers and neighbour and they will share the food the elders brought from the ceremony which was given by the bride's family. The groom's father will introduce each woman to the new bride as a wife of the family after she was first introduced. The man will also ask the old wives to assist the new bride were necessary, he will tell the old wives that if they see her come to cut leaves at their backyard they should allow her and if she needs salt, and they should give it to her as one of them and said same to her. This was how marriage was done in those days. But today, there are so many things I see today which I believe that it is the new world that has influence our people and most importantly, our people do not know our culture and traditions anymore and nobody cares to learn from the elders, they are doing what they see others do and they copy them (Male, 71 years, Idu, Uruan).

Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio peoples experienced culture shift. Gathered data from participants revealed great dimensions of changes in the cultural practice of traditional marriage. It was gathered that what was obtainable before as part of the Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony are missing today and new cultural elements have been introduced into the practice.

Strange delicacies and drinks and Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony

Findings from gathered data show that there have been changes in quantity and types of foods presented during Ibibio traditional marriage ceremonies today as compare to what was obtainable in the traditional Ibibio society. In the case of quantity, finding show that in the traditional Ibibio society, foods were prepared for few members of the groom's family and for the father of the groom who will not accompany the team to the ceremony but wait at home for his daughter in-law. One of the study participants from Etinan Local Government Area in his responses reported that said that:

My brother what we see today is not what used to be before. In our days and in the days of my father, foods were very few kinds. What we have as “Udia Ibeje” today was made for few people because traditional marriage ceremony used to be for very few elders of the groom's family. We used to have soups like *afang*, *editan*, *atamam* and most especially *ubó* which were made of vegetable leaves and cocoyam's leaves. We also used to have *itimehe akpapa* and roast corns picked from the bride mother's *ubium*. But today, we have some people cook different kinds of foods which are not part of our culture. Mind you that rice was not an important food as we make it be today. Some people even engage caterers to cook and these caterers have brought various strange foods into our culture and we are gradually losing our traditional foods. It is a pity that some of our children do not know these foods and how to cook them and in the nearest future I will not be surprise if indomie noodles in part of the Udia ibeje of my people. But before, I know I will die and rest with my fathers (Male, 72 years,

Etinan, family head).

During Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony, emergence of findings shows that the foods were few and the cost was affordable base on the quantity which was relative to the expected visitors. One of the study participants from Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area in her narrative reported that:

When I was given to my husband, my mother was not under any pressure and my father was happy because he was going to host visitors he can afford. He called my mother, gave her some money and my mother added her own and we went to the market on the market day to buy food items for my husband's family. It was not something that my parent had to go looking for where to borrow money for food or what is called entertainment today. Most of the leaves and vegetables were gotten from my parent's farm because we were not expecting to cook for 50 people. But today, our people have to cook other tribe's foods during our traditional marriage because in some cases the groom may not come from here unlike before that we used to marry among ourselves. Because the bride's family and the expected couples are faced with large number of visitors and sometime groom coming from another tribe, they have to cook strange foods to satisfy the groom and his family. Because of the large expected turn up of visitors, the families involve are now battling on the cost of cooking these food and drinks, and what type of food should be cooked. Our traditional marriage ceremony is no long what it used to be (Female, 65 years, Ibesikpo, trader).

Further findings from collected data revealed that due to the introduction of new or what the study participants referred to as strange foods, the bride's family have now shifted the burden of entertaining their visitors which was the culture of the Ibibio to entertain their visitors, to the visitors paying for or sponsoring their entertainment at the proposed bride's house. Findings also revealed that the issue of entertainment money was not there before now. But today groom's families are asked to pay for entertainment because of the expected visitors and family members. One of the study participants from Uruan Local Government Area in his narratives reported that”

It is our tradition as Ibibio to entertain or visitors, but this has changed due to changes in the traditional marriage practice of the Ibibio people today. The introduction of strange foods and drinks into our traditional marriage ceremony has brought about so many changes. I believed that it is the high cost of entertaining the high numbers of visitors that has brought about the shift of entertaining your visitors to the visitors entertaining themselves. Many kinds of foods are seen today at traditional marriage ceremonies especially were the people engaged the services of caterers. These caterers are destroying our culture with their strange foods which they claim are better to our health that what we have as our traditional foods. Imagine, how someone can say that

fried rice is richer than “Itemehe Akpakpa”. Well it is the new world that is influencing everything in Africa, (Male, 69 years, Uruan, Businessman).

Traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people has been experiencing changes in the terms of ceremonial foods. Gathered data show that the majority of the study participants' referred to the new set of foods as strange foods. This implies that a lot of foods served today at Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony are strange to the traditional foods known and cultivated by the Ibibio people.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study through gathered data show that the order of events during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio has changed due to influence of modernization which is made possible through the dynamic nature of culture. One of the visible changes as discovered through gathered data is the changes in the traditional attires of the Ibibio people during their traditional marriage ceremony. It is discovered that a lot of Ibibio sons today are not wearing their traditional wrapper and chieftaincy gown during traditional marriage ceremony. Data show that the wear other ethnic group's traditional attires for Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony. This is as a result of influence of components of modernization like the internet and mobility. The finding give credence to Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

Other emergence of findings is the changes in the traditional order of activities during Ibibio traditional marriage ceremony. Data show that the traditional marriage ceremony that used to take place in the late evening is now billed to start in the afternoon. Also, the bride's family that used to wait to sit and host their visitors and now brought out with songs and dance. This and other changes have made the patterns culture shifts which are experienced among the Ibibio people during their traditional marriage ceremony. This is also in agreement with the postulation of Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

Further emergence is the fact that in the Ibibio traditional marriage, the entertainment that was mainly the bride's family is now shifted to the groom and his family. It was discovered that what is called “*Udia Ibeje*” or entertainment is now the groom's responsibility depending on the number of expected visitors from the groom's side and the bride' side. This shift has affected cost and kinds of foods found among the traditional marriage ceremonies of the Ibibio people. This changes has given credence to Inglehart and Welzei (2005) who posit that modernization brings an intense awareness of change and innovation.

CONCLUSION

Traditional marriage among the Ibibio people of Southern Nigeria is a very important event which authenticates marriage as a traditional institution as obtainable in other parts of Africa. There have been observable changes in the traditional marriage ceremonies of the Ibibio people. Some of these changes are in adoption of other ethnic group's traditional attires by Ibibio sons during their traditional marriage ceremonies, changes in the patterns of activities during the traditional marriage, and introduction of strange foods which have brought about the

shift in bearing the entertainment (*udia ibeye*) cost from the bride's family to the groom.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Ibibio people should promote Ibibio traditional attires in order to encourage the upcoming generations of using examine traditional attires especially during traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, South – South Nigeria
2. The elders of the Ibibio ethnic group should project appropriate order of traditional rites for the traditional marriage ceremony of the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, South – South Nigeria
3. Delicacies of the Ibibio people should be uphold by the people in order to avoid extinction in the nearest future.
4. The Ibibio people should endeavor to promote their cultural values in order to preserve the existence of the fourth largest ethnic group in Nigeria.

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WOMEN IN EDUCATION AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN ORON FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Education plays great role in empowering women to contribute to development, but the barriers of culture of exclusion driven by ideologies of patriarchy has brought about the slow pace in attaining development in many communities across Africa. This descriptive research sought to examine the roles of education in empowering women to contribute to the development of Oron Federal Constituency of Akwa Ibom State. Women in Development Theory (WID) was adopted as theoretical guide. A total of 393 study participant were engaged as sample size from the 5 local government areas of the constituency. Both primary and secondary data were analysed by the researcher. Primary data were gathered through the use of questionnaire and were analysed descriptively using of frequency tables. Findings of the study shown that more female pupils are enrolled in the 107 primary school which implies high level of female education, women engage in various programmes like educational intervention, health care intervention, community development levy toward the development of the constituency, and factors like cultural belief, poverty, family roles and early marriage constitute barriers to women participation in development. Based on these findings, the researchers among others recommended that cultural practice of women exclusion should be abolished among the people of Oron Federal Constituency and Akwa Ibom State as a whole.

KEYWORDS: Education, development, women, culture and Oron

INTRODUCTION

Education is fundamental to the development of the human capacity (Bassey, 2016). Within the National Policy on Education, there is provision for equal opportunities (equalitarianism) for males and females in schools and even in adult education (of men and women) that is not within the formal school system. Thus the National Policy on Education recognizes equality of men and women when it comes to education (Benjamin, 2008). This policy has created the right for the girl child building on the United Nations General Assembly in its 57th meeting in December 2002, which proclaimed 2005-2014 as United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (Benjamin, 2008). According to Sharma (2016), education for Sustainable Development emphasizes education of all to be an indispensable element for achieving sustainable development. This act recognized the capacity of educated women in contributing to community development worldwide.

Samuel (2016) argued that community development is one of the alternative vehicles for the positive transformation of societies. This in its implication ascertains the fact every city, town and urban centre is driven through the base of community development by people participation in the developmental programmes of such place. The United Nations in 1956 defined community development as a “process by which the efforts of the people are united with those of governmental authorities to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of communities, to integrate these communities into the life of the nation and enable them to contribute fully to the national progress” (UN, 2019). Mere (1982) in his work “*Economic for a Developing World*” also accentuated that community development is an instrument of social advancement of all communities (Samuel, 2016). Community developments especially among the developing nations have taken centre stage of concern for every organization within and outside the developing nations. The quest for sustainable development goals is to attain great success in community development by meeting the various classes of human needs especially in the third world. Every definition of community development will advocates the advancement of human lives and socio-economic statuses within any given community, but one of the key factor that have been proven to contribute to the achieving development from community perspective remains education. With the population of girls being born into our society everyday, and the mark set by the educated women in their various contributions toward the development of their respective community, girl child education seem to be calling for more and more policy, investment, and provisions for its growth especially in Africa.

Women's education is very important for the development of our communities, states, nations, and key to the achievement of global sustainable development. Due to the rising population of women in our society, educating our women is giving empowerment to a good percentage of our population to contribute their quota to the development of our families, communities, state, and nation at large. According to Alan (2010), sustainable development of any country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men, education brings about empowerment and in other words; education empowers women to engage in sustainable development activities. Benjamin (2008) posits that, today most of the educated men desire to marry educated women, so that their children will have educated mothers, and this marks a great change in male attitude to the education of women and a steadily increasing demand for girls' education. The results of these educated women are gradually influencing the Nigerian society and are changing the views of women and other as such influence is steadily changing

the old-fashioned attitudes (Benjamin, 2008). According to Somani (2017), girls' education is pivotal to the development of society. This is given credence by the saying of Greg Mortenson; "If you teach a boy, you educate an individual; but if you teach a girl, you educate a community."

According to Sharma (2016), women play important and varied roles from home to society to workplace as a homemaker, societal wellbeing and job provider and job seeker respectively. Fortunate African women who enjoyed good education have proven their abilities in several walks of life (Benjamin, 2008). They are found among successfully doctors, teachers, lawyers, and are found in industry, commerce and public administration. These set of women have proved the case for women's education by demonstrating their usefulness outside the home (Benjamin, 2008). Sharma (2016) posits that women are visible backbone of any civilized society in the role of friend, daughter, daughter-in-law, sister, wife, mother or a role of working woman; women have facilitated this male dominant society in every aspect, and constitute approximately 50% of the World's population.

According to Osirike, and Egbayabo, (2012), community development is a derivation of two main concepts: community organization and economic development. Osirike, and Egbayabo, (2012) also argued that although defined in varying ways, community development implies mutually related development activities and situations. It is geared towards solving the problems of the community in order to raise their standard of living as well as promoting social welfare and development. The process of community development involves various activities ranging from tackling of specific tasks on aspects of community welfare to multipurpose programmes aimed at the transformation of the social organization and values of the whole community

Currently, women have risen to a higher profile in community development projects and likewise in decision making processes in the area. Their involvement was due to the fact that, some of the cultural values, beliefs and practices that determined the position of women in the past, have undergone drastic restructuring while others have been completely rendered obsolete. At the same time, new roles and values have also emerged (Osirike, and Egbayabo, 2012). From this lay down perspectives, this research work seeks to concentrate on the roles of education in empowering women in Oron Federal Constituency, Akwa Ibom State to contribute to their community development at different levels, through various developmental programmes.

Culture of exclusion of women in decision making, in a patriarchal society is posing great barrier to the pace at which sustainable development through execution of community development programmes should be achieved. British Council (2012) argued that many diverse socio-cultural factors influence the value that parents attach to their daughters' education. Gender norms and stereotypes exclude women and girls from decision-making, community participation and control over their own lives in many areas. Women as wives, mothers and caregivers understand the weight of various challenges facing the human world. This is because, they have been at the receiving ends of these social, economic, political, leadership, and war crisis. As a response to these issues, educated women have the capacity to contribute to development programmes which can alleviate the root causes of some of these problems.

Most of the educated women today are considered, rated and treated as weaker vessels

because of the cultural doctrine associated with women treatment. This has forced some educated men, who have received same level of education with this class of women to put up restriction in opportunities for educated women to participate in community leadership, thereby preventing educated women participation in community development decision making. Though, more educated women are rising up today to take up challenges that are facing their families, communities and nation at large. The exclusion of educated women in community decision making due to cultural norm and traditions is hampering the pace at which women participation in community development programmes would have attained success in our various community, state, and by extension the nation Sharma (2016).

As women education is rising in influence in our society every day, the number of girl child in educational institutions is increasing, and our society is having more educated women who are mentally empowered to contribute their own quota at homes and communities. The rising number of educated women in our society has reduced many of our social problems like in increasing the number of women going for antenatal, increasing the number of nursing mothers going for immunization of their children, increasing the number of working women in different fields of professions. These educated women have contributed to reduction of poverty at family levels and in empowering others within their reach. According to Peters, Basse and Usoro (2019), educating girls is a particularly effective way of eradicating poverty and the positive effects of education for girls are well documented on the health and welfare of families as well as on economic opportunities and social transformation on a larger scale. Social responsibility burden at individual and family levels of most men have been greatly reduced by the roles of educated women who are their wives, relatives or partners. The rising numbers of educated women have been more of advantage for many families today to the extent that it is reducing the cultural norm of and problems associated with having only female children in a patriarchal society.

In Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State, women education is on the same level of policy implementation, resource investment, free and compulsory at the primary and secondary levels. Educated women in Oron Federal Constituency are increasing in number. They have set many stride in their quest to contribute to alleviation of social, economic, political, leadership, family, and community problems. The Present deputy governor of Akwa Ibom State Senator Akon Ekaenyi is an icon of the subject. Their set marks in the community development speak for the importance of girl child education, but the challenge of overcoming the cultural norms associated with women restrictions in accordance to various traditional practices found within the cultural and ideological diversity of the people of Oron Federal Constituency still call for concern, as in lifting the culture bars for effective women participation in community development. Literatures like Benjamin (2008) and Sharma (2016) present the fortunes, privileges, occupations, contributions to works and families of educated women, but the roles of the educated women in community development is the identified gap which this research work sought to fill. On this backdrop, this research work seeks to fill this gap in the literature, by examining the roles of education in enhancing women participation in community development in Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Women In Development Theory “WID”

“Women in Development” (WID) theory has its root in Ester Boserup work of 1970. According to Colombo in Commission of the European Communities of 1984, since the Danish economist Ester Boserup published *Women's Role in Economic Development* in 1970, it gradually has become clear that not only is there a women's issue in most Third World countries - since their structure is often founded on a concept of the inferiority of women and a denial of their right to active participation in social life - but there is also a women's issue characteristic of these countries. In other words, under-development has specific and particularly grave implications for the status of women, implications that are being accentuated rather than mitigated by the process of modernization and development.

The term "women in development" came into use in the early 1970s, after the publication of Ester Boserup's *Women's Role in Economic Development* (1970). Boserup was the first to systematically delineate on a global level the sexual division of labour that existed in agrarian economies. She analysed the changes that occurred in traditional agricultural practices as societies became modernized and examined the differential impact of those changes on the work done by men and women. She concluded that in sparsely populated regions where shifting agriculture is practiced, women tend to do the majority of agricultural work (Buvinic, 1986).

METHODOLOGY

Survey research method was adopted for this study because the research study covers a large population and a complex study area. Simple random sampling method was used for the purposes of selecting study participants. The study area is Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom state. Oron Federal Constituency consists of 5 local government areas which include; Oron, Mbo, Okobo, Udung Uko, and Urue Offong/Oruko local government areas. Oron Federal Constituency is part of Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. The targeted population of this study was the female population in Oron Federal Constituency, which is also, refer to as Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District with Oron 130,259, Mbo 152,610, Udung Uko 105, 660, Okobo 153, 476, and Urue Offong/Oruko 79,253. The projected female population of Oron Federal Constituency, according to the Akwa Ibom State Demographic Dividend Profile (2018), as derived from the 2006 national population census (NPC, 2006) was 621,481. The projected female population of the constituency was 621,481 as at 2018.

In determining the sample size, the researcher used Alien Taro Yamane method. Yamane (1967) provides a simplified formula to calculate sample size. Therefore, the sample size of this study was 400, and was randomly selected from each of the local government area within Oron Federal Constituency. The headquarters of each of the local government areas were chosen by the researcher for the purpose of randomly selecting the study participants. A total of 393 (*n*) were finally adopted as sample size based on the retrieved questionnaire. Questionnaire was adopted as tool for data collection because it provided closed-ended options that were easy to choose by the participants. The data collected in this study were analysed descriptively using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT

Level of Female Education in Oron Federal Constituency

Table 1: Distribution of primary school pupils for ECCDE class, by local government area and sex between 2009/2010 and 2014/2015 school sessions

Local Government Area	No. of Schools	ECCDE		
		M	F	MF
Mbo	29	3255	3910	7165
Okobo	33	3409	4000	7409
Oron	13	1376	1476	2852
UdungUko	11	917	1026	1943
UrueOffong/ Oruko	21	1065	1313	2378
Total	107	10,022	11,725	21,747

Source: Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development (2015).

Table 1 shows that in Oron Federal Constituency, Okobo Local Government Area has the highest number (7409) of pupils enrolled in Early Child Care Development Education (ECCDE) across the 33 primary schools, with females making the highest proportion of 4000 (54.1%) while the males are 3409 (45.9%). This is followed by Mbo Local Government Area with 3910 (54.6%) females and 3255 (45.4%) males, making a total of 7165 pupils across the 29 primary schools. Oron Local Government Area is next with 1476 (51.8%) females, while males are 1376 (48.2%), making a total of 2852 across 13 primary schools. This is followed by UrueOffong/ Oruko Local Government Area with a total of 2378 pupils, the females making the highest proportion with 1313 (55.2%), while the males are 1065 (44.8%) across 21 primary schools. UdungUko is the local government area with the least number of pupils and primary schools, with 1943 pupils at ECCDE class across 11 primary schools. This comprises 1026 (52.8%) of females, and 917 (47.2%) of males.

The analysis of Table 1 shows that Oron Federal Constituency as at 2014/2015 school session had a total of 21,747 pupils under Early Childhood Care and Development Education (ECCDE) across 107 primary schools. 11,725 (53.9%) were females, while males were 10,022 (46.1%). This implies that in ECCDE class at primary school level of education, females have the highest percentage of enrolment (11,725/53.9%) within 2014/2015 school year against (10,022/46.1%) males.

Roles of Educated Women in Community Development in Oron Federal Constituency**Table 2: Percentage Distribution of responses on Women Participation in Community Development in Oron Federal Constituency**

Women Participation in Community Development Programmes	Yes	%	No	%
Educational Intervention	342	85.5	58	14.5
Health Care intervention	357	89.3	43	10.7
Community Development Levy	368	92	32	32
Food Production/availability	353	88.3	47	11.7
Women Empowerment Intervention	374	93.5	26	6.5
Political Activities	279	69.8	121	30.2
Community Development Decision Making	213	53.3	187	46.7
Social Welfare intervention	308	77	92	23
Total	2594		606	

Source: Filed work (2023)

Table 2 shows that 342 (85.5%) agreed with “yes” against 58 (14.5%) with “No”, that women participate in community development through education intervention programmes in Oron Federal Constituency. 357 (89.3%) agreed against 43 (10.7%) that women participate in community development through health care intervention programmes/projects. 368 (92%) agreed that women participate in community development through contribution of community development levy, against 32 (8%). 353 (88.3%) said “Yes” that women participate in community development through production/availability of food against 47 (11.7%) who said “No”. 374 (93.5%) who said “Yes” that women participate in community development through women empowerment intervention programmes/projects, against 26 (6.5%) who disagreed. 279 (69.8%) agreed that women contribute to community development through political activities engagement against 121 (30.2%) who disagreed. 213 (53.3%) agreed that women contribute to community development through decision making at community level, against 187 (46.7%) who disagreed. 308 (77%) agreed that women participate in community development through social welfare intervention programmes/projects, against 92 (23%). This implies that the “Yes” are higher in proportion of responses than the “No” counterpart in all questions in this section.

Factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency**Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Factors affecting women education in Oron Federal Constituency**

Factors that affect women education	Yes	%	No	%
Cultural belief	302	75.5	98	24.5
Poverty	353	88.3	47	11.7
Family roles	377	94.2	23	5.8
Early marriage	201	50.3	199	49.7
Gender role	278	69.5	122	30.5
Lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education	317	79.3	83	20.7

Source: Field work (2023)

Table 3 shows responses on factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency. Under cultural belief, those who say “Yes” have the highest proportion of responses with 302 (75.5%), while those who say “No” are 98 (24.5%). Under poverty, those who say “Yes” make the highest portion of respondents with 353 (88.3%), while those who say “No” are 47 (11.7%). Under family roles, those who say “Yes” are 377 (94.2%) which make the highest proportion of responses, while those who say “No” are 23 (5.8%). Under early marriage, those who say “Yes” make the highest portion of respondents with 201 (50.3%), while those who say “No” are 199 (49.7%). Under gender role as one of the factors that affect women education in Oron Federal Constituency, 278 (69.5%) of the respondents agree that gender role affects women quest for education, while 122 (30.5%) disagree. Under lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education, 317 (79.3%) of the respondents say “Yes”, while those who say “No” are 83 (20.7%).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is the fact that female education plays great roles in women participation in community development in Oron Federal Constituency. This was found to be supported by the discovery that education positioned women with required qualification and knowledge to contribute to the development of their respective communities within the local government areas in Oron Federal Constituency in Akwa Ibom State. This finding supports the position of Somani (2017). According to Somani (2017), girls' education is pivotal to the development of society.

Findings further shows that throughout the 289 primary schools in Oron Federal Constituency, females are more enrolled than males. According to discovery through gathered information, Oron Federal Constituency people shows great belief in women education as girls

are found more in schools than boys. Emerging from the findings of the study is that educated women in Oron Federal Constituency play great roles in community development programmes/projects across the local government areas. It was gathered that educated women in Oron Federal Constituency engages in various community development programmes like; education intervention programmes, health care intervention, community levy, food production/availability, women empowerment intervention, political activities, decision making, and social welfare intervention programmes to bring about development in their different communities. This finding agrees with Alan (2010) who argues that; sustainable development of any country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men, education brings about empowerment, and in other words; education empowers women to engage in sustainable development activities.

Emergence from the findings of the study is the fact that there are factors that affect women education. According to gathered data, factors like cultural belief, poverty, family roles, early marriage, gender role and lack of sponsorship programmes for girl child education affect women quest for educational attainment in Oron Federal Constituency. British Council (2012) argued that many diverse socio-cultural factors influence the value that parents attach to their daughters' education. Gender norms and stereotypes exclude women and girls from decision-making, community participation and control over their own lives in many areas.

CONCLUSION

Education plays great role in empowering women to contribute to development, but the barriers of culture of exclusion driven by ideologies of patriarchy has brought about the slow pace in attaining development in many communities across the 5 local government areas in Oron Federal Constituency. Women education is on the rise in Oron Federal Constituency as more girl children are enrolled in 107 primary schools than the boys. Educated women in Oron Federal Constituency engaged various developmental programmes like health care intervention, educational intervention, social welfare empowerment and community development levy contribution, food production, and women empowerment. Various factors form barriers which the women in Oron Federal Constituency faced in their quest to contributing to the development of the constituency.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and analysis of data, the researcher proposed the following recommendations:

1. Cultural practice of women exclusion should be abolished from among the people of Oron Federal Constituency and Akwa Ibom State as a whole.
2. Government should see how to develop sponsorship programmes for girl child education.
3. Women should be given opportunities to take up leadership positions especially in rural communities in order to have opportunities to contribute their wisdom toward community development.
4. Women should be allowed to be part of decision making bodies on issues that affect them.

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CULTURE OF ALCOHOL AND PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE ABUSE: A QUALITATIVE INTEROGATION OF DISTORTED VALUES AMONG IBIBIO YOUTHS

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ABSTRACT

Culture projects morals which must be acquired by man as member of the society. But some traditional practices have offered youths the opportunity to seize the moral boundaries and forced expansion toward loss of traditional values. This research examined the roles of youths in distorting communal values through engagement in drug abuse on the basis of traditional rites as cultural heritage of Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Etinan Local Government Area was divided by cluster into Iman North and Iman South based on the existing geo-political divides. Six villages were purposively selected, 3 from each cluster within Iman North and Iman South based on their homogeneous characteristics. The Fetterman's Big-net approach was used to select study participants from each of the selected villages. Cultural influence on youths' drugs/psychoactive substance abuse behaviour model was adopted by the researchers to provide a conceptual framework for the study. The researchers adopted ethnographic research design for the study which involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts. Findings showed that some customs and traditional practices like traditional marriage list and burial rites that were meant to guide social behaviours tend to generate unintended consequences among youths. Inspired by the findings, the study makes case for a culture-mediated regulation of illicit drinks among traditional items that are culturally approved for youths during rites observances.

KEYWORDS: Culture, youths, value orientation, psychoactive drugs abuse, and traditional rites

INTRODUCTION

Culture has been explained in many perspectives in relation to human behaviour and capabilities to adapt to inhabited environment (Peters, 2019). Culture is a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits which a man acquired as a member of a given society (Modo, 2016). According to Modo (2016), culture is the integrated system of learned behaviour, patterns characteristic of the members of a society. Culture explains that human behaviour is learned by members of the society as part of adaptation's responsibility (Peters, 2019). Culture determines to a large extent what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks in many societies, and the use of any substance in many societies is socially accepted or rejected depending on the socio-cultural values and norms of the people (Nwagu, *et al.*, 2017). The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009). Culture has great influence over humans' behaviour as they grow within a specific society.

Each society as means of cultural adaptation engages in traditional practices and rites of passage which are learned by members of the society as values orientations and are preserved in some forms of traditional codes, and later transfer from one generation to another as forms of socialization by young and upcoming members of such society. Adolescent and youth form the age group whereby humans tend to acquire acceptable behaviours within the norms of the society as part of their transition from childhood to adulthood in order to adapt to a given environment (Peters, 2019). Human beings alone have the capacity to create and sustain culture and every society has its own culture no matter how simple that culture appears because culture is learned, culture is shared, culture is adaptive, culture is integrative, culture is dynamic, culture is gratifying and culture is selective and limiting (Modo, 2016). Traditional rites are embedded in cultural values which have capacity to shape people's attitudes toward substance use and influence their risk of experimentation with drugs (Unger, *et al.*, 2004). The kind and level of use of drug and its abuse is related to cultural values of a society.

Issues relating to drug users and abusers as forms of human behaviour have been a booming area of study for scientists and other researchers since and even before the turn of the 21st century (Usoro, *et al.*, 2020). According to Abbott and Chase (2008), sociocultural beliefs as forms of value orientations can shape the approach to and behaviour regarding psychoactive substance use and abuse. Culture has influence over people's attitudes toward substance use and their experimentation with drugs through traditional rites and practices (Soto, *et al.*, 2011). According to Heath (2001), culture plays a central role in forming the expectations of individuals about potential problems they may face with drug use as substance use and abuse is found to be rooted in culture of the people. Many studies have shown that traditional cultural values influence adolescents' attitudes and beliefs, which in turn influence their health risk behaviours like in combining cigarette, alcohol, and other drug use (Soto *et al.*, 2011). Nwagu *et al.*, (2017) and Jiloha (2009) posit that almost all cultures have used psycho-active drugs to facilitate social interaction, to alter consciousness, and to heal their people, which have form their modes of traditional rites and practices. Jiloha (2009) further argued that the social and cultural factors influencing the initiation of tobacco use vary from country to country, from developed world to developing nations, region to region and culture to culture

Psychoactive substances for several purposes have been produced within our society,

consumed within our society, sold within our society, and shared among the people. Room (2013) posits that in early nineteenth-century America, the most common way of understanding the concept of substance and alcohol addiction is to be historically and culturally specific. McGovern (2009) argued that in India, the consumption of alcoholic beverages started prior to their colonization as forms of traditional practices which are embedded in the culture of the people. Psychoactive drug abuse behaviour like human behaviour in general is conceived of as an outcome of genetic and biochemical characteristics, past learning experiences, motivational states, psychosocial antecedents, and cultural context in which it unfolds and these conditions assume a considerable variety in drug-abuse behaviour. Among these, social and cultural factors play an important role in initiation, maintenance and therapeutic intervention of psychoactive drug-abuse (Jiloha, 2009). Several studies have shown that culture plays key role in psychoactive substance drug acceptance, psychoactive drug use and the level of abuse (Guerreroa and Andrews, 2011; Room, 2013; and Jiloha, 2009).

Cultural aspects of substance abuse cannot be adequately addressed without considering the cultural experiences of substance abusers of which the majority are the youths (Peters, 2019). Parents are considered to be adults who have undergone cultural socialization, and this positioned parents at an influential point over their children in relation to substance and alcohol use and abuse. According to Jiloha (2009), parents have a tremendous influence on their children and the children of smoker parents are twice likely to become smokers. Parental disapproval of smoking makes an adolescent less likely to initiate smoking. Female adolescents are more likely to be smokers if both parents are smokers and there is a strong correlation between mother smoking and the female youth becoming a smoker (Peters, 2020). Raised in a home where parents smoke exposes the young person to tobacco smoking. Parents who smoke may also give easy access to cigarettes and less likely to oppose their children's smoking. According to Elkind (1985) cited in Peters (2019), children are more likely to smoke whose elder siblings are smokers. Cannabis, a traditional drug in Indian society is ritualized in social and religious gatherings. Elkind further stated that it is a socially sanctioned behaviour in certain cultural groups to use Bhang and Charas by adolescents and has parental approval for that. Parental attitude towards alcohol plays an important role in initiating the adolescent to drink alcohol (Jiloha, 2013). Many studies show that parents as agents of socialization have great role in influencing their children behaviours toward substance and alcohol use and abuse (Peters, 2020). Social influences together with local cultural norms are central factors that can influence the use of alcohol (Nwagu, 2017).

Substance and alcohol use and abuse is rooted in the culture of the people of Nigeria (Peters, 2020). According to Mamman *et al.* (2014), while alcohol and other substances are celebrated in the south, the Northern part of the nation forbids alcohol, but accept cigarettes, kolanut, bitter kola and others. Many ethnic groups in Nigeria culturally accept the use of some substances and alcohol for various purposes. Oluwabamide (2003) posits that different cultural groupings in Nigeria have different ways of practicing traditional health care services. These traditional healings include the use of herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots (Oluwabamide, 2003). Much of these psychoactive substances are mixed with alcohol which serve as extractive chemical with capacity to extract from the herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots the content which will then serve as drug for treatment. In the course of taking these

treatments, many people have developed or cultivated substance and alcohol use and abuse behaviour. Traditional health care providers and their practices are culturally accepted by the Nigerian society. In some parts of the cultural area where alcohol is not religiously accepted, some people take alcohol as medicine for treatment of some illness through patronage of traditional health care givers.

Dumbili (2013) argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. During such occasions, palm wine and hot drinks are specifically used in pouring libations, offering prayers and heralding such events. Among the most commonly consumed alcoholic beverages are; palm wine—fermented from the sap of oil palm tree, beer, *burukutu*—fermented from guinea-corn and native gin—distilled from palm wine (Oshodin, 1995). Nigerian in 2010 had a total alcohol per capita (15+) consumption of 23.1 litres of pure alcohol among male and female drinkers. This did not include the large quantity of homemade alcohol consumed which usually goes unrecorded (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to a study conducted in Enugu Ezike by Nwagu *et al.* (2017), palm wine is a major source of income for the community, and young men and older men are involved in tapping wine. Many young people at one time or the other depended on the income from palm wine for their daily needs, including education. Many developing countries are highly dependent on national revenues from alcohol. Individuals in many rural communities in such countries also depend on income from homemade alcoholic beverage such as palm wine. It is, however, worthy to note that when production of such homemade alcoholic beverages increases in a bid to increase income by producers, the consumption also increases (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Palm wine produced in many rural communities is a perishable commodity which needs to be consumed or it spoils. Members of Enugu Ezike produce and consume palm wine in large quantities. Some researchers have noted that in many developing countries, alcohol is often more readily available than clean drinking water. This seems to be the case in Enugu Ezike where this study was conducted (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to Abdu-Raheem (2013), it has also been noted in Nigeria that parents, peer groups, and society at large contribute to the alarming rate of psychoactive drug abuse among the secondary school students. Alan (2003) argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological (to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. He further stressed that despite the fact that drug abuse has adverse effects on the youth involved by changing their brain perception of difficulties and problems, the number of undergraduates that use or abuse stimulants has steadily increased in recent years. Peters and Basse (2020) posit that psychoactive drug use and abuse affect behaviours of the youths with frequent fight among the youths, neglect and disrespect of the elders, rape, forceful taking of other people's property and communal crises are resultant effects of psychoactive drug use and abuse by the youths. Peters and Basse (2020) further stated that psychoactive drug consumption has played a key role in the cultural shift among the youths of the riverine areas in Akwa Ibom State.

The world drug problem remains a common and shared responsibility that requires

effective and increased international cooperation and demands an integrated, multidisciplinary, mutually reinforcing and balanced approach to drug supply (Usoro, *et al.*, 2018). Youths have been at the centre of drug abuse and the most affected group in term of negative impacts and consequences. The most venerable and deeply involved group in the social menace of drugs abuse is the youth, and drugs abuse among the youths has dominated discussion in the mainstream of the media in recent time (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Psychoactive drug abuse has been on the rise among youths in Nigeria despite the known risk factors and efforts by diverse social, governmental and non-governmental institutions to reduce the pace at which this problem grows within the Nigerian society. The menace of psychoactive drugs abuse in Nigeria has reached a frightening proportion and it pervaded every fibre in the society (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Psychoactive drug abuse and its consequences are recognized today as a rapid growing global social problem (Lakhanpal and Agnihotri, 2007; United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2007).

Youths characterized the largest portion of the Nigerian population both at urban centres and rural areas (NPC, 2006). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) (1997) stated that the use and misuse of drugs by adolescents has become one of the most disturbing health related events in Nigeria especially, among students. Majority of the traditional and cultural activities are carried out or performed by the youths under the supervision, command and authority of the elders as means of certifying cultural values. This opportunity created by culture and traditional rites are often seized by some of these youths to abuse the use of illicit substances hence, hence the many cases of psychoactive drug abuse. Peters, Bassey, Usoro and Samuel (2022) posit that among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, traditions and cultural activities within the society have offered youths the opportunities to brew, demand, sell, use, and abuse illicit substances. The high rate of psychoactive drug abuse under the disguise of carrying out traditional rites and cultural activities is disturbing. Literature like Chia *et al.* (2016), has presented the used of psychoactive drugs for different reasons including traditional rites and observations, religious ceremonies, treatment of ailments or palliatives, but the impacts of abuse of these psychoactive substances by the youths as part of traditional rites and observations, and religious ceremonies which often result in majority of the youths using their influence to force shift of moral boundaries by strife and in some cases enforce their decisions against the elders' decisions during rites and ceremonies, which are mostly contrary to the moral codes of the society has not been given attention by previous authors which is the gap in literature and the main focus of this study. Against this backdrop, this study sought to examine how youths through traditional rites and cultural practices that promote psychoactive drug use, have enforce shift of moral boundaries and distort cultural value orientations among the rural people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Culture and drug abuse

Culture as a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits which a man acquired as a member of a given society (Tylor, 1871; Modo, 2016) is an embodiment of human life through socialization processes. Culture therefore has great influence over humans' behaviour as they grow within a

specific society. According to Modo (2016), human beings alone have the capacity to create and sustain culture and every society has its own culture no matter how simple that culture appears. Drug use and abuse is culturally experienced. This is because culture is learned, culture is shared, culture is adaptive, culture is integrative, culture is dynamic, culture is gratifying and culture is selective and limiting (Modo, 2016).

Cultural values can shape people's attitudes toward substance use and influence their risk of experimentation with drugs (Unger *et al.*, 2004). The kind and level of use of drug and its abuse is related to cultural values of a society. According to Abbott and Chase (2008), sociocultural beliefs can shape the approach to and behaviour regarding substance use and abuse. Culture has influence over people's attitudes toward substance use and their experimentation with drugs (Soto *et al.*, 2011). According to Soto *et al.* (2011), many studies show that traditional cultural values influence adolescents' attitudes and beliefs, which in turn influence their health risk behaviours (e.g., cigarette, alcohol, and drug use) (Beck and Bargman, 1993; Castro *et al.*, 2007; Gilet *et al.*, 2000; Unger *et al.*, 2002; Unger *et al.*, 2006). According to their report, there exist few studies which show how specific cultural values can be or operate as protection against substance use (Castro *et al.*, 2007; Unger *et al.*, 2002; 2006). (

According to Heath (2001), culture plays a central role in forming the expectations of individuals about potential problems they may face with drug use. Substance use and abuse as found to be is rooted in culture of the people. According to Jiloha (2009), drug abuse is a complex phenomenon, which has various social, cultural, biological, geographical, historical and economic aspects. Jiloha further maintained that the disintegration of the old joint family system, absence of parental love and care in modern families where both parents are working, decline of old religious and moral values etc lead to a rise in the number of adolescent drug addicts who take drugs to escape hard realities of life. Clark *et al.* (1997) argued that a young woman in a barrio, ghetto or hollow, who finds herself subjected to sexual demands from older men, role restrictions by the community, or other types of abuse and neglect, may not respond to a policy that immoralizes her behaviour with respect to substance use and stigmatizes her existence. The cultural pressures on adolescent women must be understood in a constructive manner. The adolescent woman who uses psychoactive substances or who is pregnant and uses psychoactive substances must be understood developmentally and contextually (Clark *et al.*, 1997). Cultural aspects of substance abuse cannot be adequately addressed without considering the cultural experiences of substance abusers (Clark *et al.*, 1997). Several studies show that culture plays key role in substance and drug acceptance, drug use and the level of abuse (Guerreroa, and Andrews, 2011; Anderson, 1998; Room, 2013; and Jiloha, 2009).

Culture determines to a large extent what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks in many societies, and the use of any substance in many societies is socially accepted or rejected depending on the socio-cultural values and norms of the people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017) and Jiloha (2009) posit that almost all cultures have used psycho-active drugs to facilitate social interaction, to alter consciousness, and to heal their people. Drugs, for several purposes have been produced within our society, consumed within our society, sold within our society, and shared among the people. Among the internally displaced persons, women used drugs for several purposes (Usoro and Ononokpono, 2019). Inform of setting the moral acceptance for drugs, our society has traditionally adopted some of these drugs and substances for consumption under the cultural norms of the people. Our society's expanded chemical

manipulation simply represents a large technical capacity, more wealth, leisure, individual choice and, conversely, a reduction in constraining social settings, peer and family standards, and personal proscriptions as to what is not done (Jiloha, 2009). Room (2013) posits that in early nineteenth-century America, the most common way of understanding the concept of substance and alcohol addiction is to be historically and culturally specific. McGovern (2009) argued that in India, the consumption of alcoholic beverages started prior to their colonization.

Drug abuse behaviour like human behaviour in general is conceived of as an outcome of genetic and biochemical characteristics, past learning experiences, motivational states, psychosocial antecedents, and cultural context in which it unfolds and these conditions assume a considerable variety in drug-abuse behaviour. Among these, social and cultural factors play an important role in initiation, maintenance and therapeutic intervention of drug-abuse (Jiloha, 2009).

Through cultural acceptability, many cultural human groupings have been practising healing through drug use. Gone and Looking (2011) posit that when it comes to matters of recovery, healing, and wellness in the context of substance use, a contemporary tribal commitment to traditional cultural reclamation and revitalization find continued expression by recent generational cohorts of American Indians who, routinely assert that “our culture is our treatment.” Kunitz and Levy (2000) argued that there exists a prevalence of alcohol dependence among a large sample of South western American Indians which was estimated at 70% as the highest ever reported. This cultural perspective has brought about the rejection of the modern therapy for treatment of illnesses as majority of such population display high level of substance and alcohol abuse traditionally.

According to Lynch and Bonnie (1994), many factors play a part in initiation and maintenance of drug abuse in adolescents. Initiation of drug use is complex. Among these factors, social and cultural factors are major factors with prevalence rate of influence among young people. Jiloha (2009) argued that the social and cultural factors influencing the initiation of tobacco use vary from country to country, from developed world to developing nations, region to region and culture to culture.

Parents are considered to be adults who have undergone cultural socialization. This positioned parents at an influential point over their children in relation to substance and alcohol use and abuse. According to Jiloha (2013), parents have a tremendous influence on their children and the children of smoker parents are twice likely to become smokers. Parental disapproval of smoking makes an adolescent less likely to initiate smoking. Female adolescents are more likely to be smokers if both parents are smokers. There is a strong correlation between mother smoking and the female youth becoming a smoker. Raised in a home where parents smoke exposes the young person to tobacco smoke. Parents who smoke may also give easy access to cigarettes and less likely to oppose their children's smoking. According to Elkind (1985), children are more likely to smoke whose elder siblings are smokers. Cannabis, a traditional drug in Indian society is ritualized in social and religious gatherings. It is a socially sanctioned behaviour in certain cultural groups to use Bhang and Charas by adolescents and has parental approval for that. Parental attitude towards alcohol plays an important role in initiating the adolescent to drink alcohol (Jiloha, 2013). Many studies show that parents as agents of socialization have great role in influencing their children behaviours toward substance and alcohol use and abuse (Conradet *al.*, 1992; Aaroet *al.*, 1981;

Eiser *et al.*, 1989; Elkind, 1985; Jiloha, 2013). Social influences together with local cultural norms are central factors that can influence the use of alcohol (Nwagu, 2017).

Many cultural justifications are given by some cultural setting for substance and alcohol use and abuse. The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009). Natera (1995) argued that in Mexico, alcohol consumption is a part of all aspects of their social and family life in both urban and rural areas. Bennett (1989) posits that alcohol use is evident from birth and baptism to weddings and to funerals. According to Room (2013), there was a shift in American culture at the time of the rise of the temperance movement. And in the context of that movement, it was argued that drinking came into focus as a potential explanation of bad events or behaviour as Americans came to see alcohol as an exceptionally powerful substance that not only made drinkers clumsy but also made them behave in ways in which they would not wish to behave when sober. Alcohol consumption and later addiction in this environment received a cultural acceptability to ease depression and set one out of sober mode.

Nigerian culture of alcohol use and abuse

According to Otile (1990), the culture of Nigeria is shaped by Nigeria's multiple ethnic groups and the country has over 372 languages, seven of them are extinct. Nigeria has major ethnic groups and minor ones. The major ones are considered to be Hausa-Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo. Nigeria's other ethnic groups, sometimes called 'minorities', are found throughout the country but especially in the north and the middle belt. The traditionally nomadic Fulani can be found all over West and Central Africa. The Fulani and the Hausa are predominantly Muslims while the Igbo are predominantly Christian and so are the Efik, Ibibio, and Annang people. The Yoruba are equally likely to be either Christian or Muslim. Indigenous religious practices remain important to all of Nigeria's ethnic groups, and frequently these beliefs are blended with Christian beliefs, a practice known as syncretism. According to Oluwabamide (2003), Nigeria is a plural country with different cultural groupings which include; Hausa-Fulani, Nok, Igbo ukwu, Ife, Nupe, Yako, Tiv, Yoruba and Benin.

Substance and alcohol use and abuse is rooted in the culture of the people of Nigeria. According to Mammanet *al.* (2014), while alcohol and other substances are celebrated in the south, the Northern part of the nation forbids alcohol, but accept cigarettes, kolanut, bitter kola and others. Many ethnic groups in Nigeria culturally accept the use of some substances and alcohol for various purposes. Oluwabamide (2003) posits that different cultural groupings in Nigeria have different ways of practicing traditional health care services. These traditional healings include the use of herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots (Oluwabamide, 2003). Much of these substances are mixed with alcohol which serve as extractive chemical with capacity to extract from the herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots the content which will then serve as drug for treatment. In the course of taking these treatments, many people have developed or cultivated substance and alcohol use and abuse behaviour. Traditional health care providers and their practices are culturally accepted by the Nigerian society. In some parts of the cultural area where alcohol is not religiously accepted, some people take alcohol as medicine for treatment of some illness through patronage of traditional health care giver.

Dumbili (2013) argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly

during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. During such occasions, palm wine and hot drinks are specifically used in pouring libations, offering prayers and heralding such events. Among the most commonly consumed alcoholic beverages are; palm wine–fermented from the sap of oil palm tree, beer, *burukutu*–fermented from guinea-corn and native gin–distilled from palm wine (Oshodin, 1995). Nigerian in 2010 had a total alcohol per capita (15+) consumption of 23.1 litres of pure alcohol among male and female drinkers. This did not include the large quantity of homemade alcohol consumed which usually goes unrecorded (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

While low to moderate consumption of alcoholic beverages may not cause any harm to the drinker, heavy and uncontrolled consumption, especially among young people predispose drinkers to numerous health challenges (WHO, 2014). Drinking in any community can, however, be influenced by the social and cultural norms of the community. If community members are properly guided, they can play useful roles in controlling alcohol abuse, hence preventing alcohol problems, particularly among the young people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to a study conducted in Enugu Ezike by Nwagu *et al.* (2017), palm wine is a major source of income for the community, and young men and older men are involved in tapping wine. Many young people at one time or the other depended on the income from palm wine for their daily needs, including education. Many developing countries are highly dependent on national revenues from alcohol. Individuals in many rural communities in such countries also depend on income from homemade alcoholic beverage such as palm wine. It is, however, worthy to note that when production of such homemade alcoholic beverages increases in a bid to increase income by producers, the consumption also increases (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Palm wine produced in many rural communities is a perishable commodity which needs to be consumed or it spoils. Members of Enugu Ezike produce and consume palm wine in large quantities. Some researchers have noted that in many developing countries, alcohol is often more readily available than clean drinking water. This seems to be the case in Enugu Ezike where this study was conducted (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

Nwagu *et al.* (2017) further observed that, consumption of alcohol particularly palm wine by members of the community is therefore generally seen as normal. The community only frowns at the abuse of alcohol which to members is drinking to the point that one cannot control himself or herself. It is, however, wrong to believe that it is only when an individual cannot control himself or herself after drinking that alcohol has been abused. People's definitions of what 'normal' and 'harmful' drinking are, can be used to assess and compare their attitudes about alcohol consumption with that of other communities. Drinking to a level that is harmful to the body irrespective of the drinker's apparent coordination of his or her actions after the drinking is also abuse. Drinking by women and young people in this community did not receive equal approval like drinking by men. Sometimes drinking by children and women are disapproval by some people in the community. Double standard with respect to drinking is common in many societies. In many societies, men are expected to drink, and the ability to drink large quantities may be considered 'macho' (Nwagu *et al.* 2017).

According to Abdu-Raheem (2013), it has also been noted in Nigeria that parents, peer groups, and society at large contribute to the alarming rate of drug abuse among the secondary school students. Alan (2003) argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological

(to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. He further stressed that despite the fact that drug abuse has adverse effects on the youth involved by changing their brain perception of difficulties and problems, the number of undergraduates that use or abuse stimulants has steadily increased in recent years.

Chikere and Mayowa (2011) found that in a number of school and college surveys in Nigeria, alcohol use is the most common among students, with many drinking students having had their first drink in family settings. They also discovered that the majority of students affected were initiated into the use of alcohol at a tender age of 16-20 years. Abdu-Raheem (2013) maintained that in an attempt to control sleep or energise themselves, most adolescents and young ones start experimenting with tobacco, alcohol, ephedrine and other caffeinated substances such as Nescafe and red bull. Some of the reasons for the drug abuse, as identified by Ajayi and Ekundayo (2010), are to reduce pain, anxiety and tension, ignorance and misinformation, parental background, urge to commit crimes, peer group influence, isolation and loneliness. Linhardt (2001) also noted that students see the use of stimulants in positive terms for relief from pain and problems, elevation of mood, wakefulness, increased confidence, feeling and psychomotor activities and athletics, and feeling of euphoria. McCrystal *et al.* (2007) confirmed that for many adolescents, drug abuse has now become a part of their lives and perhaps may have now contributed to their academic failure.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Cultural Influence on Youths' Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour (Peters, 2019)

The youths within a certain age cohort (culturally defined as young adults and adolescents between the age of 50 years and below), and mostly of males though females are included, through communication or interaction with other members of the age group, with

time develop learned behaviour of drugs and psychoactive substance abuse due to engagement in traditional rites and cultural acceptability of psychoactive substances as part of traditional requirements for cultural activities and traditional rites. This has been prevalent in all societies across the world whether traditional or modernized society, where culture has played acceptable roles of what is acceptable as drinks and foods within the society or community.

The principles of Cultural Influence of Youths' Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour (Peters, 2019) are:

- i. Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour is acquired through learning social behaviour as part of cultural prescriptions which later generates new behaviours acquired by observing and imitating others.
- ii. Youths come to have differential access to certain Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour through interaction with other people in the community/society as defined by traditionally accepted codes and cultural practices of the elders or elites.
- iii. Youths build and develop behaviour through relationships within communities and the wider society which they found themselves.

The culture of alcohol abuse is socially learned by the Iman Ibom youth in Etinan Local Government Area through culturally prescribed youth's items which are authorized for youth's consumption by the elders as part of rights in case of traditional rite.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers adopted ethnographic research design for the study which involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. The study was conducted in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Etinan Local Government Area was divided by cluster into Iman North and Iman South based on the existing geo-political divides. 6 villages were purposively selected, 3 from each cluster within Iman North and Iman South based on their homogeneous characteristics. The Fetterman's Big-net approach was used to randomly select study participants from each of the purposively selected villages. Data were collected through the use of interview schedule. Methods of data collection include; key informant interview, participant observation, respondent driven interview, and direct interview. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts.

RESULT

Traditional rites and psychoactive drug abuse

Traditional practices have created avenues for psychoactive drug abuse among the youths of Etinan local Government Area. Participants emphasized the role of list content of traditional marriage requirement as key cultural provisions for alcoholic and psychoactive substance abuse among the youths in Etinan Local Government Area. They agreed that there are such items like illicit gin, schnapps, different brands of hot drink, tobacco leaves, grinded snuff, beer of different brands, palm wine, and petrol cannot be excluded from the traditional marriage requirement list for any reasons what so ever.

One of the Key Informants participants aged 57 years explained:

There are some items you cannot take out of our traditional marriage requirement list. If you do, then it is no longer Etinan traditional marriage requirement list. Let me tell you, presenting traditional marriage list without those items will look as if you are a stranger to our customs. Those items like illicit gin, palm wine, tobacco, snuff, hot drinks, and beer, are what make the marital requirement list traditional and celebrative. This is because, everything other items like the cloths and bride price belong to the parents, but these other items are what the parents do share with the people and youths also have their own share. Therefore, if the youths abuse their own share which is what we have observed these days, that is their own issues and I know that they now know what the consequences are (Obong J. Male, 57years, interviewed on 12/9/2023).

As part of observation and interview, the youths are given a special section of the traditional marriage requirement with items that are capable of intoxicating them. It was gathered by the researcher that there is a part of the traditional marriage requirement list which is referred to as “Nkpo Iwaad” otherwise translated as “Youths' Items”. This section of the list contains items like cigarettes of different brands, grinded snuff (tobacco), kolanut, illicit gin, hot drink, beer, palm wine, and other items. The youths have over the years and generations, collected such items as the part of their requirement for giving out one of their own out in marriage.

One of the study participants from focus group discussion aged 47 years revealed that these items or sections of the list is very important if at all anyone wants to marry from any family in Etinan Local Government Area:

Youths' items are an important part of the list. This is so because, if the groom's family does not pay everything as contain in the list either before the day of the traditional marriage or on the arrival of the groom's family for the traditional marriage, the youths of that community will come out and block the entrance to the bride's family compound against the groom and his family on the marriage day. The youths have since been involved in the consumption of these items as morally accepted items (Aslia, female, 54 years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

Discussion on burial rites and drug abuse revealed that there are many aspects of burial ceremonies of Iman Ibom people which include “ntord” (reporting to different parties which include; siblings, in-laws, immediate family, major/extended family, and the village as the case may demands), “ubede ufok ikpo” (opening of funeral home), “ubobndak” (building of traditional tent), “Ubonkpo” (collection of levy), “usuan ufok ikpo” (closing of funeral home) and “ukpok ndak” (losing and scattering of traditional tent).

These sub-cultural complexes of Iman Ibom people burial rites according to gathered information through interview, unveil the cultural practices promote alcohol and tobacco and other psychoactive substances consumption. Study participants explained that illicit gin, palm

wine, beer, tobacco, hot drinks and other items are collected through assessment list from in-laws and relatives. In other cases, these items are bought for consumption by the bereaved family through assessment money from immediate relatives or family members.

A participant aged 42 years explained in his narratives how alcohol and psychoactive substances are collected and shared among the people during burial ceremonies. According to him:

In our community we collect illicit gin, palm wine, hot drinks and other food items from our in-laws and other relatives through what we call assessment. These items are used for entertainment during the burial rites. These items are consumed by our people according to the cultural grouping of people during the burial ceremonies. The youths (iwaad) are always given their special place and entertained with items like beer, illicit gin, hot drink, palm wine, and food items. This is tradition which is carried out all over Iman Ibom is customized to be right by our forefathers, and there is nothing wrong with it (Uk, male, 42 years, interviewed 12/9/2023).

Traditional marriage ceremonies have been a custom among Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area as a grand celebration of giving out Iman Ibom daughter out in marriage by the family concern. Study participants explained that traditional marriage ceremony can be in-door or out-door depending on the financial capacity of the groom and the groom's family. During burial ceremonies in Etinan Local Government Area, Iman Ibom people performed several burial rites which according to the study participants include “ububndak” (building of traditional tent). From observation and discussion, this particular burial rite traditionally takes place 2 days or a day to the burial ceremony. By observation, this has served as an opportunity for youths to abuse alcohol and psychoactive substances.

Culture of alcohol and psychoactive drug abuse in forcing shift of moral boundaries

Information gathered through key informant interview revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by traditional practices for their selfish interest. These youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rites to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional events.

Like in the case of “ububndak” (building of traditional tent) as burial rites, the community leader as one of the Key Informants had this to say:

This ububndak was a tradition of our people in those days when there was nothing like canopies and tent for rent as we have today. I remember when I was a child, our fathers did not have formalin to embalm their dead, so they will keep the dead body standing at the corner of the room, pour a bottle of original illicit gin not the chemical they drink today oh, into the dead body through the mouth and closed the mouth thereafter. The body will stay for 3 – 4 days without decay. This is when family and community members will come for ububndak. This traditional tent was to create a shed

against the sun or reduce the pressure of rain water during the burial ceremony. It was traditionally customized that the bereaved family will bring food and drinks that they can afford but today, the youths have come out with list of items they must collect for *ububndak* and this include all these substances that make them high so that they can work very well according to them. I have been mobilizing for the abolition of *ububndak* in my community, but the youths are also mobilizing against my motion on this which is why I say that the youths are no more respectful of the elders especially when they drink these substances. They will begin to insult people and if control is not enforcing by God's grace, sometimes they quarrel among themselves or with the elders. (Obong A. male, 75 years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

On “*ukpokndak*” (scattering or pulling down of the traditional tent), the tradition is facing elimination in some parts of Northern Iman region of Etinan Local Government Area as some elders in the most communities are mobilizing against the abuse of the practices by the community youths. This tradition according to discussion has it that after the burial ceremony, a day will be set aside by the bereaved family for the family and community to come and pull down or scatter the traditional tent. This cultural practice is accompanied with presentation of food and alcoholic drinks (like illicit gin, beer, hot drink). Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted there shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenue to showcase conflicting social behaviours which were not morally prescribed by the elders.

According to the key informant;

Ukpokndak should be abolished among my people. This is my stand. I have said it again and again. My stand is because the youths have used this practice to make unnecessary demands for items that are beyond our moral standard. You cannot come to “*ukpokndak*” with marijuana in our fathers' days. But today, they will come with marijuana, demand for cigarettes, look for how they can mix these psychoactive leaves with *kaikai* (illicit gin), and at the end they will be over high and start insult their elders in any little case. So I have influenced the dismantling of the tent immediately after burial on the same day with only a bottle of *kaikai* and I am still pushing on with it. By God's grace we will abolish that practice (Obong S. male, 70years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

The people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State have culturally prescribed codes and traditional rites of passage for youths. These have defined what is accepted by the society and what is not accepted. The provision of psychoactive substance for youths as traditional requirements for traditional rites as part of the culture of the people, have created avenue for the youths to abuse psychoactive substances and drugs during traditional activities and as part of normal youthful life by some youths. Gathered data have shown that the youths have seize such traditional rights to force expansion of culture boundaries for

inclusion other substances which some are traditionally produced with local herbs and under such anti-social behaviour, the youths have become deviants in the society.

Culture of alcohol and psychoactive drug abuse on distorted cultural values by youths

The influence of some cultural practices on the lives of the youths as gathered by the researchers is in the creation of avenue for psychoactive drug and alcohol abuse. Most of the youths are looking for any available avenue created by cultural events where drinks and food are shared for them to cease it as an opportunity to consume alcohol and psychoactive substances and drugs. Gathered information through observations and interviews revealed that most of the youths in Iman Ibom Clan, Etinan Local Government Area sees traditional rites items which include alcohol, raw tobacco, petrol, cigarettes, snuff and other illicit substances as licence for abuse of psychoactive substances and distortion of cultural values. Participants of the study through interview agreed that most of the youths of Etinan Local Government Area have used the provisions of traditional rights as measure for consuming psychoactive substances which according to gathered data are responsible for their anti-social behaviour which the youths are living today.

One of the study participants during interview said that;

Most of our youths have no respect for elders today as a result of what they are taking which are these ikpo and other things that make them high. You will see a young boy of 13 years behaving and talking to his senior with disrespect as if he is as old as the person he is talking to. This is because when they talk those things, they see everybody as equal and they will insult their elders. This is not how we used to live while we were young in our days. We were taught respect and honour to the elders and your senior. In our days, you dare not touch what does not belong to you. But today, these small small boys do not consider these morals again. They have decided to reck our society because of these things they smoke and drink. And you can't blame them because it is the elders that accepted those "mkpomkparawa" for them which are all illicit and can control their brain. I pray God help us with our upcoming children else, I have fear for what our society will be in the future (Akan, Male, 49years, interviewed on 12/8/2023).

Gathered information through interviews and observation have shown that the community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural value to what is today seen as anti-value or distorted value life styles by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. Youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and substance abuse deviate from the societal accepted codes of conducts and practices.

One of the participants from focus group discussion, in her responses reported that;
These substances that our youths take these days have really done to us much evil because we are losing our children and crime rate

seems to be increasing within our homes. We now have children who talk back to their parents, some even fight their parents, some will even curse and abuse their parents, some are even fighting among themselves as sibling with cutlass. Some fought until they destroyed what was supposed to be their inheritance from their father. What is the cause? These things that they smoke and drink everyday which we did not see or use these kind things during our days. But now, a girl is not a girl, you will see them form gangs and share these items among themselves. When these things start to harm them, they will begin to cause trouble even from their family. It is a pity that the world has spoiled and children are no more children again. Today you see them do things that when we were of their age we couldn't do such things. But these things are making high and they misbehave (Abee, female, 52 years interviewed on 12/8/2022)

Another study participant as a youth said that:

We should know that the world has changed and we are no more in those old school days. Everything has changed and we have to change along. Sir, if you don't change along the world will leave you behind. We are not taking things that the elders are not talking. In fact, we are learning from them. Sir, let me tell you, you do not know what those leaders take but they will not want us to take. Why? We are human beings too and our blood is even stronger than their own. But when you see us make trouble, it is because the elders want to rob us of our rights and we want to enforce our right so that they will not cheat us (Stev, male, 26 years, interviewed on 12/8/2023)

Values are prescribed by culture and traditional rites are mediums through which culture are coded, preserved and transferred from one generation to another. These values are prescribed by the elders of the society as custodians of customs and traditions. When the elders prescribed psychoactive substances for the youths as traditional rights, the youths as found among the people of Etinan Local Government Area through interviews revealed that most youths through the influence of psychoactive substances have changed and falsified the cultural value of the people of Etinan Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is that cultural practices like traditional marriage ceremony and burial ceremony create an avenue for psychoactive substance abuse among the youths of Etinan Local Government Area. Findings of the study show that traditional marriage requirements play a pivotal point in the traditional marriage ceremony among the people of Etinan Local Government Area. The researcher discovered through findings that alcohol and psychoactive substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and petrol are contained in the traditional marriage list of the people of Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Nwagu (2017) gives credence to the findings from this study when he reported that

there are local cultural norms that are central factors and can influence the use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances (Nwagu, 2017). It was further noted that collection of these psychoactive substances as part of traditional marriage requirements in giving out their daughters in marriage, is regarded as tradition which had been laid down by their ancestors, and had been upheld from generation to generations. Further findings show that the youths found the cultural acceptability of these psychoactive substances by their fathers as moral licence to drink alcohol, smoke cigarettes, consume marijuana, inhale tobacco in form of snuff, and produce new psychoactive liquor called “brew” (a mixture of kaikai, palm wine, marijuana, tramadol, lemon grass, and hollandia yogurt).

Findings of the study also revealed that burial rites are performed along with alcohol and psychoactive substances by the people of Iman Ibom clan, in Etinan Local Government Area. Findings on burial ceremony show that the youths (Iwaad) are greatly involved in the burial activities and have influenced the items which they must be given as “Mkpo Mkparawa” (youth's items). These items according to findings contain alcohol and other psychoactive substances which are traditionally accepted and as the custom of the people to give such items to the youths during burial rite such as in “ububndak” (building of traditional tent), “ukpokndak” (dismantling or pulling down of the traditional tent), and on the burial day. Dumbili (2013) give credence to the findings when argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009).

Emergence of the study further revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by traditional practices for their selfish interest. The youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rights to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional rites. Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted thereby shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenue to showcase conflicting social behaviours which were not morally prescribed by the elders. Alan (2003) give credence to the findings when he argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological (to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. Findings of the study also revealed that community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural value to what is today seen as anti-value or distorted value life styles by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. It was discovered that some youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and substance abuse deviate from the societal accepted codes of conducts and practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper sought to examine the roles of youths in twisting communal values through engagement in alcohol and drug abuse on the basis of traditional rites as cultural heritage of Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Youths of Iman Ibom people are given traditional rights to consume psychoactive substances as part of traditional rites by the elders of the communities. Youths have seized the opportunity given to them by these traditional rights as chance to expand the cultural boundaries by making further demands for other illicit substances and also create some locally for their consumption. The consumption of these substances has brought about deviant and anti-social behaviours like theft, stealing, assaults and other such vices. Youths have forced changes in the cultural and moral life style of the people through the chance of consuming psychoactive substances which are allocated to them as traditional rights. The society is facing a shift through the deviants' life of youth as a result of influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse. The implication of this is that what was tend to be culturally good have turn to become avenue of abuse and roots of anti-social behaviour which have led to distorted cultural values among the youths of Iman Ibom people in Etinan Local Government Area.

In order to rescue the future and the soul of the society, and reduce damages to the health condition of the youths in the society, researchers make case for culture-mediated regulation of illicit drinks among traditional items that are culturally approved for youths during rites observances, and rural orientations on dangers of drug and psychoactive substance abuse.

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